

Simulation of Security Configuration Assessment (SCA) Wazuh for Compliance Monitoring Using CIS Benchmark Standard on Ubuntu Server

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BAB I. Methodology

1.1 Framework of Thinking

The framework of thinking in this research aims to ensure that the research carried out is effective and structured when the research is carried out.

Figure 1.1 Framework of Thinking Research

As can be seen in Figure 3.1, there are 6 phases of the framework, namely Preparation of Tools and Materials, System design, System installation, Remediation, Analysis and evaluation and Result, these stages have been adjusted to the needs of the research to be carried out.

1.2 Preparation of Tools and Materials

At this stage, namely preparing the hardware and software used in conducting research. For the hardware that will be used to support the virtual simulation of the research, namely using an Asus Zenbook 14X laptop with the following specifications:

Component	Spesification
Processor	Intel® Core™ i9-12900H Processor 2.5 GHz
Intergrated GPU	Intel Iris X ^e Graphics
System Memory	32GB LPDDR5 on board
Storage	1TB M.2 NVMe™ PCIe® 4.0 Performance
Operating System	Windows 11 Home

Table 1.1 Hardware Specifications

The software used in this research is:

Name <i>Software</i>	Version
Wazuh Manager	4.11
Wazuh Agent	4.11
Oracle Virtualbox	7.1.6
Ubuntu Server	22.04 LTS

Table 1.2 Software Version

1.2.1 Wazuh Manager

In this study, wazuh manager version 4.11 was chosen as the main platform to support the implementation of the Security Configuration Assessment configuration. Wazuh manager provides an SCA module that functions to automatically evaluate system configurations based on security policies such as CIS Benchmark. The module can identify configuration inconsistencies, provide remediation recommendations, and automatically report compliance. Version 4.11 brings improvements in terms of detection accuracy, flexibility, custom rule creation, and management of assessment results.

1.2.2 Wazuh Agent

Wazuh Agent 4.11 is installed on an endpoint to run the Security Configuration Assessment (SCA) process locally. The agent is tasked with collecting configuration

information on the system, comparing it with applicable policies such as CIS Benchmark, and sending the evaluation results to Wazuh Manager for further analysis. Using the same version as wazuh manager 4.11, aims to minimize incompatibility between wazuh agent and wazuh manager. In addition, version 4.11 already supports SCA scanning.

1.2.3 Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS

In this study, Ubuntu Server 22.04 was chosen as the primary operating system because it offers high stability and long-term update support for five years. Ubuntu Server is also one of the operating systems fully supported by Wazuh, both for manager and agent installations, and has a user community and official documentation that is easy to obtain, making it easy to troubleshoot if a problem occurs.

1.2.4 Oracle Virtualbox

Oracle Virtualbox was chosen as the virtualization platform in this study, because it has flexible capabilities in supporting various operating systems, such as Windows, Linux and MacOS. In addition, virtualbox also provides other supporting features such as Snapshot, virtual machine cloning, resource management such as CPU, memory and storage that are easy to do. Other considerations are the open-source nature and compatibility of Virtualbox with various Linux distributions, including Ubuntu Server 22.04, so choosing Virtualbox as a virtualization platform is the right choice.

1.3 System Design

At this stage, the researcher designs the architecture that will be created in the research process and explains how the system works.

1.3.1 System Architecture

The system architecture in this study is designed to support the implementation process of Security Configuration Assessment (SCA). This system consists of 3 main components, namely Wazuh Agent, Wazuh Manager and Wazuh Dashboard, each of which has a specific role in the SCA workflow.

1.3.2 Wazuh Agent

Wazuh Agent is installed on the target server, namely Ubuntu Server 22.04, to run the system configuration scanning process. Wazuh Agent receives SCA rules distributed by Wazuh Manager, then wazuh agent performs a local check on the configuration on

the system. The check includes testing various security aspects such as permission settings, service configuration, authentication, logging and networking.

1.3.3 Wazuh Manager

Wazuh Manager functions as a center for agent management and processing assessment data results, such as distributing SCA rules to Wazuh Agent, receiving SCA configuration scanning results from agents, then managing the assessment results by storing, processing and classifying the results based on the level of compliance or non-compliance with security standards such as CIS Benchmark.

1.3.4 Wazuh Dashboard

Wazuh Dashboard is used to visualize Security Configuration Assessment (SCA) results data. Through this dashboard, you can see a summary of the system's compliance level, detect inappropriate configurations, and monitor improvements that have been made. This dashboard also makes it easy to track remediation progress through filtering and reporting.

Figure 1.1 System Design

1.3.5 System Workflow

Based on Figure 3.2, the workflow of the Security Configuration Assessment system can be explained as follows:

1. Distribute Rules SCA

Wazuh Manager sends a collection of SCA rules that have been adjusted to the existing operating system to Wazuh Agent.

2. Perform Scan SCA

After receiving the rules, Wazuh Agent performs a scanning process on the system configuration according to the list of rules IDs provided. The agent will

evaluate whether the server configuration is in accordance with the provisions or not.

3. Sending Result SCA

After the scanning process is complete, Wazuh Agent sends the assessment results to Wazuh Manager, regarding how much of the system configuration is in compliance and how much is not in compliance.

4. Visualization Data

Wazuh Manager then processes the results received and forwards them to the Wazuh Dashboard for the data to be visualized in the form of tables, graphs and summary reports to facilitate analysis.

1.4 System Installation

The system architecture in this study is designed to support the implementation process of Security Configuration Assessment (SCA). This system consists of 3 main components, namely Wazuh Agent, Wazuh Manager and Wazuh Dashboard, each of which has a specific role in the SCA workflow.

1.4.1 Install Wazuh Manager

Wazuh Manager is the main component that is responsible for managing agents, processing scan data results and distributing SCA rules. The installation steps are as follows:

1. Perform an update to update the list of packages available on the Ubuntu server system from the software repository.
2. Download and install Wazuh Manager through the official Wazuh repository.
3. Run and verify the services required by Wazuh Manager to ensure that the system is active.

1.4.2 Install Wazuh Agent

Wazuh Agent is installed on the target server that will be assessed for its configuration, namely Ubuntu server 22.04. The wazuh agent installation process is carried out as follows:

1. Performing an update to update the list of packages available on the Ubuntu server system from the software repository.
2. Downloading and installing the Wazuh agent from the official repository.

3. Configuring the agent to direct the Wazuh Manager IP Address as the central server.
4. Checking the wazuh agent service status and ensuring that the connection is connected to the wazuh manager.

1.4.3 Configuration Security Configuration Assessment

At this stage, the configuration is done to support the configuration scanning process carried out by the Wazuh agent to run. The following are the SCA configuration stages carried out:

1. Activate the SCA module on the wazuh agent side, in the wazuh agent configuration directory.
2. After the module is active, reload the wazuh-agent service so that the configuration changes are successfully implemented.
3. Monitor the ossec.conf log to ensure that the initial Security Configuration Assessment scan process is running normally

1.5 Remediation

After completing the module configuration in the Security Configuration Assessment (SCA), the next step is to perform Remediation on findings that do not comply with security standards. This remediation stage aims to improve the system configuration to comply with the standard policy used, namely the CIS Benchmark, it is labeled as failed if it does not comply with the standard which will then be fixed so that the status changes to passed.

1.6 Analysis and Evaluation

After the remediation stage is carried out, the next process is to analyze and evaluate the configuration that has been carried out in accordance with the CIS Benchmark standard along with identifying potential technical constraints that may arise during the remediation process. This stage also includes identifying rules that have similar or overlapping functions, so a strategy is needed to select a relevant configuration approach. Then for the evaluation process, several alternative configuration scenarios will be developed that have been adjusted from the results of the analysis that has been carried out. Testing Results and Conclusions

1.7 Result

At this stage, after the Analysis and evaluation have been carried out, namely providing overall results about the results of the remediation that has been carried out. The results of this stage will be an overall evaluation of the Rule ID that has been remediated in the system.

BAB II. Result and Discussion

2.1 Installing System

Before installing the system, prepare the tools and materials along with the design plan that will be used in this research simulation. For hardware preparation, refer to Table 1.1 and the software used refers to Table 1.2, then for the reference system design carried out in this study, refer to Figure 1.1. After preparing the tools and materials and design plan, the next step is to install the system, namely the Wazuh Manager Installation, Wazuh Agent and perform the Security Configuration Assessment (SCA) Configuration.

2.1.1 Installation Wazuh Manager

The Wazuh Manager was installed virtually using VirtualBox with the Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS operating system. The first step in the Wazuh Manager installation process is as follows:

- A. Ensure that the available packages in the repository are updated beforehand to guarantee that all packages are in their latest and stable versions. The command executed is “apt-get update & upgrade”.

```
root@Wazuh-Manager:/home/Iilham# apt-get update && apt-get upgrade
Hit:1 https://packages.wazuh.com/4.x/apt stable InRelease
Hit:2 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy InRelease
Get:3 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy-updates InRelease [128 kB]
Get:4 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy-security InRelease [129 kB]
Hit:5 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy-backports InRelease
```

Figure 2.1 Update Package System

Based on Figure 2.1, the update and upgrade processes have been performed on the Ubuntu Server 22.04 operating system. This step aims to prevent dependency conflicts and to ensure a smooth installation process on an up-to-date system.

- B. The next step involves downloading and installing the Wazuh Manager package by executing the command `curl -sO https://packages.wazuh.com/4.11/wazuh-install.sh && bash ./wazuh-install.sh -a`.

```

root@Wazuh-Manager:/home/Ilham# curl -sO https://packages.wazuh.com/4.11/wazuh-install.sh && bash ./
wazuh-install.sh -a
05/03/2025 01:22:44 INFO: Starting Wazuh installation assistant. Wazuh version: 4.11.0 (x86_64/AMD64)
05/03/2025 01:22:44 INFO: Verbose logging redirected to /var/log/wazuh-install.log
05/03/2025 01:23:05 INFO: Verifying that your system meets the recommended minimum hardware requirements.
05/03/2025 01:23:05 INFO: Wazuh web interface port will be 443.

```

Figure 2.2 Download and Install Package Wazuh

In Figure 2.2, the process of downloading and installing the Wazuh package from the official link. The installation package already includes the Wazuh Indexer and Wazuh Dashboard components. By using the official repository, the system obtains a more stable version with verified file integrity.

- C. After the Wazuh Manager has been downloaded and installed, the next step is to start the installed Wazuh Manager service. This can be done by executing the commands “systemctl daemon-reload”, “systemctl enable wazuh-manager”, and “systemctl start wazuh-manager”.

```

root@Wazuh-Manager:/home/Ilham# systemctl daemon-reload
root@Wazuh-Manager:/home/Ilham# systemctl enable wazuh-manager
root@Wazuh-Manager:/home/Ilham# systemctl start wazuh-manager

```

Figure 2.3 Start Service Wazuh Manager

- D. Based on Figure 2.3, after the Wazuh Manager service is activated, the next step is to verify the status of the service to ensure it is running properly. There are three components that need to be monitored to ensure the Wazuh Manager service functions correctly: the Wazuh Manager, the Wazuh Indexer, and the Wazuh Dashboard.

```

root@Wazuh-Manager:/home/Ilham# systemctl status wazuh-manager
● wazuh-manager.service - Wazuh manager
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/wazuh-manager.service; enabled; vendor preset: enabled)
   Active: active (running) since Wed 2025-04-30 19:55:04 WIB; 24min ago
     Process: 4174 ExecStart=/usr/bin/env /var/ossec/bin/wazuh-control start (code=exited, status=0/0)
    Tasks: 154 (limit: 4562)
     Memory: 1.3G
        CPU: 19.567s
   CGroup: /system.slice/wazuh-manager.service
           └─1116 /var/ossec/framework/python/bin/python3 /var/ossec/api/scripts/wazuh_apid.py
           └─1117 /var/ossec/framework/python/bin/python3 /var/ossec/api/scripts/wazuh_apid.py
           └─1121 /var/ossec/framework/python/bin/python3 /var/ossec/api/scripts/wazuh_apid.py
           └─1123 /var/ossec/framework/python/bin/python3 /var/ossec/api/scripts/wazuh_apid.py
           └─1172 /var/ossec/bin/wazuh-authd
           └─1251 /var/ossec/bin/wazuh-db
           └─1305 /var/ossec/bin/wazuh-execd
           └─1341 /var/ossec/bin/wazuh-analysisd
           └─1370 /var/ossec/bin/wazuh-syscheckd

```

Figure 2.4 Status Wazuh Manager

Based on Figure 2.4, a status check of the Wazuh Manager was performed using the command `systemctl status wazuh-manager`, and the service status was confirmed to be normal, indicated by 'active (running)'.

```
root@Wazuh-Manager:/home/Ilham# systemctl status wazuh-dashboard
● wazuh-dashboard.service - wazuh-dashboard
   Loaded: loaded (/etc/systemd/system/wazuh-dashboard.service; enabled; vendor preset: enabled)
   Active: active (running) since Wed 2025-04-30 18:09:22 WIB; 2h 9min ago
     Main PID: 659 (node)
        Tasks: 11 (limit: 4562)
       Memory: 208.0M
          CPU: 1min 49.127s
      CGroup: /system.slice/wazuh-dashboard.service
             └─659 /usr/share/wazuh-dashboard/node/bin/node --no-warnings --max-http-header-size=65536
```

Figure 2.5 Status Wazuh Dashboard

As shown in Figure 2.5, the status of the Wazuh Dashboard service was checked using the command `systemctl status wazuh-dashboard`, confirming that the service is operating normally with a status of 'active (running)'.

```
root@Wazuh-Manager:/home/Ilham# systemctl status wazuh-indexer
● wazuh-indexer.service - wazuh-indexer
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/wazuh-indexer.service; enabled; vendor preset: enabled)
   Active: active (running) since Wed 2025-04-30 20:18:45 WIB; 47s ago
     Docs: https://documentation.wazuh.com
     Main PID: 4354 (java)
        Tasks: 115 (limit: 4562)
       Memory: 1.5G
          CPU: 1min 6.378s
      CGroup: /system.slice/wazuh-indexer.service
             └─4354 /usr/share/wazuh-indexer/jdk/bin/java -Xshare:auto -Dopensearch.networkaddress=
```

Figure 2.6 Status Wazuh Indexer

Based on Figure 2.6, a status check of the Wazuh Indexer was performed using the command `systemctl status wazuh-indexer`, and the service status was confirmed to be normal, indicated by “active (running)”.

2.1.2 Installation Wazuh Agent

After installing the Wazuh Manager, the next step is to install the Wazuh Agent. The Wazuh Agent is installed virtually using VirtualBox with the Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS operating system. In this phase, besides installation, basic configuration of the Wazuh Agent is performed to enable connection with the Wazuh Manager. Once the configuration is complete, the agent service is started and ensured to be running normally. The following are the steps involved in the Wazuh Agent installation process:

- A. The first step in the Wazuh Agent installation process, similar to the Wazuh Manager, is to ensure that the packages available in the repository are updated

beforehand to guarantee that all packages are in their latest and stable versions.

The command executed is “apt-get update & apt-get upgrade”.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Illam-WazuhAgent# apt-get update && apt-get upgrade
Hit:1 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy InRelease
Hit:2 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy-updates InRelease
Hit:3 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy-security InRelease
Hit:4 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy-backports InRelease
Reading package lists... Done
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
```

Figure 2.7 Update Package System

Based on Figure 2.7, the update and upgrade processes on the system have been successfully completed.

- B. The next step is to download the Wazuh Agent and install the Wazuh Agent service using the command “wget https://packages.wazuh.com/4.x/apt/pool/main/w/wazuh-agent/wazuh-agent_4.11.0-1_amd64.deb && dpkg -i ./wazuh-agent_4.11.0-1_amd64.deb”. The Wazuh Agent installation source is taken from the official Wazuh repository to maintain the integrity of the installation package.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Illam-WazuhAgent# wget https://packages.wazuh.com/4.x/apt/pool/main/w/wazuh-agent/wazuh-agent_4.11.0-1_amd64.deb && dpkg -i ./wazuh-agent_4.11.0-1_amd64.deb
--2025-04-30 21:50:00-- https://packages.wazuh.com/4.x/apt/pool/main/w/wazuh-agent/wazuh-agent_4.11.0-1_amd64.deb
Resolving packages.wazuh.com (packages.wazuh.com)... 108.138.141.96, 108.138.141.104, 108.138.141.97, ...
Connecting to packages.wazuh.com (packages.wazuh.com)|108.138.141.96|:443... connected.
HTTP request sent, awaiting response... 200 OK
Length: 11078824 (11M) [application/vnd.debian.binary-package]
Saving to: 'wazuh-agent_4.11.0-1_amd64.deb.3'

wazuh-agent_4.11.0-1_amd 100%[=====] 10.57M 6.07MB/s in 1.7s
2025-04-30 21:50:02 (6.07 MB/s) - 'wazuh-agent_4.11.0-1_amd64.deb.3' saved [11078824/11078824]
```

Figure 2.8 Download and Install Package Wazuh Agent

As shown in Figure 2.8, the process of downloading and installing the Wazuh Agent has been successfully carried out.

- C. After successfully installing the Wazuh Agent, the next step is to start the Wazuh Agent service by executing the commands `systemctl daemon-reload`, `systemctl enable wazuh-agent`, and `systemctl start wazuh-agent`.

```
root@UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent:/home/Illam-WazuhAgent# systemctl daemon-reload
root@UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent:/home/Illam-WazuhAgent# systemctl enable wazuh-agent
Created symlink /etc/systemd/system/multi-user.target.wants/wazuh-agent.service → /lib/systemd/system/wazuh-agent.service.
root@UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent:/home/Illam-WazuhAgent# systemctl start wazuh-agent
root@UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent:/home/Illam-WazuhAgent# _
```

Figure 2.9 Status Services Wazuh Agent

Based on Figure 2.9, the commands to start the Wazuh Agent service were executed, and no issues were encountered during the activation process.

- D. At this stage, after the Wazuh Agent service has been activated, a verification is performed to ensure that the Wazuh Agent is running normally by using the command “systemctl status wazuh-agent”.

```
root@UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl status wazuh-agent
● wazuh-agent.service - Wazuh agent
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/wazuh-agent.service; enabled; vendor preset: enabled)
   Active: active (running) since Thu 2025-03-06 22:37:32 WIB; 40s ago
     Process: 2705 ExecStart=/usr/bin/env /var/ossec/bin/wazuh-control start (code=exited, status=0/...)
    Tasks: 33 (limit: 4562)
   Memory: 362.2M
     CPU: 35.219s
   CGroup: /system.slice/wazuh-agent.service
           └─3314 /var/ossec/bin/wazuh-execd
             └─3325 /var/ossec/bin/wazuh-agentd
               └─3339 /var/ossec/bin/wazuh-syscheckd
                 └─3353 /var/ossec/bin/wazuh-logcollector
                   └─3370 /var/ossec/bin/wazuh-modulesd

Mar 06 22:37:25 UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent systemd[1]: Starting Wazuh agent...
Mar 06 22:37:25 UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent env[2705]: Starting Wazuh v4.11.0...
Mar 06 22:37:26 UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent env[2705]: Started wazuh-execd...
Mar 06 22:37:27 UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent env[2705]: Started wazuh-agentd...
Mar 06 22:37:28 UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent env[2705]: Started wazuh-syscheckd...
Mar 06 22:37:29 UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent env[2705]: Started wazuh-logcollector...
Mar 06 22:37:30 UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent env[2705]: Started wazuh-modulesd...
Mar 06 22:37:32 UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent env[2705]: Completed.
Mar 06 22:37:32 UbuntuServer-WazuhAgent systemd[1]: Started Wazuh agent.
```

Figure 2.10 Status Service Wazuh Agent

Based on Figure 2.10, the result of the Wazuh Agent service status check shows that the service is already active (running).

- E. After the Wazuh Agent service has been activated, the next step is to configure the agent by specifying the IP address of the Wazuh Manager. This configuration allows the Wazuh Agent to be registered as an agent under the Wazuh Manager. The configuration can be performed by editing the “/var/ossec/etc/ossec.conf” file.

```
GNU nano 6.2 /var/ossec/etc/ossec.conf
<!--
Wazuh - Agent - Default configuration for ubuntu 22.04
More info at: https://documentation.wazuh.com
Mailing list: https://groups.google.com/forum/#!forum/wazuh
-->

<ossec_config>
  <client>
    <server>
      <address>192.168.1.7</address>
      <port>1514</port>
      <protocol>tcp</protocol>
    </server>
    <config-profile>ubuntu, ubuntu22, ubuntu22.04</config-profile>
    <notify_time>10</notify_time>
    <time-reconnect>60</time-reconnect>
    <auto_restart>yes</auto_restart>
    <crypto_method>aes</crypto_method>
    <enrollment>
      <enabled>yes</enabled>
      <agent_name>Ubuntu-Server-22.04</agent_name>
      <authorization_pass_path>etc/authd.pass</authorization_pass_path>
    </enrollment>
  </client>
```

Figure 2.11 Configuration Wazuh Agent

Based on Figure 2.11, the IP address of the Wazuh Manager has been added to the “ossec.conf” file.

- F. After configuring the Wazuh Agent, the next step is to restart the Wazuh Agent service and verify that the agent is connected to the Wazuh Manager. The service can be restarted using the command `systemctl restart wazuh-agent`, and the connection can be confirmed by checking the list of agents on the Wazuh Manager or through the Wazuh Dashboard.

Figure 2.12 Wazuh Agent Active

Based on Figure 2.12, it can be observed that the Wazuh Agent, which has been installed and configured, is successfully connected to the Wazuh Manager.

2.1.3 Configuration Security Configuration Assessment

After the Wazuh Agent has been successfully installed and connected to the Wazuh Manager, the next step is to activate the Security Configuration Assessment (SCA) module on the Wazuh Agent. The activation of the SCA module is performed by adding the scan configuration to the `ossec.conf` file on the agent side. The following are the configuration steps performed:

- A. Edit the `ossec.conf` file to add the location of the SCA policy and change the enabled status to “yes”.

```
GNU nano 6.2 /var/ossec/etc/ossec.conf
<sca>
  <enabled>yes</enabled>
  <scan_on_start>yes</scan_on_start>
  <interval>12h</interval>
  <skip_nfs>yes</skip_nfs>

  <policies>
    <policy>/var/ossec/ruleset/sca/cis_ubuntu22-04.yml</policy>
  </policies>
</sca>
```

Figure 2.13 SCA Configuration

Based on Figure 2.13, the SCA module has been activated using the “<enabled>yes</enabled>” and the policy path to be used for SCA on the Wazuh Agent has been added using the directive “<policy>/var/ossec/ruleset/sca/cis_ubuntu22-04.yml</policy>”.

- B. After configuring the SCA, the next step is to restart the Wazuh Agent service and monitor the logs for any errors related to the configuration. To restart the Wazuh Agent service, use the command `systemctl restart wazuh-agent`, and to monitor the Wazuh Agent logs, use the command `tail -f /var/ossec/logs/ossec.log`.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/var/ossec/ruleset# systemctl restart wazuh-agent
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/var/ossec/ruleset# tail -f /var/ossec/logs/ossec.log
2025/04/30 23:07:25 wazuh-modulesd:control: INFO: Starting control thread.
2025/04/30 23:07:25 wazuh-modulesd:syscollector: INFO: Module started.
2025/04/30 23:07:25 wazuh-modulesd:syscollector: INFO: Starting evaluation.
2025/04/30 23:07:25 sca: INFO: Starting evaluation of policy: '/var/ossec/ruleset/sca/cis_ubuntu22-04.yml'
2025/04/30 23:07:25 wazuh-modulesd:syscollector: INFO: Evaluation finished.
2025/04/30 23:07:26 wazuh-syscheckd: INFO: (6009): File integrity monitoring scan ended.
2025/04/30 23:07:26 wazuh-syscheckd: INFO: FIM sync module started.
2025/04/30 23:07:27 wazuh-logcollector: INFO: (9203): Monitoring journal entries.
2025/04/30 23:07:30 sca: INFO: Evaluation finished for policy '/var/ossec/ruleset/sca/cis_ubuntu22-04.yml'
2025/04/30 23:07:30 sca: INFO: Security Configuration Assessment scan finished. Duration: 5 seconds.
2025/04/30 23:07:46 rootcheck: INFO: Ending rootcheck scan.
```

Figure 2.14 Restart Service Wazuh Agent

Based on Figure 2.14, after restarting the Wazuh Agent and monitoring the `ossec.log` file, there is information indicating that the SCA module is running and has successfully conducted the SCA rules scan on the Wazuh Agent.

Figure 2.15 Result Scan SCA

As shown in Figure 2.15, this represents the first scan result after the Security Configuration Assessment (SCA) configuration was applied.

2.2 Remediation

After the system installation and Security Configuration Assessment (SCA) configuration process is complete, this stage is to remediate the scan results that have been run. The remediation stage aims to reconfigure the system to comply with the security standards that have been implemented by the CIS Benchmark for Ubuntu server 22.04.

Based on the results of the first scan, as seen in Figure 2.15, it is known that there are a total of 182 Rules IDs, 76 statuses passed, 106 failed with an initial compliance score percentage of 41%. This shows that the system still requires significant adjustments to achieve an optimal level of compliance. The remediation process is focused on all rule IDs that have failed status. With this remediation process, it is hoped that the system can achieve a more optimal level of compliance with the security standards that have been set in the CIS Benchmark.

The following are the remediation steps for each Rule ID based on the CIS Benchmark:

- Rule ID 28500

Title	Ensure /tmp is a separate partition.
-------	--------------------------------------

Description	The /tmp directory must be mounted as a separate partition to enhance system security.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root privileges. 2. /tmp must be configured in /etc/fstab.
Testing Step	1. Execute findmnt --kernel /tmp to verify that /tmp is mounted as a separate partition. 2. Execute systemctl is-enabled tmp.mount to ensure /tmp is enabled at boot. 3. Check /etc/fstab to ensure /tmp has the recommended mount options.
Test Data	1. Output of findmnt --kernel /tmp. 2. Output of systemctl is-enabled tmp.mount. 3. Mount configuration in /etc/fstab or tmp.mount.
Expectation	1. /tmp should appear as a separate partition in the output of findmnt --kernel /tmp. 2. The output of systemctl is-enabled tmp.mount should return enabled or generated. 3. The /etc/fstab or tmp.mount configuration should contain defaults,rw mount options.
Actual Result	1. /tmp appears as a separate partition with tmpfs as the source. 2. The command systemctl is-enabled tmp.mount returns enabled. 3. The configuration in /etc/fstab includes the defaults,rw mount options.
Test Status	Passed

Table 2.1 Rule ID 28500

Based on Table 2.1, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28500.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw 0 0

```

Figure 2.16 Configuration Rule ID 28500

Based on Figure 2.16, a configuration has been made to separate the tmpfs mount on the system in the /etc/fstab file..

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/# systemctl is-enabled tmp.mount
enabled

```

Figure 2.17 Mount Tmp

Based on Figure 2.17, a mount has been performed on the tmp that has been configured..

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /tmp
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/tmp tmpfs tmpfs rw,relatime,inode64
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent#

```

Figure 2.18 Status Tmp

Based on Figure 2.18, the tmp status has been successfully mounted.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28500	Ensure /tmp is a separate partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /tmp,systemctl is-enabled tmp.mount	Passed

Figure 2.19 Status Rule ID 28500

Based on Figure 2.19, the status of rule ID 28500 has changed to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28501

Title	Ensure nodev option set on /tmp partition.
Description	The /tmp directory must be mounted with the nodev mount option to prevent users from creating unauthorized block devices.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root privileges.

	2. The nodev option must be configured for /tmp in /etc/fstab.
Testing Step	1. Execute findmnt --kernel /tmp. 2. Verify that the mount options for /tmp include nodev. 3. If nodev is not present, check /etc/fstab and manually add the nodev option.
Test Data	1. Output showing nodev from findmnt --kernel /tmp. 2. Mount configuration for /tmp in /etc/fstab containing nodev.
Expectation	1. The output of findmnt --kernel /tmp must include the nodev option for the /tmp partition. 2. The /etc/fstab file must include the nodev option for mounting /tmp.
Actual Result	1. The output of findmnt --kernel /tmp confirms that /tmp is mounted with the nodev option. 2. The /etc/fstab file includes the nodev option in the /tmp mount configuration.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.2 Rule ID 28501

Based on Table 2.2, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28501.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab *
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nodev 0 0

```

Figure 2.20 Configuration Rule ID 28501

Based on Figure 2.20, add the “nodev” command to the /etc/fstab path file..

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/# mount -o remount /tmp
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/# findmnt --kernel /tmp
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/tmp tmpfs tmpfs rw,nodev,relatime,inode64
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/# █

```

Figure 2.21 Mount Tmp Nodev

Based on Figure 2.21, the /tmp partition is remounted, this is intended so that the changes to the “nodev” option can work.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28501	Ensure nodev option set on /tmp partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /tmp	Passed

Figure 2.22 Status Rule ID 28501

Based on Figure 2.21, the status of Rule ID 28501 changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28502

Title	Ensure noexec option set on /tmp partition
Description	The /tmp directory must be mounted with the noexec option to prevent the execution of binary files that could pose security threats.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. The noexec mount option must be configured for /tmp in /etc/fstab.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Execute the command findmnt --kernel /tmp. 2. Verify that the mount options include noexec. 3. If not found, check /etc/fstab and add the noexec option manually.
Test Data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Output of findmnt --kernel /tmp showing noexec. 2. Mount configuration in /etc/fstab containing noexec.
Expectation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The output from findmnt --kernel /tmp must include the noexec option. 2. /etc/fstab must include the noexec option for /tmp.
Actual Result	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The output from findmnt --kernel /tmp shows that /tmp is mounted with noexec. 2. /etc/fstab contains the noexec option in the mount configuration
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.3 Rule ID 28502

Based on Table 2.3, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28502.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab *
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nodev noexec 0 0

```

Figure 2.23 Configuration Rule ID 28502

Based on Figure 2.23, the “noexec” command is added to the path file /etc/fstab/

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/# mount -o remount /tmp
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/# findmnt --kernel /tmp
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/tmp tmpfs tmpfs rw,nodev,noexec,relatime,inode64
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/#

```

Figure 2.24 Mount Tmp Noexec.

Based on Figure 2.24, after the configuration is done in the /etc/fstab file, so that the configuration that has been done functions normally.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28502	Ensure noexec option set on /tmp partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /tmp	Passed

Figure 2.25 Status Rule ID 285002

Based on Figure 2.25, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28502 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28503

Title	Ensure nosuid option set on /tmp partition.
Description	The /tmp directory must be mounted with the nosuid option to prevent execution of files with the setuid bit set within the /tmp directory.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. The nosuid mount option must be configured for /tmp in /etc/fstab.
Testing Step	1. Execute the command findmnt --kernel /tmp. 2. Ensure that the output includes the nosuid option.

	3. If not present, verify and update the /etc/fstab file accordingly.
Test Data	1. Output of findmnt --kernel /tmp showing nosuid. 2. Configuration in /etc/fstab containing the nosuid option.
Expectation	1. The output from findmnt --kernel /tmp must show nosuid as one of the mount options. 2. /etc/fstab must contain the nosuid option for /tmp.
Actual Result	1. The output from findmnt --kernel /tmp confirms that /tmp is mounted with the nosuid option. 2. The /etc/fstab file includes the nosuid mount option for /tmp.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.4 Rule ID 28503

Based on Table 2.4, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28503.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab *
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nodev,noexec,nosuid 0 0

```

Figure 2.26 Configuration Rule ID 28503

Based on Figure 2.26, the “nosuid” command is added for the /tmp partition in the “/etc/fstab” path file.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/# mount -o remount /tmp
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/# findmnt --kernel /tmp
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/tmp tmpfs tmpfs rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime,inode64

```

Figure 2.27 Mount Tmp Nosuid

Based on Figure 2.27, after the configuration is done in the /etc/fstab file, /tmp is remounted so that the configuration that has been done functions normally.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28503	Ensure nosuid option set on /tmp partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /tmp	Passed

Figure 2.28 Status Rule ID 28503

Based on Figure 2.28, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28503 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28504

Title	Ensure separate partition exists for /var.
Description	The /var directory stores logs, caches, and other dynamically changing system files. Mounting /var on a separate partition improves system security, disk management, and helps prevent a full root filesystem that may disrupt system operation.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root privileges. 2. /var must be configured in the /etc/fstab file.
Testing Step	1. Run the command findmnt --kernel /var. 2. Verify that /var is mounted on a different partition than /. 3. Ensure that /var is permanently mounted via /etc/fstab.
Test Data	1. Output from findmnt --kernel /var. 2. Mount configuration of /var in /etc/fstab.
Expectation	1. The output of findmnt --kernel /var must indicate that /var resides on a partition separate from /. 2. /etc/fstab must include the mount entry for /var using a separate partition.
Actual Result	1. /var is confirmed to be mounted on a partition distinct from /. 2. /var is permanently configured in /etc/fstab
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.5 Rule ID 28504

Based on Table 2.5, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28504.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults 0 2

```

Figure 2.29 Configuration Rule ID 28504

Based on Figure 2.29, a mount is created for /var on the “/dev/sdb1” partition with ext4 format.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt /var/
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var /dev/sdb1 ext4 rw,relatime

```

Figure 2.30 Mounting Var

Based on Figure 2.30, the /var mount process has been successful on /dev/sdb1

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28504	Ensure separate partition exists for /var.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var	Passed

Figure 2.31 Status Rule ID 28504

Based on Figure 2.31, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28504 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28505

Title	Ensure nodev option set on /var partition.
Description	The /var directory is used to store logs, caches, spool data, and other dynamic files. It is not intended to host device files. Setting the nodev mount option prevents users from creating block or character special devices in /var.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root privileges. 2. /var must be configured in the /etc/fstab file.
Testing Step	1. Ensure the nodev option is configured in /etc/fstab. 2. Run findmnt --kernel /var to validate that the option has been applied at runtime.

Test Data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mount configuration of /var in /etc/fstab with the nodev option. 2. Output from the command findmnt --kernel /var.
Expectation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The /etc/fstab file must contain a mount configuration for /var that includes the nodev option. 2. The output of findmnt --kernel /var must show that /var is mounted with the nodev option.
Actual Result	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The nodev mount option for /var has been properly configured in /etc/fstab. 2. The command findmnt --kernel /var confirms the presence of the nodev mount option.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.6 Rule ID 28505

Based on Table 2.6, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28505.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nodev 0 2

```

Figure 2.32. Configuration Rule ID 28505

Based on Figure 2.32, the configuration adds the “nodev” option to the “/var” mount point.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var /dev/sdb1 ext4 rw,nodev relatime

```

Figure 2.33 Mount Var Nodev

Based on Figure 2.33, after remounting, the “nodev” option is already valid on the /var target.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28505	Ensure nodev option set on /var partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var	● Passed

Figure 2.34 Status Rule ID 28505

Based on Figure 2.34, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28505 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28506

Title	Ensure nosuid option set on /var partition.
Description	The /var directory must not contain files with the Set-User-ID (SUID) or Set-Group-ID (SGID) bits enabled, as these could be exploited to gain elevated privileges. The nosuid option prevents execution of binaries with SUID/SGID within /var.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. The /var partition must be defined in the /etc/fstab file.
Testing Step	1. Ensure the nosuid option is included in the /etc/fstab configuration for /var. 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /var to verify the option is active during runtime.
Test Data	1. The nosuid mount option configured in /etc/fstab. 2. The output from findmnt --kernel /var.
Expectation	1. The /etc/fstab entry for /var must include the nosuid mount option. 2. The findmnt --kernel /var output must confirm that /var is mounted with the nosuid option.
Actual Result	1. The nosuid option has been configured correctly in the /etc/fstab entry for /var. 2. The output of findmnt --kernel /var confirms the use of the nosuid option.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.7 Rule ID 28506

Based on Table 2.7, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28506.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev

```

Figure 2.35 Configuration Rule ID 28506

Based on Figure 2.35, the configuration adds the “nosuid” option to the /var mount point.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var /dev/sdb1 ext4 rw,nosuid,nodev,relatime

```

Figure 2.36 Mount Var Nosuid

Based on Figure 2.36, after remounting, the “nosuid” option is already valid on the /var target.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28506	Ensure nosuid option set on /var partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var	● Passed

Figure 2.37 Status Rule ID 28506

Based on Figure 2.37, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28506 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28507

Title	Ensure separate partition exists for /var/tmp.
Description	The /var/tmp directory is used for temporary file storage by all users and certain applications. Files in /var/tmp must persist across reboots. Isolating /var/tmp on its own partition helps prevent resource exhaustion, provides more granular mount options, and mitigates potential security exploits.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root privileges. 2. A new disk partition is available.

	3. The /var/tmp directory is not yet configured as a separate partition.
Testing Step	1. Run findmnt --kernel /var/tmp to verify if /var/tmp is mounted. 2. Check if /etc/fstab contains a dedicated entry for /var/tmp. 3. Run findmnt --kernel /var/tmp again to confirm persistence after reboot.
Test Data	1. Mount configuration for /var/tmp in /etc/fstab. 2. Output from findmnt --kernel /var/tmp.
Expectation	1. /etc/fstab must include a separate mount configuration for /var/tmp. 2. The findmnt --kernel /var/tmp command must show that /var/tmp is mounted on a different partition from /.
Actual Result	1. /var/tmp has been separated into a different partition from the root (/) directory. 2. /var/tmp has been mounted permanently by configuring it in the /etc/fstab file
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.8 Rule ID 28507

Based on Table 2.8, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28507.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
## /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults 0 2

```

Figure 2.38 Configuration Rule ID 28507

Based on Figure 2.38, perform Configuration to add a new file system to the mount point /var/tmp.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var/tmp
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var/tmp /dev/sdc1 ext4 rw,relatime

```

Figure 2.39 Mount Var Tmp

Based on Figure 2.39, the /var/tmp mount process was successful on /dev/sdc1.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28507	Ensure separate partition exists for /var/tmp.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var/tmp	Passed

Figure 2.40 Status Rule ID 28507

Based on Figure 2.40, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28507 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28508

Title	Ensure noexec option set on /var/tmp partition.
Description	The /var/tmp directory is used for temporary file storage. The noexec option prevents users from executing binary files from /var/tmp, such as running scripts or malware from this temporary directory.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root privileges. 2. The /var/tmp partition must exist and be configured in /etc/fstab.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure the noexec option has been configured in /etc/fstab. 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /var/tmp to validate the configuration result.
Test Data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. noexec configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output from findmnt --kernel /var/tmp.
Expectation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. /etc/fstab must contain the mount configuration for /var/tmp with the noexec option. 2. The output of findmnt --kernel /var/tmp must indicate that /var/tmp has the noexec option.
Actual Result	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The noexec mount option for /var/tmp has been properly configured in the /etc/fstab file.

	2. The output of the findmnt --kernel /var/tmp command confirms that the /var/tmp partition has the noexec option enabled.
Test Status	Passed

Table 2.9 Rule ID 28508

Based on Table 2.9, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28508.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec 0 2

```

Figure 2.41 Configuration Rule ID 28508

Based on Figure 2.41, the Configuration adds the “noexec” option to the mount point /var/tmp.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var/tmp
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var/tmp /dev/sdc1 ext4 rw,noexec relatime

```

Figure 2.42 Mount Var Tmp Noexec

Based on Figure 2.42, after remounting, the “exec” option is already valid on the target /var/vmp.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28508	Ensure noexec option set on /var/tmp partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var/tmp	● Passed

Figure 2.43 Status Rule ID 28508

Based on Figure 2.43, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28508 policy, so the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28509

Title	Ensure nosuid option set on /var/tmp partition.
-------	---

Description	The nosuid option must be applied to the /var/tmp directory to prevent the creation or execution of files with the Set-User-ID (setuid) bit in the /var/tmp directory.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. The /var/tmp partition must exist and be configured in /etc/fstab.
Testing Step	1. Make sure the nosuid option is configured in /etc/fstab. 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /var/tmp to validate the mount configuration from /etc/fstab.
Test Data	1. nosuid configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output from findmnt --kernel /var/tmp.
Expectation	1. /etc/fstab must contain the mount configuration for /var/tmp with the nosuid option. 2. The findmnt --kernel /var/tmp output must show that /var/tmp uses nosuid.
Actual Result	1. The nosuid mount option for /var/tmp has been configured properly in /etc/fstab. 2. The output of findmnt --kernel /var/tmp confirms the nosuid option is applied.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.10 Rule ID 28509

Based on Table 2.10, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28509.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid 0 2

```

Figure 2.44 Configuration Rule ID 28509

Based on Figure 2.44, the Configuration adds the “nosuid” option to the mount point /var/tmp.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Illam-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var/tmp
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var/tmp /dev/sdc1 ext4 rw,nosuid noexec,relatime
```

Figure 2.45 Mount Var Tmp Nosuid

Based on Figure 2.45, after remounting, the “exec” option is already valid on the target /var/vmp.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28509	Ensure nosuid option set on /var/tmp partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var/tmp	Passed

Figure 2.46 Status Rule ID 28509

Based on Figure 2.46, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28509 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28510

Title	Ensure nodev option set on /var/tmp partition.
Description	The nodev option must be applied to the /var/tmp directory to prevent users from creating block or character special device files in the /var/tmp directory.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. The /var/tmp partition must exist and be configured in /etc/fstab.
Testing Step	1. Make sure the nodev option is configured in /etc/fstab. 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /var/tmp to validate the mount configuration from /etc/fstab.
Test Data	1. Nodev configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output from findmnt --kernel /var/tmp.
Expectation	1. /etc/fstab must contain the mount configuration for /var/tmp with the nodev option. 2. The findmnt --kernel /var/tmp output must show that /var/tmp uses nodev.
Actual Result	1. The nodev mount option for /var/tmp has been properly configured in /etc/fstab.

	2. The output of <code>findmnt --kernel /var/tmp</code> confirms the <code>nodev</code> option is applied.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.11 Rule ID 28510

Based on Table 2.11, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28510.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid,nodev 0 2

```

Figure 2.47 Configuration Rule ID 28510

Based on Figure 2.47, the Configuration adds the “`nodev`” option to the mount point `/var/tmp`.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var/tmp
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var/tmp /dev/sdc1 ext4 rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime

```

Figure 2.48 Mount Var Tmp Nodev

Based on Figure 2.48, after remounting, the “`nodev`” option is already valid on the target `/var/vmp`.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28510	Ensure nodev option set on /var/tmp partition.	Command: <code>findmnt --kernel /var/tmp</code>	● Passed

Figure 2.49 Status Rule ID

Based on Figure 2.49, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28510 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28511

Title	Ensure separate partition exists for <code>/var/log</code> .
-------	--

Description	The /var/log directory is used by the system to store service and application logs. If not on a separate partition, log growth can exhaust disk space on /, potentially disrupting the system. Isolating /var/log on its own partition enables stricter mount option controls, enhances security, and prevents disk space issues that may interfere with system operations.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. A new disk partition. 3. The /var/log partition has not yet been configured separately.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the command <code>findmnt --kernel /var/log</code>. 2. Check whether the new partition has been permanently mounted in <code>/etc/fstab</code>. 3. Recheck the mount using <code>findmnt --kernel /var/log</code>.
Test Data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mount configuration in <code>/etc/fstab</code>. 2. Output of <code>findmnt --kernel /var/log</code>.
Expectation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <code>/etc/fstab</code> must contain the mount configuration for <code>/var/log</code> on a separate partition. 2. The output of <code>findmnt --kernel /var/log</code> must show that <code>/var/log</code> is not on the root (<code>/</code>) partition.
Actual Result	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <code>/var/log</code> is mounted on a partition separate from <code>/</code>. 2. The partition is permanently mounted as per the <code>/etc/fstab</code> configuration.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.12 Rule ID 28511

Based on Table 2.12, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28511.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdg1 /var/log ext4 defaults 0 2

```

Figure 2.50 Configuration Rule ID 28511

Based on Figure 2.50, the configuration adds a mount point for the path “/var/log” on the partition “/dev/sdg1”.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Iham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var/log
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var/log /dev/sdg1 ext4 rw,relatime

```

Figure 2.51 Mount Dev Sdg1

Based on Figure 2.51, the process of mounting /var/log has been successful on /dev/sdg1

ID ^	Title	Target	Result
28511	Ensure separate partition exists for /var/log.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var/log	Passed

Figure 2.52 Status Rule ID 28511

Based on Figure 2.52, the configuration has been carried out in accordance with the Rule ID 28511 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28512

Title	Ensure nodev option set on /var/log partition.
Title	The nodev option prevents the creation of block or character special device files on /var/log. This directory is solely used to store system and application logs, and no device files should exist within it.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. /var/log must already be mounted as a separate partition.
Testing Step	1. Ensure the nodev option is configured in /etc/fstab.

	2. Run the command <code>findmnt --kernel /var/log</code> to validate the mount configuration from <code>/etc/fstab</code> .
Test Data	1. <code>nodev</code> mount configuration in <code>/etc/fstab</code> . 2. Output of the <code>findmnt --kernel /var/log</code> command.
Expectation	1. <code>/etc/fstab</code> must include the mount configuration for <code>/var/log</code> with the <code>nodev</code> option. 2. The output of <code>findmnt --kernel /var/log</code> must show that <code>/var/log</code> has the <code>nodev</code> option set.
Actual Result	1. The <code>nodev</code> configuration for mounting <code>/var/log</code> has been applied correctly in <code>/etc/fstab</code> . 2. The output from <code>findmnt --kernel /var/log</code> confirms that <code>/var/log</code> has the <code>nodev</code> option.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.13 Rule ID 28512

Based on Table 2.13, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28512..

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdg1 /var/log ext4 defaults,nodev 0 2

```

Figure 2.53 Configuration Rule ID 28512

Based on Figure 2.53, the Configuration adds the “`nodev`” option to the `/var/log` mount point.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var/log
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var/log /dev/sdg1 ext4 rw,nodev,relatime

```

Figure 2.54 Mount Var Log Nodev

Based on Figure 2.54, after remounting, the “nodev” option is already valid on the /var/log target.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28512	Ensure nodev option set on /var/log partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var/log	● Passed

Figure 2.55 Status Rule ID 28512

Based on Figure 2.55, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28512 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28513

Title	Ensure noexec option set on /var/log partition.
Description	The noexec option prevents the execution of binary files within the /var/log directory. This directory is only used for storing system and application logs, so no executable files should exist within it.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. /var/log must already be mounted as a separate partition.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure the noexec option is configured in /etc/fstab. 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /var/log to validate the mount configuration from /etc/fstab.
Test Data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. noexec mount configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output of the findmnt --kernel /var/log command.
Expectation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. /etc/fstab must include the mount configuration for /var/log with the noexec option. 2. The output of findmnt --kernel /var/log must show that /var/log has the noexec option set.
Actual Result	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The noexec configuration for mounting /var/log has been correctly applied in /etc/fstab. 2. The output from findmnt --kernel /var/log confirms that /var/log has the noexec option.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.14 Rule ID 28513

Based on Table 2.14, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28513.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdg1 /var/log ext4 defaults,nodev,noexec 0 2
  
```

Figure 2.56 Configuration Rule ID 28513

Based on Figure 2.56, the Configuration adds the “noexec” option to the mount point /var/log.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var/log
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var/log /dev/sdg1 ext4 rw,nodev,noexec,relatime
  
```

Figure 2.57 Mount /var/log nodev

Based on Figure 2.57, after remounting, the “noexec” option is already in effect on the target /var/log.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28513	Ensure noexec option set on /var/log partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var/log	Passed

Figure 2.58 Status Rule ID 28513

Based on Figure 2.58, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28513 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28514

Title	Ensure nosuid option set on /var/log partition.
Description	The nosuid option ensures that no files with setuid permissions can be executed from /var/log, which could otherwise be used in privilege escalation attacks. Since this directory is used only to store system and application logs,

	there is no reason to allow the execution of privileged files within it.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. /var/log must already be mounted as a separate partition.
Testing Step	1. Ensure the nosuid option is configured in /etc/fstab. 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /var/log to validate the mount configuration from /etc/fstab.
Test Data	1. nosuid mount configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output of the findmnt --kernel /var/log command.
Expectation	1. /etc/fstab must include the mount configuration for /var/log with the nosuid option. 2. The output of findmnt --kernel /var/log must show that /var/log has the nosuid option set.
Actual Result	1. The nosuid configuration for mounting /var/log has been correctly applied in /etc/fstab. 2. The output from findmnt --kernel /var/log confirms that /var/log has the nosuid option.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.15 Rule ID 28514

Based on Table 2.15, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28514.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdg1 /var/log ext4 defaults,nodev,noexec,nosuid 0 2

```

Figure 2.59 Configuration Rule ID 28514

Based on Figure 2.59, the Configuration adds the “nosuid” option to the /var/log mount point.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Illham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var/log
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var/log /dev/sdg1 ext4 rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Illham-WazuhAgent#

```

Figure 2.60 Mount /var/log nosuid

Based on Figure 2.60, after remounting, the “nosuid” option is already in effect on the /var/log target.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28514	Ensure nosuid option set on /var/log partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var/log	Passed

Figure 2.61 Status Rule ID 28514

Based on Figure 2.61, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28514 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28515

Title	Ensure separate partition exists for /var/log/audit.
Description	The directory /var/log/audit stores audit logs from the system, including sensitive security information. Separating this directory into its own partition helps improve security, prevents resource exhaustion risks, and ensures availability of audit log data if other partitions fail or run out of space.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. New disk partition. 3. /var/log/audit partition has not yet been configured separately.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the command findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit. 2. Check if the new partition is permanently mounted in /etc/fstab. 3. Verify again whether /var/log/audit is mounted by running findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit.
Test Data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mount configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output of findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit.
Expectation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. /etc/fstab must contain mount configuration for /var/log/audit on a separate partition.

	2. Output of <code>findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit</code> must show that <code>/var/log/audit</code> is on a different partition than <code>/</code> .
Actual Result	1. <code>/var/log/audit</code> is already separated on a partition different from <code>/</code> . 2. <code>/var/log/audit</code> is permanently mounted as configured in <code>/etc/fstab</code> .
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.16 Rule ID 28515

Based on Table 2.16, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28515.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdg1 /var/log ext4 defaults,nodev,noexec,nosuid 0 2
/dev/sde1 /var/log/audit ext4 defaults 0 2

```

Figure 2.62 Configuration Rule ID 28515

Based on Figure 2.62, Configuration is performed to add a mount point for the path “`/var/log/audit`” on the partition “`/dev/sde1`”.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var/log/audit /dev/sde1 ext4 rw,relatime

```

Figure 2.63 Mount Dev Sde1

Based on Figure 2.63, the process of mounting `/var/log/audit` has been successful on `/dev/sde1`

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28515	Ensure separate partition exists for <code>/var/log/audit</code> .	Command: <code>findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit</code>	● Passed

Figure 2.64 Status Rule ID 28515

Based on Figure 2.64, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28515 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28516

Title	Ensure noexec option set on /var/log/audit partition.
Description	The noexec option prevents the execution of binary files within the /var/log/audit directory. This directory is used only for storing system and security audit logs, so executable files should not exist inside it.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. /var/log/audit is mounted as a separate partition.
Testing Step	1. Ensure the "noexec" option is configured in /etc/fstab. 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit to validate the /etc/fstab configuration.
Test Data	1. "noexec" configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output from findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit.
Expectation	1. /etc/fstab should include the mount configuration for /var/log/audit with the "noexec" option. 2. Output of findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit should indicate that /var/log/audit has the "noexec" option set.
Actual Result	1. The "noexec" option for mounting /var/log/audit is already configured in /etc/fstab. 2. The output of findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit matches and shows /var/log/audit has the "noexec" option set.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.17 Rule ID 28516

Based on Table 2.17, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28516.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdg1 /var/log ext4 defaults,nodev,noexec,nosuid 0 2
/dev/sde1 /var/log/audit ext4 defaults,noexec 0 2

```

Figure 2.65 Configuration Rule ID 28516

Based on Figure 2.65, the Configuration adds the “noexec” option to the mount point /var/log/audit.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var/log/audit /dev/sde1 ext4 rw,noexec,relatime

```

Figure 2.66 Mount /var/log/audit noexec

Based on Figure 2.66 after remounting, the “noexec” option is already in effect on the /var/log/audit target.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28516	Ensure noexec option set on /var/log/audit partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit	Passed

Figure 2.67 Status Rule ID 28516

Based on Figure 2.67, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28516 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28517

Title	Ensure nodev option set on /var/log/audit partition.
Description	The nodev option prevents the creation of block or character devices on /var/log/audit. This directory is used only for storing system audit and security logs, so device files should not exist inside it.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access.

	2. /var/log/audit is mounted as a separate partition.
Testing Step	1. Ensure the "nodev" option is configured in /etc/fstab. 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit to validate the /etc/fstab configuration.
Test Data	1. "nodev" configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output from findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit.
Expectation	1. /etc/fstab should include the mount configuration for /var/log/audit with the "nodev" option. 2. Output of findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit should indicate /var/log/audit has the "nodev" option set.
Actual Result	1. The "nodev" option for mounting /var/log/audit is already configured in /etc/fstab. 2. The output of findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit matches and shows /var/log/audit has the "nodev" option set.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.18 Rule ID 28517

Based on Table 2.18, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28517.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdg1 /var/log ext4 defaults,nodev,noexec,nosuid 0 2
/dev/sde1 /var/log/audit ext4 defaults,noexec,nodev 0 2

```

Figure 2.68 Configuration Rule ID 28517

Based on Figure 2.68, the Configuration adds the “nodev” option to the mount point /var/log/audit.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var/log/audit /dev/sde1 ext4 rw,nodev noexec,relatime

```

Figure 2.69 Mount Var Log Audit Nodev

Based on Figure 2.69, after remounting, the “nodev” option is already valid on the /var/log/audit target.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28517	Ensure nodev option set on /var/log/audit partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit	● Passed

Figure 2.70 Status Rule ID 28517

Based on Figure 2.70, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28517 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28518

Title	Ensure nosuid option set on /var/log/audit partition.
Description	The nosuid option ensures that no files with setuid permissions can be executed from /var/log/audit, which could be used in privilege escalation attacks. Since this directory is used to store audit and security logs, there is no reason to run privileged files inside it.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. /var/log/audit is mounted as a separate partition.
Testing Step	1. Ensure the "nosuid" option is configured in /etc/fstab. 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit to validate the /etc/fstab configuration.
Test Data	1. "nosuid" configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output from findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit.
Expectation	1. /etc/fstab should include the mount configuration for /var/log/audit with the "nosuid" option. 2. Output of findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit should indicate /var/log/audit has the "nosuid" option set.
Actual Result	1. The "nosuid" option for mounting /var/log/audit is already configured in /etc/fstab. 2. The output of findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit matches and shows /var/log/audit has the "nosuid" option set
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.19 Rule ID 28518

Based on Table 2.19, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28518.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdg1 /var/log ext4 defaults,nodev,noexec,nosuid 0 2
/dev/sde1 /var/log/audit ext4 defaults,noexec,nodev,nosuid 0 2
    
```

Figure 2.71 Configuration Rule ID 28518

Based on Figure 2.71, the Configuration adds the “nosuid” option to the mount point /var/log/audit.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/var/log/audit /dev/sde1 ext4 rw,nosuid nodev,noexec,relatime
    
```

Figure 2.72 Mount Var Log Audit Nosuid

Based on Figure 2.72, after remounting, the “nosuid” option is already in effect on the /var/log/audit target.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28518	Ensure nosuid option set on /var/log/audit partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /var/log/audit	Passed

Figure 2.73 Status Rule ID 28518

Based on Figure 2.73, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28518 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”..

- Rule ID 28519

Title	Ensure separate partition exists for /home.
Description	The /home directory is used to store user data. Separating /home into its own partition can improve security, allow

	stricter mount option configurations, and protect the system from excessive disk usage by users.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. A new disk partition available. 3. /home partition is not yet configured separately.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the command <code>findmnt --kernel /home</code>. 2. Check if the new partition is permanently mounted in <code>/etc/fstab</code> for <code>/home</code>. 3. Verify <code>/home</code> is mounted correctly by running <code>findmnt --kernel /home</code> again.
Test Data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mount configuration in <code>/etc/fstab</code>. 2. Output from the command <code>findmnt --kernel /home</code>.
Expectation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <code>/etc/fstab</code> must contain a mount configuration for <code>/home</code> on a separate partition. 2. Output of <code>findmnt --kernel /home</code> should show <code>/home</code> is mounted on a partition different from root (<code>/</code>).
Actual Result	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <code>/home</code> is on a separate partition from root (<code>/</code>). 2. <code>/home</code> is permanently mounted via <code>/etc/fstab</code>.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.20 Rule ID 28519

Based on Table 2.20, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28519.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
##
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdg1 /var/log ext4 defaults,nodev,noexec,nosuid 0 2
/dev/sde1 /var/log/audit ext4 defaults,noexec,nodev,nosuid 0 2
/dev/sdf1 /home ext4 defaults,rw 0 2

```

Figure 2.74 Configuration Rule ID 28519

Based on Figure 2.74, Configuration is done to add a mount point for the path “/home” on the partition “/dev/sdf1”.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /home
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/home /dev/sdf1 ext4 rw,relatime
```

Figure 2.75 Mount Dev Sdf1 Hom

Based on Figure 2.75, the mount process was carried out and the result was that /home was successfully mounted on the /dev/sdf1 partition.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28519	Ensure separate partition exists for /home.	Command: findmnt --kernel /home	● Passed

Figure 2. 76 Status Rule ID 28519

Based on Figure 2.76, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28519 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28520

Title	Ensure nodev option set on /home partition.
Description	The nodev option must be applied on the /home partition to prevent users from creating block or character special devices in this directory, as /home is not intended for such activities.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. /home is mounted as a separate partition.
Testing Step	1. Ensure "nodev" is configured in "/etc/fstab". 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /home to validate the /etc/fstab configuration.
Test Data	1. "nodev" configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output from findmnt --kernel /home.
Expectation	1. /etc/fstab must contain the mount configuration for /home with the "nodev" option. 2. The output of findmnt --kernel /home should show that /home has the "nodev" option.

Actual Result	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "nodev" configuration for mounting /home is already set in /etc/fstab. 2. The output of findmnt --kernel /home confirms that /home has the "nodev" option.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.21 Rule ID 28520

Based on Table 2.21, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28520.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdg1 /var/log ext4 defaults,nodev,noexec,nosuid 0 2
/dev/sde1 /var/log/audit ext4 defaults,noexec,nodev,nosuid 0 2
/dev/sdf1 /home ext4 defaults,rw,nodev 0 2

```

Figure 2.77 Configuration Rule ID 28520

Based on Figure 2.77, the Configuration adds the “nodev” option to the /home mount point.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Iilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /home
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/home /dev/sdf1 ext4 rw,nodev,relatime

```

Figure 2.78 Mount Home Nodev

Based on Figure 2.78, after remounting, the “nodev” option is already valid on the /home target.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28520	Ensure nodev option set on /home partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /home	Passed

Figure 2.79 Status Rule ID 28520

Based on Figure 2.79 the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28520 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28521

Title	Ensure nosuid option set on /home partition.
Description	To enhance security on /home, the nosuid option must be enabled to prevent users from creating setuid files, which can be used in privilege escalation attacks.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. /home mounted as a separate partition.
Testing Step	1. Ensure "nosuid" is configured in "/etc/fstab". 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /home to validate the /etc/fstab configuration.
Test Data	1. "nosuid" configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output from findmnt --kernel /home.
Expectation	1. /etc/fstab must contain the mount configuration for /home with the "nosuid" option. 2. Output of findmnt --kernel /home must show that /home has the "nosuid" option.
Actual Result	1. "nosuid" configuration for mounting /home is already set in /etc/fstab. 2. Output of findmnt --kernel /home confirms that /home has the "nosuid" option.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.22 Rule ID 28521

Based on Table 2.22, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28521.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
/dev/sdb1 /var ext4 defaults,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdc1 /var/tmp ext4 defaults,noexec,nosuid,nodev 0 2
/dev/sdg1 /var/log ext4 defaults,nodev,noexec,nosuid 0 2
/dev/sde1 /var/log/audit ext4 defaults,noexec,nodev,nosuid 0 2
/dev/sdf1 /home ext4 defaults,rw,nodev,nosuid 0 2

```

Figure 2.80 Configuration Rule ID 28521

Based on Figure 2.80, the Configuration adds the “nosuid” option to the /home mount point.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /home
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/home /dev/sdf1 ext4 rw,nosuid,nodev,relatime
```

Figure 2.81 Mount Home Nosuid

Based on Figure 2.81, after remounting, the “nosuid” option is already in effect on the /home target.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28521	Ensure nosuid option set on /home partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /home	● Passed

Figure 2.82 Status Rule ID 28521

Based on Figure 2.82, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28521 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28522

Title	Ensure nodev option set on /dev/shm partition
Description	The nodev option on the /dev/shm filesystem ensures that the partition cannot be used to create special device files. This is important because /dev/shm is used as shared memory space and is not intended to store devices, so applying the nodev option helps prevent potential misuse.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. /shm is mounted as a separate partition.
Testing Step	1. Ensure "nodev" is configured in "/etc/fstab". 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /shm to validate the /etc/fstab configuration.
Test Data	1. "nodev" configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output from findmnt --kernel /shm.
Expectation	1. /etc/fstab must contain the mount configuration for /shm with the "nodev" option.

	2. Output of findmnt --kernel /shm must show that /dev/shm has the "nodev" option.
Actual Result	1. "nodev" configuration for mounting /shm is already set in /etc/fstab. 2. Output of findmnt --kernel /shm confirms that /shm has the "nodev" option.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.23 Rule ID 28522

Based on Table 2.23, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28522.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
## /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0

```

Figure 2.83 Configuration Rule ID 28522

Based on Figure 2.83, the Configuration adds the “nodev” option to the mount point /dev/shm.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /dev/shm
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/dev/shm tmpfs tmpfs rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime,inode64
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent#

```

Figure 2.84 Mount /dev/shm nodev

Based on Figure 2.84, after remounting, the “nodev” option is already valid on the /dev/shm target.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28522	Ensure nodev option set on /dev/shm partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /dev/shm	● Passed

Figure 2.85 Status Rule ID 28522

Based on Figure 2.85, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28522 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28523

Title	Ensure noexec option set on /dev/shm partition
Description	The noexec option prevents the execution of binary files on the /dev/shm filesystem. Since this directory is used as shared memory between processes, this setting helps protect the system from executing malicious code stored in this location.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. /shm is mounted as a separate partition.
Testing Step	1. Ensure "noexec" is configured in "/etc/fstab". 2. Run the command findmnt --kernel /shm to validate the /etc/fstab configuration.
Test Data	1. "noexec" configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output from findmnt --kernel /shm.
Expectation	1. /etc/fstab must contain the mount configuration for /shm with the "noexec" option. 2. Output of findmnt --kernel /shm must show that /dev/shm has the "noexec" option
Actual Result	1. "noexec" configuration for mounting /shm is already set in /etc/fstab. 2. Output of findmnt --kernel /shm confirms that /shm has the "noexec" option.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.24 Rule ID 28523

Based on Table 2.24, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28523.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
# /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/71543e4d-4646-4a7e-83c5-684c86451d1a / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev noexec,relatime 0 0

```

Figure 2.86 Configuration Rule ID 28523

Based on Figure 2.86, the Configuration adds the “noexec” option to the mount point /dev/shm.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /dev/shm
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/dev/shm tmpfs tmpfs rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime,inode64
```

Figure 2.87 Mount /dev/shm noexec

Based on Figure 2.87, after remounting, the “nodev” option is already valid on the /dev/shm target.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28523	Ensure noexec option set on /dev/shm partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /dev/shm	Passed

Figure 2.88 Status Rule ID 28523

Based on Figure 2.88, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28523 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28524

Title	Ensure nosuid option set on /dev/shm partition
Description	The nosuid option prevents files with the setuid or setgid bit from being executed with elevated privileges on the /dev/shm filesystem. This is important to prevent non-root users from executing programs that could escalate their privileges.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. /shm is mounted as a separate partition.
Testing Step	1. Ensure that the nosuid option is configured in /etc/fstab. 2. Run findmnt --kernel /shm to validate the configuration.
Test Data	1. nosuid configuration in /etc/fstab. 2. Output from findmnt --kernel /shm.
Expectation	1. /etc/fstab must include the mount configuration for /shm with the nosuid option. 2. Output of findmnt --kernel /shm should confirm that /dev/shm has the nosuid option

Actual Result	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. nosuid has been configured for the /shm mount in /etc/fstab. 2. The output of findmnt --kernel /shm confirms that /shm has the nosuid option.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.25 Rule ID 28524

Based on Table 2.25, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28524.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/fstab
## /etc/fstab: static file system information.
#
# Use 'blkid' to print the universally unique identifier for a
# device; this may be used with UUID= as a more robust way to name devices
# that works even if disks are added and removed. See fstab(5).
#
# <file system> <mount point> <type> <options> <dump> <pass>
# / was on /dev/sda2 during curtin installation
/dev/disk/by-uuid/4d76f109-241f-4f10-aab7-b2857a868d59 / ext4 defaults 0 1
tmpfs /tmp tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,noexec,nodev,relatime 0 0
tmpfs /dev/shm tmpfs defaults,rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime 0 0

```

Figure 2.89 Configuration Rule ID 28524

Based on Figure 2.89, the Configuration adds the “nosuid” option to the mount point /dev/shm.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# findmnt --kernel /dev/shm
TARGET SOURCE FSTYPE OPTIONS
/dev/shm tmpfs tmpfs rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime,inode64
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent#

```

Figure 2.90 Mount /dev/shm nosuid

Based on Figure 2.90, after remounting, the “nosuid” option is already valid on the /dev/shm target.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28524	Ensure nosuid option set on /dev/shm partition.	Command: findmnt --kernel /dev/shm	● Passed

Figure 2.91 Status Rule ID 28524

Based on Figure 2.91, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28524 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28526

Title	Ensure AIDE is installed.
-------	---------------------------

Description	AIDE (Advanced Intrusion Detection Environment) is a tool used to verify the integrity of the file system. It creates a baseline snapshot of file attributes (including permissions, modification times, and hashes), which can later be compared to detect unauthorized or suspicious changes.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. Internet connection to install required packages
Testing Step	Check whether AIDE is already installed using: `dpkg-query -s aide`
Test Data	Output from <code>dpkg-query -s aide</code> and <code>dpkg-query -s aide-common</code>
Expectation	Both packages (aide and aide-common) must be installed with the status “install ok installed”.
Actual Result	Both AIDE packages were successfully installed and have the status “install ok installed”.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.26 Rule ID 28526

Based on Table 2.26, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28526.

```
root@WazuhAgent-Ubuntu-Server:/# apt install aide aide-common -y
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
aide is already the newest version (0.17.4-1ubuntu0.1).
aide-common is already the newest version (0.17.4-1ubuntu0.1).
0 upgraded, 0 newly installed, 0 to remove and 43 not upgraded.
root@WazuhAgent-Ubuntu-Server:/#
```

Figure 2.92 Install AIDE

Based on Figure 2.92, the AIDE software installation is carried out with the command “apt install aide aide-common -y”.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# dpkg-query -s aide | grep Status
Status: install ok installed
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# dpkg-query -s aide-common | grep Status
Status: install ok installed
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# █
```

Figure 2.93 Verifikasi AIDE

Based on Figure 2.93, verification of the AIDE installation results status was carried out and the result was “install ok installed”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28526	Ensure AIDE is installed.	Command: dpkg-query -s aide	● Passed

Figure 2.94 Status Rule ID 28526

Based on Figure 2.94, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28526 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28527

Title	Ensure bootloader password is set.
Description	The bootloader is the initial program that runs when the system is powered on. Setting a password on the bootloader prevents unauthorized users from modifying boot parameters or accessing recovery mode without authorization. This protects against actions such as disabling security features during boot.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. GRUB bootloader in use.
Testing Step	1. Create a GRUB password using the command <code>grub-mkpasswd-pbkdf2</code> . 2. Edit the <code>/etc/grub.d/40_custom</code> file to add the superuser and the encrypted password. 3. Run <code>update-grub</code> to apply the configuration changes.
Test Data	Contents of <code>/boot/grub/grub.cfg</code> and the output from <code>grub-mkpasswd-pbkdf2</code> .
Expectation	The <code>/boot/grub/grub.cfg</code> file must contain the lines for <code>set superusers</code> and <code>password_pbkdf2</code> with the defined username and encrypted password.
Actual Result	GRUB password has been successfully created and is enforced during system boot.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.27 Rule ID 28527

Based on Table 2.27, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28527.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# grub-mkpasswd-pbkdf2
Enter password:
Reenter password:
PBKDF2 hash of your password is grub.pbkdf2.sha512.10000.46E9C4B36AF92154518BD317BDB8484A9AA68A2535FDAF14D543685EE9FC
E10DB639785181952E5D924B27186E0C57E6384CEB80D86287CE09642D11C3717BD3.C9D83E58C0A1435EF5F8FE7F73F4961851A3FF01D3B0DE71
CC7C47253EB816BCB1469758FF9F5445B57A1CEE8DB3AC9F3D6EE44AC7DF1161FA9E929A49AC8E7A
```

Figure 2.95 Configuration Rule ID 28527

Based on Figure 2.95, the configuration for creating a password for the bootloader is carried out, by using the command “grub-mkpasswd-pbkdf2” and inputting the password to be created.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# cat /etc/grub.d/40_custom
#!/bin/sh
exec tail -n +3 $0
# This file provides an easy way to add custom menu entries. Simply type the
# menu entries you want to add after this comment. Be careful not to change
# the 'exec tail' line above.

set superusers="IlhamGrub"
password_pbkdf2 IlhamGrub grub.pbkdf2.sha512.10000.46E9C4B36AF92154518BD317BDB8484A9AA68A2535FDAF14D543685EE9FCE10DB6
39785181952E5D924B27186E0C57E6384CEB80D86287CE09642D11C3717BD3.C9D83E58C0A1435EF5F8FE7F73F4961851A3FF01D3B0DE71CC7C47
253EB816BCB1469758FF9F5445B57A1CEE8DB3AC9F3D6EE44AC7DF1161FA9E929A49AC8E7A
```

Figure 2.96 Add Password

Based on Figure 2.96, after successfully creating a password, the next step is to add the password and user to be created in the file “/etc/grub.d/40_custom”.


```
WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer (BootLoader) [Running] - Oracle VirtualBox
File Machine View Input Devices Help
Enter username:
IlhamGrub
Enter password:
—
```

Figure 2.97 Grub Login

Based on Figure 2.97, the username and password that have been created have been successfully implemented.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28527	Ensure bootloader password is set.	File: /boot/grub/grub.cfg	Passed

Figure 2.98 Status Rule ID 28527

Based on Figure 2.98, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28527 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28528

Title	Ensure permissions on bootloader config are configured.
Description	The bootloader configuration file (/boot/grub/grub.cfg) contains critical boot settings, including security parameters and passwords. To maintain its integrity, only the root user should have read access, and no other user should be allowed to read or modify the file.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. GRUB bootloader is being used.
Testing Step	1. Check the current file permissions of grub.cfg using stat /boot/grub/grub.cfg. 2. If the uid and gid are not set to root and permissions are not 0400 or -r-----, ownership and permissions are incorrect. 3. Run chown root:root /boot/grub/grub.cfg and chmod 0400 /boot/grub/grub.cfg. 4. Recheck with stat /boot/grub/grub.cfg.
Test Data	Output from the stat /boot/grub/grub.cfg command.
Expectation	The file should be owned by root:root and have permissions set to -r----- (0400).
Actual Result	The owner and permission of grub.cfg have been set correctly as recommended.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.28 Rule ID 28528

Based on Table 2.28, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28500.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# chown root:root /boot/grub/grub.cfg
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# chmod u-wx,go-rwx /boot/grub/grub.cfg
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# █
```

Figure 2.99 Configuration Rule ID 28528

Based on Figure 2.99, the command has been executed to change the permissions and owner on the grub.cfg file.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# stat /boot/grub/grub.cfg
File: /boot/grub/grub.cfg
Size: 10370          Blocks: 24          IO Block: 4096   regular file
Device: 802h/2050d Inode: 917518      Links: 1
Access: (0400/-r-----)  Uid: (  0/   root)   Gid: (  0/   root)
Access: 2025-04-15 23:23:48.228000000 +0700
Modify: 2025-04-15 22:24:57.352000000 +0700
Change: 2025-04-15 22:24:57.352000000 +0700
Birth: 2025-03-10 22:25:40.565135259 +0700
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# █

```

Figure 2.100 Result Configuration

Based on Figure 2.100, the owner and permissions on the grub.cfg file have changed to root and permissions 0400.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28528	Ensure permissions on bootloader config are configured.	Command: stat /boot/grub/grub.cfg	Passed

Figure 2.101 Status Rule ID 28528

Based on Figure 2.101, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28528 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28529

Title	Ensure authentication required for single user mode.
Description	Single-user mode is a system recovery mode that allows direct root access without authentication. If left unsecured, unauthorized individuals may gain full system access without credentials. Therefore, it is crucial to ensure the root account has a password to prevent misuse when the system is in recovery mode.
Prerequisite	Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root or sudo access.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the command <code>passwd --status root</code> to check whether the root account has a password. 2. If the output shows <code>root P ...</code>, the root account is password-protected. If it shows <code>root NP ...</code>, the root account does not have a password. 3. If necessary, set a password using the command <code>passwd root</code>. 4. Reverify using <code>passwd --status root</code>.
Test Data	Output from the <code>passwd --status root</code> command.

Expectation	The root account should have a password status of P (Password set), not NP (No Password).
Actual Result	The root account password has been successfully set, and the status shows P.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.29 Rule ID 28529

Based on Table 2.29, it is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28529.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# passwd root
New password:
Retype new password:
passwd: password updated successfully
```

Figure 2.102 Configuration Rule ID 28529

Based on Figure 2.102, the configuration for creating the root password has been carried out.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# passwd --status root
root P 03/10/2025 0 99999 7 -1
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent#
```

Figure 2.103 Result Configuration

Based on Figure 2.103, it can be seen that the Configuration result was successful, there is a “P” symbol after the root name which indicates that the password status has been set.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28529	Ensure authentication required for single user mode.	Command: passwd --status root	● Passed

Figure 2.104 Status Rule ID 28529

Based on Figure 2.104, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28529 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28532

Title	Ensure core dumps are restricted
Description	A core dump is a file that captures a program’s memory contents after it crashes. While useful for debugging, it may

	contain sensitive information. To prevent unauthorized access or data leakage, restrictions should be applied to core dumps, such as limiting their creation and preventing core dumps from setuid programs.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. systemd-coredump service installed (if applicable).
Testing Step	1. Add the line <code>* hard core 0</code> to the file <code>/etc/security/limits.conf</code> . 2. Add the line <code>fs.suid_dumpable = 0</code> to the file <code>/etc/sysctl.conf</code> . 3. Verify the configurations using: - <code>grep -Rh "fs.suid_dumpable" /etc/sysctl.conf</code> - <code>grep -Rh "hard core 0" /etc/security/limits.conf</code>
Test Data	Output from <code>/etc/security/limits.conf</code> and <code>/etc/sysctl.conf</code>
Expectation	Core dumps are restricted through <code>limits.conf</code> , the kernel parameter <code>fs.suid_dumpable</code> is set to 0, and (if applicable) <code>systemd-coredump</code> is not storing core dumps.
Actual Result	Core dump restrictions have been successfully applied using <code>fs.suid_dumpable = 0</code> and <code>* hard core 0</code> .
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.30 Rule ID 28532

Based on Table 2.30, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28532.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/sysctl.conf
#####
# Additional settings - these settings can improve the network
# security of the host and prevent against some network attacks
# including spoofing attacks and man in the middle attacks through
# redirection. Some network environments, however, require that these
# settings are disabled so review and enable them as needed.
#
# Do not accept ICMP redirects (prevent MITM attacks)
#net.ipv4.conf.all.accept_redirects = 0
#net.ipv6.conf.all.accept_redirects = 0
#_or_
# Accept ICMP redirects only for gateways listed in our default
# gateway list (enabled by default)
# net.ipv4.conf.all.secure_redirects = 1
#
# Do not send ICMP redirects (we are not a router)
#net.ipv4.conf.all.send_redirects = 0
#
# Do not accept IP source route packets (we are not a router)
#net.ipv4.conf.all.accept_source_route = 0
#net.ipv6.conf.all.accept_source_route = 0
#
# Log Martian Packets
#net.ipv4.conf.all.log_martians = 1
#
#####
# Magic system request Key
# 0=disable, 1=enable all, >1 bitmask of sysrq functions
# See https://www.kernel.org/doc/html/latest/admin-guide/sysrq.html
# for what other values do
#kernel.sysrq=438
fs.suid_dumpable = 0

```

Figure 2.105 Configuration sysctl

Based on Figure 2.105, Configuration has been added to the sysctl.conf file with the parameter “fs.suid_dumpable = 0”.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/security/limits.conf
#
# - priority - the priority to run user process with
# - locks - max number of file locks the user can hold
# - sigpending - max number of pending signals
# - msgqueue - max memory used by POSIX message queues (bytes)
# - nice - max nice priority allowed to raise to values: [-20, 19]
# - rtprio - max realtime priority
# - chroot - change root to directory (Debian-specific)
#
#<domain> <type> <item> <value>
#
#* soft core 0
#root hard core 100000
#* hard rss 10000
#@student hard nproc 20
#@faculty soft nproc 20
#@faculty hard nproc 50
#ftp hard nproc 0
#ftp - chroot /ftp
#@student - maxlogins 4
# End of file
* hard core 0

```

Figure 2.106 Configuration Limits

Based on Figure 2.106, Configuration has been added to the limits.conf file with the parameter “* hard core 0”.

ID	Title	Target	Result
28532	Ensure core dumps are restricted.	Command: sysctl fs.suid_dumpable	Passed

Figure 2.107 Status Rule ID 28532

Based on Figure 2.107, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28532 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28534

Title	Ensure AppArmor is enabled in the bootloader configuration
Description	AppArmor is a Mandatory Access Control (MAC) system that enhances Linux system security. To ensure AppArmor is activated at system boot, specific parameters must be added to the bootloader (GRUB) configuration. This prevents unauthorized users from disabling AppArmor protections during the boot process.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access. 2. GRUB is used as the system bootloader.
Testing Step	1. Open and inspect the GRUB configuration file /etc/default/grub. Check whether the GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX variable includes apparmor=1 security=apparmor. 2. If not present, modify the line to include: GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX="apparmor=1 security=apparmor" 3. Save the file and apply the changes with update-grub.
Test Data	Output from /etc/default/grub showing the GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX variable.
Expectation	The GRUB configuration file /etc/default/grub contains apparmor=1 security=apparmor in the GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX variable.
Actual Result	The GRUB configuration has been successfully updated to include apparmor=1 security=apparmor.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.31 Rule ID 28534

Based on Table 2.31, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28534.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/default/grub *
# If you change this file, run 'update-grub' afterwards to update
# /boot/grub/grub.cfg.
# For full documentation of the options in this file, see:
# info -f grub -n 'Simple configuration'

GRUB_DEFAULT=0
GRUB_TIMEOUT_STYLE=hidden
GRUB_TIMEOUT=0
GRUB_DISTRIBUTOR=`lsb_release -i -s 2> /dev/null || echo Debian`
GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX_DEFAULT="quiet splash noprompt noshell automatic-ubiquity debian-installer/locale=en_US keyboard->
GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX="apparmor=1 security=apparmor"

```

Figure 2.108 Configuration Rule ID 28534

Based on Figure 2.108, Configuration is added to the “/etc/default/grub” file with the GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX variable with the parameter “apparmor=1 security=apparmor”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28534	Ensure AppArmor is enabled in the bootloader configuration.	File: /etc/default/grub	Passed

Figure 2.109 Status Rule ID 28534

Based on Figure 2.109, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28534 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28538

Title	Ensure local login warning banner is configured properly
Description	The /etc/issue file displays a warning message to users before the login process on local terminals. This banner provides legal and monitoring policy information and must include the name of the organization that owns the system. Removing specific system information, such as the OS version, from the banner reduces the risk of disclosing sensitive details to unauthorized parties.
Prerequisite	The system is running Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access.
Testing Step	1. Check the /etc/issue file to determine if a local login warning banner is already configured. 2. If no banner is found, edit the file to include an appropriate warning message.
Test Data	Output from the configured /etc/issue file.
Expectation	The /etc/issue file contains a warning message, and this message is displayed on the terminal prior to login.

Actual Result	The /etc/issue file has been successfully updated with a local login warning message, and the message is displayed as expected.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.32 Rule ID 28538

Based on Table 2.32, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28538.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/issue
=====WARNING=====
Authorized uses only. All activity may be monitored and reported.
=====

```

Figure 2.110 Configuration Rule ID 28538

Based on Figure 2.110, Configuration has been done on the “/etc/issue” file to display a warning message on the login banner.

```

=====WARNING=====
Authorized uses only. All activity may be monitored and reported.
=====
WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer login:

```

Figure 2.111 Result Configuration Banner Login

Based on Figure 2.111, the login banner works successfully according to the configuration that has been done.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28538	Ensure local login warning banner is configured properly.	File: /etc/issue	Passed

Figure 2.112 Status Rule ID 28538

Based on Figure 2.112, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28538 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28539

Title	Ensure remote login warning banner is configured properly
Description	The /etc/issue.net file displays a warning message to users prior to login via remote access (e.g., SSH). This message informs users about the legal status of system access and

	applicable monitoring policies. To minimize the risk of unauthorized disclosure, operating system version details should be removed from this banner.
Prerequisite	The system is running Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check if /etc/issue.net contains a warning banner. 2. If not, edit the file to include a suitable warning message. 3. Ensure that the SSH daemon configuration (/etc/ssh/sshd_config) includes a directive pointing to /etc/issue.net via the Banner setting. 4. Restart the SSH service using systemctl restart sshd.
Test Data	Output from /etc/issue.net and /etc/ssh/sshd_config
Expectation	The /etc/issue.net file contains a valid warning message, and the message is displayed on remote login attempts via SSH.
Actual Result	The /etc/issue.net file has been updated with a remote login warning message and is displayed correctly during SSH login.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.33 Rule ID 28539

Based on Table 2.33, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28539.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# cat /etc/issue.net
=====Warning=====
Authorized uses only. All activity may be monitored and reported.
=====
```

Figure 2.113 Configuration Rule ID 28539

Based on Figure 2.113, the Configuration Banner login has been done in the “/etc/issue.net” file.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/ssh/sshd_config *
#AllowTcpForwarding yes
#GatewayPorts no
X11Forwarding yes
#X11DisplayOffset 10
#X11UseLocalhost yes
#PermitTTY yes
PrintMotd no
#PrintLastLog yes
#TCPKeepAlive yes
#PermitUserEnvironment no
#Compression delayed
#ClientAliveInterval 0
#ClientAliveCountMax 3
#UseDNS no
#PidFile /run/sshd.pid
#MaxStartups 10:30:100
#PermitTunnel no
#ChrootDirectory none
#VersionAddendum none

# no default banner path
Banner /etc/issue.net

```

Figure 2.114 Penambahan Configuration sshd

Based on Figure 2.114, so that the Configuration banner can run, a Configuration is added with the parameter “Banner /etc/issue.net” in the /etc/ssh/sshd_config file.

```

2025-04-16 02:18.36 /home/mobaxterm ssh Ilham-WazuhAgent@192.168.190.48
=====Warning=====
Authorized uses only. All activity may be monitored and reported.
=====
Ilham-WazuhAgent@192.168.190.48's password:

```

Figure 2.115 Result Configuration

Based on Figure 2.115, the login banner on SSH works normally.

ID	Title ↑	Target	Result
28539	Ensure remote login warning banner is configured properly.	File: /etc/issue.net	Passed

Figure 2.116 Status Rule ID 28539

Based on Figure 2.116, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28539 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28545

Title	Ensure chrony is running as user _chrony.
Description	The chronyd service is used for system time synchronization. To enhance security, the service should run with the minimum required privileges, using the dedicated _chrony user account. This limits potential damage if the service is compromised.

Prerequisite	Chrony is installed and active on Ubuntu Server 22.04.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Edit the configuration file <code>/etc/chrony/chrony.conf</code> and add the line: <code>user _chrony</code>. 2. Restart the Chrony service with <code>systemctl restart chrony</code>. 3. Run <code>ps -ef</code>
Test Data	Content from <code>/etc/chrony/chrony.conf</code> , and output from <code>ps -ef</code>
Expectation	The <code>chronyd</code> process is running under the <code>_chrony</code> user and not with elevated privileges like <code>root</code> .
Actual Result	The <code>chronyd</code> process successfully runs as user <code>_chrony</code> , confirming that least-privilege execution is enforced.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.34 Rule ID 28545

Based on Table 2.34, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28545.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/chrony/chrony.conf
# Stop bad estimates upsetting machine clock.
maxupdateskew 100.0

# This directive enables kernel synchronisation (every 11 minutes) of the
# real-time clock. Note that it can't be used along with the 'rtcfile' directive.
rtcsync

# Step the system clock instead of slewing it if the adjustment is larger than
# one second, but only in the first three clock updates.
makestep 1 3

# Get TAI-UTC offset and leap seconds from the system tz database.
# This directive must be commented out when using time sources serving
# leap-smearred time.
leapsectz right/UTC

# Running as user _chrony
user _chrony

```

Figure 2.117 Configuration Rule ID 28545

Based on Figure 2.117, Configuration has been added with the parameter “`user _chrony`” in the file “`/etc/chrony/chrony.conf`”

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# ps -ef | grep chronyd
_chrony 5271 1 0 22:01 ? 00:00:00 /usr/sbin/chronyd -F 1
_chrony 5272 5271 0 22:01 ? 00:00:00 /usr/sbin/chronyd -F 1

```

Figure 2.118 Result Configuration

Based on Figure 2.118, the `chrony` service has been running using the `_chrony` user.

ID	Title	Target	Result ↑
28545	Ensure chrony is running as user _chrony.	Command: ps -ef	● Passed ↓

Figure 2.119 Status Rule ID 28545

Based on Figure 2.119, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28545 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28546

Title	Ensure chrony is enabled and running.
Description	The chrony service must be enabled and running so that the system can synchronize time with the time server. Time synchronization is crucial to support time-based security mechanisms and ensure consistency of system log timestamps across the network, which is important for security forensic investigations.
Prerequisite	The chrony package must be installed on the system.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check if the chrony service is active by running the command <code>systemctl is-active chrony.service</code> 2. Check if the chrony service is enabled to start at boot by running <code>systemctl is-enabled chrony.service</code> 3. If either check is not satisfactory, unmask the service using <code>systemctl unmask chrony.service</code>, then enable and start it with <code>systemctl enable --now chrony.service</code>
Test Data	No specific test data is required.
Expectation	The chrony service is active (running) and enabled to start automatically on boot.
Actual Result	The chrony service is active (running) and enabled.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.35 Rule ID 28546

Based on Table 2.35, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28546.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl is-active chrony.service
active
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl is-enabled chrony.service
enabled
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# chronyc tracking

Reference ID      : 776E4A65 (119.110.74.101)
Stratum          : 3
Ref time (UTC)   : Mon Mar 10 19:29:09 2025
System time      : 0.000000000 seconds slow of NTP time
Last offset      : +0.012230828 seconds
RMS offset       : 0.012230828 seconds
Frequency        : 28.364 ppm fast
Residual freq    : -262.042 ppm
Skew             : 1000000.000 ppm
Root delay       : 0.040656433 seconds
Root dispersion  : 45.462268829 seconds
Update interval  : 0.0 seconds
Leap status      : Normal

```

Figure 2.120 Pengecekan Service Chrony

Based on Figure 2.120, the chrony service already has the status “active” and “enabled”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28546	Ensure chrony is enabled and running.	Command: ps -ef	Passed

Figure 2.121 Status Rule ID 28546

Based on Figure 2.121, the chrony service status is in accordance with the Rule ID 28546 policy, so the final status changes to “Passed”.

- ID 28547

Title	Ensure systemd-timesyncd is enabled and running
Description	The systemd-timesyncd service must be enabled and running so that the system can synchronize time with the time server. Time synchronization is crucial to support time-dependent security mechanisms and maintain consistent timestamps on log files across the network, which is useful in security forensic investigations.
Prerequisite	systemd-timesyncd must be installed on the system and not replaced by other time synchronization services such as chrony or ntpd.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check the status of the timesyncd service by running <code>systemctl is-active systemd-timesyncd.service</code> 2. Check if the timesyncd service is enabled to start at boot by running <code>systemctl is-enabled systemd-timesyncd.service</code>

	3. If either check fails, unmask the service using systemctl unmask systemd-timesyncd.service and enable it with systemctl enable --now systemd-timesyncd.service
Test Data	No specific test data is required.
Expectation	The timesyncd service is active (running) and enabled to start automatically at boot.
Actual Result	The timesyncd service is active (running) and enabled.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.36 Rule ID 28547

Based on Table 2.36, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28547.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# dpkg -l | grep systemd-timesyncd
ii systemd-timesyncd 249.11-0ubuntu3.12 amd64 minimalistic service to synchronize local time with
NTP servers
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl status systemd-timesyncd
● systemd-timesyncd.service - Network Time Synchronization
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/systemd-timesyncd.service; enabled; vendor preset: enabled)
   Active: active (running) since Thu 2025-03-27 02:09:23 WIB; 11min ago
     Docs: man:systemd-timesyncd.service(8)
   Main PID: 3802 (systemd-timesyn)
   Status: "idle."
   Tasks: 2 (limit: 4562)
   Memory: 1.3M
   CPU: 287ms
   CGroup: /system.slice/systemd-timesyncd.service
           └─3802 /lib/systemd/systemd-timesyncd

Mar 27 02:09:23 WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer systemd[1]: Starting Network Time Synchronization...
Mar 27 02:09:23 WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer systemd[1]: Started Network Time Synchronization.
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl is-enabled systemd-timesyncd
enabled
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent#

```

Figure 2.122 Status Service Systemd-Timesyncd

Based on Figure 2.122, the systemd-timesyncd service status is in the “running” and “enabled” conditions.

ID	Title ↑	Target	Result
28547	Ensure systemd-timesyncd is enabled and running.	Command: systemctl is-enabled systemd-timesyncd.service,systemctl is-active systemd-timesyncd.service	● Passed

Figure 2.123 Status Rule ID 28547

Based on Figure 2.123, the systemd-timesyncd service status is in accordance with the Rule ID 28547 policy, so the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28548

Title	Ensure ntp access control is configured
Description	If the NTP service is used on the system, proper access control configurations must be set to ensure secure time

	synchronization and prevent unauthorized modification or interrogation.
Prerequisite	NTP service is installed and used on the system (not chrony or systemd-timesyncd).
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check the contents of the configuration file /etc/ntp.conf to verify if the following lines exist: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - restrict -4 default kod nomodify notrap nopeer noquery - restrict -6 default kod nomodify notrap nopeer noquery 2. If the lines are missing, add them to the /etc/ntp.conf file. 3. Restart the NTP service using <code>systemctl restart ntp.service</code> to apply changes.
Test Data	Output of the /etc/ntp.conf configuration file.
Expectation	The NTP service is active and enabled, and the /etc/ntp.conf file contains the appropriate restrict lines with security parameters.
Actual Result	The NTP service is running active and enabled. The configuration changes in /etc/ntp.conf were successfully applied after restarting the service.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.37 Rule ID 28548

Based on Table 2.37, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28548.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/ntp.conf
filegen clockstats file clockstats type day enable

# Specify one or more NTP servers.

# Use servers from the NTP Pool Project. Approved by Ubuntu Technical Board
# on 2011-02-08 (LP: #104525). See http://www.pool.ntp.org/join.html for
# more information.
pool 0.ubuntu.pool.ntp.org iburst
pool 1.ubuntu.pool.ntp.org iburst
pool 2.ubuntu.pool.ntp.org iburst
pool 3.ubuntu.pool.ntp.org iburst

# Use Ubuntu's ntp server as a fallback.
pool ntp.ubuntu.com

# Access control configuration; see /usr/share/doc/ntp-doc/html/acconf.html for
# details. The web page <http://support.ntp.org/bin/view/Support/AccessRestrictions>
# might also be helpful.
#
# Note that "restrict" applies to both servers and clients, so a configuration
# that might be intended to block requests from certain clients could also end
# up blocking replies from your own upstream servers.

# By default, exchange time with everybody, but don't allow configuration.
restrict -4 default kod notrap nomodify nopeer noquery limited
restrict -6 default kod notrap nomodify nopeer noquery limited

```

Figure 2.124 Configuration Rule ID 28548

Based on Figure 2.124, the parameters “restrict -4 default kod notrap nomodify nopeer noquery limited” & “restrict -6 default kod notrap nomodify nopeer noquery limited” have been added to the file ”/etc/ntp.conf”.

ID	Title	Target	Result
28548	Ensure ntp access control is configured.	File: /etc/ntp.conf	Passed

Figure 2.125 Status Rule ID 28548

Based on Figure 2.125, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28548 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28549

Title	Ensure ntp is running as user ntp.
Description	The ntpd service must run with minimum privileges using a dedicated account named ntp to enhance security and limit unnecessary system access.
Prerequisite	The time synchronization service in use is ntp, not chrony or systemd-timesyncd.
Testing Step	1. Edit the file /etc/init.d/ntp and add the line RUNASUSER=ntp. 2. Restart the ntp service with systemctl restart ntp.service. 3. Run `ps -ef`
Test Data	Output from the file /etc/init.d/ntp.
Expectation	The ntpd process runs under the ntp user, and the file /etc/init.d/ntp is configured with RUNASUSER=ntp.
Actual Result	The ntp service runs successfully using the ntp user and not any other user.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.38 Rule ID 28549

Based on Table 2.38, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28549.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/init.d/ntp
#!/bin/sh

### BEGIN INIT INFO
# Provides:          ntp
# Required-Start:   $network $remote_fs $syslog
# Required-Stop:    $network $remote_fs $syslog
# Default-Start:    2 3 4 5
# Default-Stop:
# Short-Description: Start NTP daemon
### END INIT INFO

PATH=/sbin:/bin:/usr/sbin:/usr/bin

. /lib/lsb/init-functions

DAEMON=/usr/sbin/ntpd
PIDFILE=/var/run/ntpd.pid

test -x $DAEMON || exit 0

if [ -r /etc/default/ntp ]; then
. /etc/default/ntp
fi

if [ -e /run/ntp.conf.dhcp ]; then
NTPD_OPTS="$NTPD_OPTS -c /run/ntp.conf.dhcp"
fi

RUNASUSER=ntp

```

Figure 2.126 Configuration Rule ID 28549

Based on Figure 2.126, Configuration has been carried out with the parameter “RUNASUSER=ntp” in the file “/etc/init.d/ntp”.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# ps -ef | grep ntp
ntp      12065      1  0 22:57 ?        00:00:00 /usr/sbin/ntpd -p /var/run/ntpd.pid -g -u 116:110

```

Figure 2.127 Result Configuration

Based on Figure 2.127, the ntp service is already running using the ntp user.

ID	Title	Target	Result ↑
28549	Ensure ntp is running as user ntp.	Command: ps -ef	● Passed

Figure 2.128 Status Rule ID 28549

Based on Figure 2.128, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28549 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28550

Title	Ensure ntp is enabled and running.
Description	The ntp service must be active and configured to start automatically at system boot. This is essential to ensure consistent time synchronization and support system security and log integrity.

Prerequisite	The system uses ntp as the time synchronization service (not chrony or systemd-timesyncd).
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check if the ntp service is active by running <code>systemctl is-active ntp.service</code>. 2. Check if the ntp service is enabled by running <code>systemctl is-enabled ntp.service</code>. 3. If any of the checks fail, ensure the ntp service is unmasked
Test Data	No specific test data required.
Expectation	The ntp service is in an active and enabled state.
Actual Result	The ntp service runs successfully in active and enabled status.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.39 Rule ID 28550

Based on Table 2.39, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28550.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl is-active ntp.service
active
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl is-enabled ntp.service
enabled
```

Figure 2.129 Status Service ntp

Based on Figure 2.219, the NTP service is already in the “active” and “enabled” status.

ID	Title	Target	Result ↑
28550	Ensure ntp is enabled and running.	Command: systemctl is-enabled ntp.service	● Passed

Figure 2.130 Status Rule ID 28550

Based on Figure 2.130, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28550 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28561

Title	Ensure Samba is not installed.
Description	The samba package must not be installed on the system if there is no requirement to share files or directories with

	Windows systems. This helps reduce unnecessary attack surface.
Prerequisite	The system uses Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the command <code>dpkg-query -s samba</code> to check if the samba package is installed. 2. If installed, run <code>apt purge samba</code> to uninstall the samba package. 3. Verify again by running <code>dpkg-query -s samba</code>
Test Data	No specific test data required.
Expectation	The samba package is not installed on the system.
Actual Result	The samba package was installed on the system and has been successfully uninstalled.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.40 Rule ID 28561

Based on Table 2.40, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28561.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# sudo apt purge samba -y
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
Package 'samba' is not installed, so not removed
The following packages were automatically installed and are no longer required:
  apport-symptoms python3-apport python3-problem-report python3-systemd
Use 'sudo apt autoremove' to remove them.
0 upgraded, 0 newly installed, 0 to remove and 41 not upgraded.

```

Figure 2.131 Uninstall Samba

Based on Figure 2.131, uninstall the Samba service with the command “`sudo apt purge samba -y`”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28561	Ensure Samba is not installed.	Command: <code>dpkg-query -s samba; dpkg-query -W -f='\${binary:Package} \${Status} \${db:Status-Status}\n'</code> samba	Passed

Figure 2.132 Status Rule ID 28561

Based on Figure 2.132, after uninstalling Samba, according to the Rule ID 28561 policy, the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28566

Title	Ensure rsync service is either not installed or masked.
Description	The rsync service must be removed or stopped and masked to prevent its usage. This is because rsync uses an unencrypted protocol which can expose security risks in inter-system communication.
Prerequisite	The system uses Ubuntu Server 22.04 with systemd.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check the status of the rsync service with the command <code>systemctl is-active rsync</code>. 2. Check if the rsync service is enabled with the command <code>systemctl is-enabled rsync</code>. 3. If either check is not as expected, remove the rsync package using <code>apt purge rsync</code>.
Test Data	No specific test data required.
Expectation	The rsync package is not installed, or the rsync service is inactive and masked or disabled.
Actual Result	The rsync package has been successfully uninstalled.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.41 Rule ID 28566

Based on Table 2.41, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28566.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# sudo apt purge rsync -y
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
The following packages will be REMOVED:
  rsync* ubuntu-standard*
0 upgraded, 0 newly installed, 2 to remove and 40 not upgraded.
After this operation, 868 kB disk space will be freed.
(Reading database ... 75650 files and directories currently installed.)
Removing ubuntu-standard (1.481.3) ...
Removing rsync (3.2.7-0ubuntu0.22.04.4) ...

```

Figure 2.133 Uninstall rsync

Based on Figure 2.133, the rsync service has been uninstalled using the command “`sudo apt purge rsync -y`”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28566	Ensure rsync service is either not installed or masked.	Command: <code>dpkg-query -W -f='\${binary:Package} \${Status} \${db:Status-Status}\n' rsync</code>	● Passed

Figure 2.134 Status Rule ID 28566

Based on Figure 2.134, after uninstalling rsync, according to the Rule ID 28566 policy, the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28570

Title	Ensure telnet client is not installed.
Description	Telnet is an unencrypted communication protocol that can compromise the security of information such as login credentials. Therefore, the telnet package must not be installed on the system, and remote connections should be performed using secure protocols like SSH.
Prerequisite	The system uses Ubuntu Server 22.04.
Testing Step	1. Check if the telnet package is installed with the command <code>dpkg-query -s telnet</code> . 2. If installed, uninstall it using <code>apt purge telnet</code> .
Test Data	No specific test data required.
Expectation	The telnet service/package is not installed on the system.
Actual Result	The telnet service was installed but has been successfully uninstalled.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.42 Rule ID 28570

Based on Table 2.42, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28570.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# apt purge telnet -y
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
The following packages will be REMOVED:
 telnet*
0 upgraded, 0 newly installed, 1 to remove and 40 not upgraded.
After this operation, 158 kB disk space will be freed.
(Reading database ... 75613 files and directories currently installed.)
Removing telnet (0.17-44build1) ...
```

Figure 2.135 Uninstall Service telnet

Based on Figure 2.135, the telnet service has been uninstalled with the command “`apt purge telnet -y`”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28570	Ensure telnet client is not installed.	Command: dpkg-query -s telnet	Passed

Figure 2.136 Status Rule ID 28570

Based on Figure 2.136, after uninstalling telnet according to the Rule ID 28570 policy, the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28573

Title	Ensure UFW is installed
Description	UFW (Uncomplicated Firewall) is a simple interface for managing an iptables-based firewall. Using UFW facilitates administrators in configuring host-based firewall rules to prevent attacks from internal networks or misconfigured software.
Prerequisite	The system runs Ubuntu Server 22.04 with root access.
Testing Step	1. Check the UFW installation status with the command <code>dpkg-query -s ufw</code> . If the output contains <code>Status: install ok installed</code> , then UFW is installed. 2. If UFW is not installed, install it using <code>apt install ufw</code> .
Test Data	No specific test data required.
Expectation	The <code>ufw</code> package is installed with status <code>install ok installed</code> .
Actual Result	The UFW package has been successfully installed.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.43 Rule ID 28573

Based on Table 2.43, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28573.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# apt-get install ufw
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
The following packages were automatically installed and are no longer required:
  libevent-pthreads-2.1-7 libopts25 sntp
Use 'sudo apt autoremove' to remove them.
The following NEW packages will be installed:
  ufw

```

Figure 2.137 Install UFW

Based on Figure 2.137, the UFW package has been installed with the command “apt-get install ufw”.

ID	Title	Target	Result ↑
28573	Ensure ufw is installed.	Command: dpkg-query -s ufw	Passed

Figure 2.138 Status Rule ID 28573

Based on Figure 2.138, after the ufw service installation is carried out in accordance with the Rule ID 28573 policy, the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28574

Title	Ensure iptables-persistent is not installed with ufw.
Description	The iptables-persistent package is used to load iptables rules at boot time. If UFW is used, iptables-persistent should not be installed because both manage netfilter and may cause conflicts.
Prerequisite	The system uses UFW as the firewall management tool.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verify if iptables-persistent is installed by running the command <code>dpkg-query -s iptables-persistent</code>. 2. If installed, uninstall it by running <code>apt purge iptables-persistent</code>. 3. Verify again that iptables-persistent status is "not installed".
Test Data	No specific test data required.
Expectation	The iptables-persistent package is not installed, and UFW is installed.
Actual Result	The iptables-persistent package has been uninstalled and UFW remains installed.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.44 Rule ID 28574

Based on Table 2.44, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28574.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# apt purge iptables-persistent
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
Package 'iptables-persistent' is not installed, so not removed
The following package was automatically installed and is no longer required:
  netfilter-persistent
Use 'sudo apt autoremove' to remove it.
0 upgraded, 0 newly installed, 0 to remove and 60 not upgraded.

```

Figure 2.139 Uninstall Service iptables-persistent

Based on Figure 2.139, the iptables-persistent service has been uninstalled using the command “apt purge iptables-persistent”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28574	Ensure iptables-persistent is not installed with ufw.	Command: dpkg-query -s ufw,dpkg-query -s iptables-persistent	Passed

Figure 2.140 Status Rule ID 28574

Based on Figure 2.140, after uninstalling iptables-persistent according to the Rule ID 28574 policy, the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28575

Title	Ensure ufw service is enabled.
Description	The UFW (Uncomplicated Firewall) service must be active and running to ensure the system is protected by a firewall. UFW is a management interface for iptables and must be enabled for firewall rules to be enforced.
Prerequisite	UFW is already installed on the system.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check the status of the UFW service using the command <code>systemctl is-active ufw</code>. 2. Check if the UFW service is enabled with <code>systemctl is-enabled ufw.service</code>. 3. If either check fails, unmask the UFW service with <code>systemctl unmask ufw.service</code> and enable it immediately using <code>sudo systemctl --now enable ufw.service</code>.
Test Data	No specific test data required.
Expectation	The UFW service is active, enabled to start automatically at boot, and the status is active.
Actual Result	The UFW service is running and enabled.

Test Status	<i>Passed</i>
-------------	---------------

Table 2.45 Rule ID 28575

Based on Table 2.45, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28575.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl is-active ufw
active
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl is-enabled ufw.service
enabled
```

Figure 2.141 Status Service UFW

Based on Figure 2.141, the UFW service status is already in the “active” and “enabled” state.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28575	Ensure ufw service is enabled.	Command: systemctl is-enabled ufw.service,systemctl is-active ufw,ufw status	Passed

Figure 2.142 Status Rule ID 28575

Based on Figure 2.142, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28575 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28576

Title	Ensure ufw loopback traffic is configured.
Description	Loopback traffic is essential for internal communication between processes within the same machine. It must be allowed only on the loopback interface (lo) and denied on other interfaces to prevent traffic spoofing.
Prerequisite	UFW is installed on the system and currently active.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure UFW is configured to Allow Incoming traffic on the loopback interface (lo). 2. Ensure UFW is configured to Allow Outgoing traffic on the loopback interface (lo). 3. Ensure UFW is configured to Deny Incoming traffic from source IP 127.0.0.0/8 on other interfaces. 4. Ensure UFW is configured to Deny Incoming traffic from ::1 on other interfaces.

	5. Verify configuration using the command <code>ufw status verbose</code> .
Test Data	Output of <code>ufw status verbose</code> .
Expectation	Loopback rules are correctly configured to allow incoming and outgoing traffic only on interface <code>lo</code> and deny traffic from the loopback network on other interfaces.
Actual Result	Loopback interface is properly configured to allow inbound and outbound traffic, and deny loopback network traffic on other interfaces.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.46 Rule ID 28576

Based on Table 2.46, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28576.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# sudo ufw allow in on lo
Rule added
Rule added (v6)
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# sudo ufw allow out on lo
Rule added
Rule added (v6)
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# sudo ufw deny in from 127.0.0.0/8
Rule added
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# sudo ufw deny in from ::1
Rule added (v6)
```

Figure 2.143 Configuration Rule ID 28576

Based on Figure 2.143, Configuration has been carried out on UFW to set the loopback interface on the UFW Service.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# sudo ufw reload
Firewall reloaded
```

Figure 2.144 Restart Service UFW

Based on Figure 2.144, a reload of the UFW Service has been carried out, with the aim that the Configuration changes can run.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28576	Ensure ufw loopback traffic is configured.	Command: <code>dpkg -s ufw,ufw status verbose</code>	Passed

Figure 2.145 Status Rule ID 28576

Based on Figure 2.145, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28576 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28577

Title	Ensure ufw default deny firewall policy
Description	This rule ensures that the default policies on the UFW firewall deny all network traffic (Incoming, Outgoing, and Routed). This approach minimizes the risk of unwanted communications and reduces the security attack surface.
Prerequisite	1. UFW package must be installed on the system. 2. UFW firewall must be active (ufw enable has been executed).
Testing Step	1. Verify UFW is active by running the command <code>ufw status verbose</code> . 2. Check the default policies in the output and ensure Incoming, Outgoing, and Routed policies are set to deny. 3. If not, run the following commands: <code>ufw default deny incoming</code> <code>ufw default deny outgoing</code> <code>ufw default deny routed</code>
Test Data	Output from <code>ufw status verbose</code> .
Expectation	UFW default policies show "deny" or "reject" for Incoming, Outgoing, and Routed traffic.
Actual Result	UFW status shows default policies set to Deny for Incoming, Outgoing, and Routed traffic.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.47 Rule ID 28577

Based on Table 2.47, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28577.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# sudo ufw default deny incoming
Default incoming policy changed to 'deny'
(be sure to update your rules accordingly)
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# sudo ufw default deny outgoing
Default outgoing policy changed to 'deny'
(be sure to update your rules accordingly)
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# sudo ufw default deny routed
Default routed policy changed to 'deny'
(be sure to update your rules accordingly)
```

Figure 2.146 Configuration Rule ID 28577

Based on Figure 2.146, the default configuration for network traffic on the UFW Service is done as deny.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# ufw status verbose
Status: active
Logging: on (low)
Default: deny (incoming), deny (outgoing), deny (routed)
New profiles: skip
```

Figure 2.147 Status UFW

Based on Figure 2.147, the Default status for incoming, outgoing, and routed has been denied.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28577	Ensure ufw default deny firewall policy.	Command: dpkg -s ufw,ufw status verbose	Passed

Figure 2.148 Status Rule ID 28577

Based on Figure 2.148, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28577 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28578

Title	Ensure nftables is installed
Description	Nftables is a packet filtering system in the Linux kernel that can replace iptables. Only one firewall should be used at a time to avoid misconfiguration, which could cause loss of system connectivity.
Prerequisite	1. Root access on the Linux operating system. 2. Linux kernel version 3.13 or newer.
Testing Step	1. Check if nftables is installed and active by running dpkg -s nftables. 2. If not installed, install it with apt install nftables.
Test Data	No special test data required.
Expectation	The nftables package is installed and in an installed status, while iptables and ufw are not installed to prevent conflicts between firewall subsystems.

Actual Result	Nftables is installed and running. No other firewalls such as iptables or ufw are installed on the system.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.48 Rule ID 28578

Based on Table 2.48, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28578.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# apt install nftables
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
```

Figure 2.149 Install Nftables

Based on Figure 2.149, the nftables Service has been installed with the command “apt install nftables”.

ID	Title	Target	Result ↑
28578	Ensure nftables is installed.	Command: dpkg -s nftables	● Passed

Figure 2.150 Status Rule ID 28578

Based on Figure 2.150, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28578 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28579

Title	Ensure a nftables table exists.
Description	After installing nftables, nftables does not include any Tables by default. Tables in nftables are containers for chains which hold filtering rules. Without a Table, nftables cannot perform network traffic filtering. At least one Table must be created so the system can be filtered according to the applied security policies.
Prerequisite	1. Root access on the Linux operating system. 2. nftables package is installed and running on the system.
Testing Step	1. Check if any tables exist by running the command <code>sudo nft list tables</code> . 2. If no tables exist, create a Table with the command <code>nft create table inet filter</code>
Test Data	No special test data required.

Expectation	At least one active Table is listed in the nftables configuration. The output of nft list tables shows a valid Table name.
Actual Result	nftables is installed and running, and the list of Tables is present in the running nftables service.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.49 Rule ID 28579

Based on Table 2.49, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28579.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# nft create table inet filter
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# █
```

Figure 2.151 Configuration Rule ID 28579

Based on Figure 2.151, the Configuration has been carried out to create an nft Table with the command "nft create table inet filter".

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# nft list tables
table inet filter
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# █
```

Figure 2.152 Pengecekan status Table

Based on Figure 2.152, the command “nft list tables” was executed and the status was that the table was successfully created.

ID	Title	Target	Result ↑
28579	Ensure a nftables table exists.	Command: dpkg -s nftables	Passed

Figure 2.153 Status Rule ID 28579

Based on Figure 2.153, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28579 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28580

Title	Ensure nftables base chains exist
Description	Base chains are the primary entry points for packets coming from a network. Without base chains such as input, forward, and output, nftables cannot process incoming, forwarded, or

	outgoing packets. Therefore, at least one base chain must be created for each type of traffic.
Prerequisite	1. nftables is already installed. 2. An inet table has been created.
Testing Step	1. Check if base chains exist by running <code>nft list ruleset</code> . 2. If not present, create the base chains with the commands: <code>sudo nft create chain inet filter input { type filter hook input priority 0 \; }</code> <code>sudo nft create chain inet filter forward { type filter hook forward priority 0 \; }</code> <code>sudo nft create chain inet filter output { type filter hook output priority 0 \; }</code>
Test Data	No special test data required.
Expectation	There are base chains of type filter and hooks covering input, forward, and output in the nftables configuration.
Actual Result	Base chains for input, forward, and output exist in the nftables configuration.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.50 Rule ID 28580

Based on Table 2.50, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28580.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# nft add chain inet filter input { type filter hook input priority 0 \; }
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# nft add chain inet filter forward { type filter hook forward priority 0 \; }
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# nft add chain inet filter output { type filter hook output priority 0 \; }
```

Figure 2.154 Configuration Rule ID 28580

Based on Figure 2.154, the configuration for adding input, forward, and output filter chains has been carried out.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# nft list ruleset
table inet filter {
  chain input {
    type filter hook input priority filter; policy accept;
  }

  chain forward {
    type filter hook forward priority filter; policy accept;
  }

  chain output {
    type filter hook output priority filter; policy accept;
  }
}
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# █

```

Figure 2.155 Status nft list

Based on Figure 2.155, to verify the Configuration that has been done, do it by typing the command "nft list ruleset". It can be seen that the list ruleset contains chain information.

ID	Title	Target	Result ↑
28580	Ensure nftables base chains exist.	Command: dpkg -s nftables	Passed

Figure 2.156 Status Rule ID

Based on Figure 2.156, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28580 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28581

Title	Ensure nftables default deny firewall policy.
Description	The default policy on base chains determines the final action for packets that do not match any predefined rules. Setting the default policy to drop enhances security by ensuring only explicitly allowed traffic is accepted.
Prerequisite	1. nftables is installed and an inet table is created. 2. Base chains (input, output, and forward) exist on the inet table.
Testing Step	1. Run the command nft list ruleset. 2. Verify that the base chains have their default policy set to drop.
Test Data	No special test data required.
Expectation	All base chains (input, output, forward) have a default drop policy, ensuring any unauthorized traffic is rejected.

Actual Result	Base chains have a drop policy, allowing only traffic that matches defined rules.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.51 Rule ID 28581

Based on Table 51, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28581.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# nft add chain inet filter input { type filter hook input priority 0 \; policy drop \; }
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# nft add chain inet filter forward { type filter hook forward priority 0 \; policy drop \; }
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# nft add chain inet filter output { type filter hook output priority 0 \; policy drop \; }
```

Figure 2.157 Configuration Rule ID 28581

Based on Figure 2.157, Configuration has been carried out to make the default policy “drop”.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# nft list ruleset
table inet filter {
  chain input {
    type filter hook input priority filter; policy drop;
    tcp dport 22 accept
    udp dport 53 accept
    tcp dport 80 accept
    tcp dport 443 accept
    tcp dport 1515 accept
    tcp dport 1514 accept
    tcp dport 514 accept
    udp dport 514 accept
    tcp dport 55000 accept
    ct state established,related accept
  }

  chain forward {
    type filter hook forward priority filter; policy drop;
  }

  chain output {
    type filter hook output priority filter; policy drop;
    tcp sport 22 accept
    tcp dport 1514 accept
    tcp dport 80 accept
    tcp dport 443 accept
    tcp dport 53 accept
    udp dport 123 accept
  }
}
```

Figure 2.158 Status Default Policy Nft

Based on Figure 2.158, it is the result of the Configuration that has been carried out and it can be seen that the default policy has become “dropped”.

ID	Title	Target	Result ↑
28581	Ensure nftables default deny firewall policy.	Command: dpkg -s nftables,nft list ruleset	● Passed

Figure 2.159 Status Rule ID 285481

Based on Figure 2.159, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28581 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28582

Title	Ensure nftables service is enabled.
Description	The nftables service must load firewall rules from the configuration file /etc/nftables.conf during system boot or when the service starts. This ensures that firewall configurations remain active and consistent after reboot.
Prerequisite	The nftables package must already be installed on the system.
Testing Step	1. Check the nftables package installation status using the command: dpkg -s nftables 2. Ensure the nftables service is enabled to start automatically on boot with: systemctl enable nftables
Test Data	No specific test data required.
Expectation	The nftables service should be in an enabled state and automatically start when the system boots.
Actual Result	The nftables service is enabled and successfully runs automatically on system boot.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.52 Rule ID 28582

Based on Table 2.52, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28582.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl is-enabled nftables
enabled
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent#
```

Figure 2.160 Status Service Nftables

Based on Figure 2.160, the Service on nftables has been enabled.

ID	Title	Target	Result
28582	Ensure nftables service is enabled.	Command: dpkg -s nftables,systemctl is-enabled nftables	Passed

Figure 2.161 Status Rule ID 28582

Based on Figure 2.161, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28582 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28583

Title	Ensure iptables packages are installed.
Description	The packages iptables and iptables-persistent are required to manage host-based firewall. iptables is used to configure IPv4 firewall rules, while iptables-persistent ensures that the rules remain active after reboot.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Root access on the Linux operating system. 2. Ensure no conflict with other firewall utilities such as UFW and nftables.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check if iptables and iptables-persistent packages are installed using the commands <code>dpkg -s iptables</code> and <code>dpkg -s iptables-persistent</code>. 2. If not installed, install them using <code>apt install iptables iptables-persistent</code>.
Test Data	No special test data required.
Expectation	iptables and iptables-persistent packages are installed with status "install ok installed", and neither nftables nor ufw are installed on the system.
Actual Result	iptables and iptables-persistent packages are installed with status "install ok installed", and no ufw or nftables packages are installed.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.53 Rule ID 28583

Based on Table 2.53, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28583.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# dpkg -s iptables
Package: iptables
Status: install ok installed
Priority: optional
Section: net
Installed-Size: 2837
Maintainer: Ubuntu Developers <ubuntu-devel-discuss@lists.ubuntu.com>
Architecture: amd64
Multi-Arch: foreign
Version: 1.8.7-1ubuntu5.2

```

Figure 2.162 Status Service Iptables

Based on Figure 2.162, the status of the iptables Service has been installed, which can be seen in the “Status: install ok installed” section.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# dpkg -s iptables-persistent
Package: iptables-persistent
Status: install ok installed
Priority: optional
Section: admin
Installed-Size: 49
Maintainer: Ubuntu Developers <ubuntu-devel-discuss@lists.ubuntu.com>
Architecture: all
Version: 1.0.16

```

Figure 2.163 Status Service Iptables-Persistent

Based on Figure 2.163, the status of the iptables-persistent Service has been installed. If the iptables and iptables-persistent Services are not installed, they can be installed by typing the command “apt install iptables iptables-persistent”.

ID	Title	Target	Result ↑
28583	Ensure iptables packages are installed.	Command: dpkg -s iptables,dpkg -s iptables-persistent	● Passed

Figure 2.164 Status Rule ID 28583

Based on Figure 2.164, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28583 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28584

Title	Ensure nftables is not installed with iptables
Description	Ensure that the nftables package is not installed alongside iptables on the system, as this can cause conflicts in firewall configuration.
Prerequisite	The iptables package must be installed on the system.

Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verify iptables installation by running: <code>dpkg-query -s iptables</code>. 2. Check if nftables is installed by running: <code>dpkg-query -s nftables</code>. 3. If nftables is installed, uninstall it using: <code>apt purge nftables</code>.
Test Data	Installation status of nftables and iptables packages.
Expectation	iptables is installed and no nftables package is found on the system.
Actual Result	iptables is installed and running normally with no nftables package present on the system.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.54 Rule ID 28584

Based on Table 2.54, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28584.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# apt purge nftables
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
The following packages were automatically installed and are no longer required:
 libevent-pthreads-2.1-7 libnftables1 libopts25 sntp
Use 'sudo apt autoremove' to remove them.
The following packages will be REMOVED:
 nftables*
0 upgraded, 0 newly installed, 1 to remove and 48 not upgraded.
After this operation, 181 kB disk space will be freed.
Do you want to continue? [Y/n] y
(Reading database ... 75743 files and directories currently installed.)
Removing nftables (1.0.2-1ubuntu3) ...

```

Figure 2.165 Uninstall Nftables

Based on Figure 2.165, uninstall the nftables Service with the command “`apt purge nftables`”.

ID	Title	Target	Result ↑
28584	Ensure nftables is not installed with iptables.	Command: <code>dpkg-query -s nftables</code>	● Passed

Figure 2.166 Status Rule ID 28584

Based on Figure 2.166, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28584 policy, with the status of nftables uninstalled and iptables installed, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28585

Title	Ensure ufw is uninstalled or disabled with iptables
Description	The UFW package must not be active or installed together with iptables, as it can cause firewall configuration conflicts.
Prerequisite	The iptables package must already be installed.
Testing Step	1. Verify iptables is installed by running: <code>dpkg-query -s iptables</code> . 2. Check if ufw is installed by running: <code>dpkg-query -s ufw</code> . 3. If ufw is installed, uninstall it using: <code>apt purge ufw</code> .
Test Data	Installation status of ufw and iptables packages.
Expectation	iptables is installed and no ufw package is found on the system.
Actual Result	Iptables is installed and running normally without ufw present on the system.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.55 Rule ID 28585

Based on Table 2.55, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28585.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# apt purge ufw
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
The following packages were automatically installed and are no longer required:
 libevent-pthreads-2.1-7 libopts25 sntp
Use 'sudo apt autoremove' to remove them.
The following packages will be REMOVED:
 ufw*
0 upgraded, 0 newly installed, 1 to remove and 48 not upgraded.
After this operation, 850 kB disk space will be freed.

```

Figure 2.167 Uninstall UFW

Based on Figure 2.167, uninstall the UFW package with the command “`apt purge ufw`”.

ID	Title	Target	Result ↑
28585	Ensure ufw is uninstalled or disabled with iptables.	Command: <code>dpkg-query -s ufw</code>	● Passed

Figure 2.168 Status Rule ID 28585

Based on Figure 2.168, the configuration has been carried out in accordance with the Rule ID 28585 policy, with the status of ufw uninstalled and iptables installed, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28586

Title	Ensure iptables default deny firewall policy
Description	Default DROP policy in iptables to ensure all traffic that is not explicitly configured will be denied.
Prerequisite	iptables package must be installed on the system.
Testing Step	1. Verify iptables is installed by running: <code>dpkg-query -s iptables</code> . 2. Run <code>iptables -L</code> to check the current policies. 3. If any chain policy is not set to DROP, remediate using: <code>iptables -P INPUT drop</code> <code>iptables -P FORWARD drop</code> <code>iptables -P OUTPUT drop</code>
Test Data	Default iptables policies showing DROP on INPUT, FORWARD, and OUTPUT chains.
Expectation	All chains (INPUT, OUTPUT, FORWARD) have a default DROP or REJECT policy.
Actual Result	All default iptables chain policies are set to DROP for INPUT, FORWARD, and OUTPUT.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.56 Rule ID 28586

Based on Table 2.56, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28586.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# iptables -F INPUT DROP
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# iptables -F OUTPUT DROP
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# iptables -F FORWARD DROP
```

Figure 2.169 Configuration Rule ID 28586

Based on Figure 2.169, the Configuration has been done to perform "DROP" on input, output, and forward on the iptables Service.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# iptables -L -v -n
Chain INPUT (policy DROP 4 packets, 208 bytes)
 pkts bytes target    prot opt in     out     source         destination
  10   805 ACCEPT    all  --  lo      *       0.0.0.0/0      0.0.0.0/0
   0     0 DROP      all  --  *       *       127.0.0.0/8    0.0.0.0/0
 136 12613 ACCEPT    tcp  --  *       *       0.0.0.0/0      0.0.0.0/0          tcp dpt:22

Chain FORWARD (policy DROP 0 packets, 0 bytes)
 pkts bytes target    prot opt in     out     source         destination

Chain OUTPUT (policy DROP 245 packets, 19787 bytes)
 pkts bytes target    prot opt in     out     source         destination
  10   805 ACCEPT    all  --  *       lo      0.0.0.0/0      0.0.0.0/0
  85 13216 ACCEPT    tcp  --  *       *       0.0.0.0/0      0.0.0.0/0          tcp spt:22

```

Figure 2.170 Result Configuration

Based on Figure 2.170, it can be seen that the iptables Service for the input, forward and output chains has performed a “DROP”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28586	Ensure iptables default deny firewall policy.	Command: iptables -L	Passed

Figure 2.171 Status Rule ID

Based on Figure 2.171, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28586 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- ID 28587

Title	Ensure iptables loopback traffic is configured.
Description	Loopback traffic occurs between processes within the system and is critical for system operations. The loopback interface (127.0.0.0/8) must only accept traffic internally, while other interfaces must reject traffic from this network to prevent spoofing. Firewall configuration must allow traffic from the loopback interface and deny traffic from 127.0.0.0/8 on all other interfaces.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure iptables is installed on the system. 2. Ubuntu 22.04 server with root access.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verify iptables installation with <code>dpkg-query -s iptables</code>. 2. Run <code>iptables -L</code> to verify that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incoming traffic on the loopback interface (lo) is allowed. - Outgoing traffic on lo is allowed. - Incoming traffic from 127.0.0.0/8 on other interfaces is dropped.

	3. If conditions in step 2 are not met, run: iptables -A INPUT -i lo -j ACCEPT iptables -A OUTPUT -o lo -j ACCEPT iptables -A INPUT -s 127.0.0.0/8 -j DROP
Test Data	Iptables policy status on the loopback interface (lo).
Expectation	Firewall rules must accept traffic from the loopback interface (lo) and reject traffic from the 127.0.0.0/8 network on all other interfaces.
Actual Result	Iptables firewall rules on the loopback interface accept traffic and deny traffic originating from 127.0.0.0/8 on other interfaces.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.57 Rule ID 28587

Based on Table 2.57, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28587.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# iptables -A INPUT -i lo -j ACCEPT
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# iptables -A OUTPUT -o lo -j ACCEPT
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# iptables -A INPUT -s 127.0.0.0/8 -j DROP
```

Figure 2.172 Configuration Rule ID 28587

Based on Figure 2.172, the configuration has been done to accept traffic from the loopback interface and reject all traffic originating from the 127.0.0.0/8 network.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# iptables -L INPUT -v -n
Chain INPUT (policy ACCEPT 3298 packets, 434K bytes)
 pkts bytes target    prot opt in     out     source    destination
  0      0 ACCEPT    all  --  lo     *       0.0.0.0/0  0.0.0.0/0
  0      0 DROP     all  --  *     *       127.0.0.0/8  0.0.0.0/0
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# iptables -L OUTPUT -v -n
Chain OUTPUT (policy ACCEPT 4215 packets, 787K bytes)
 pkts bytes target    prot opt in     out     source    destination
  0      0 ACCEPT    all  --  *     lo      0.0.0.0/0  0.0.0.0/0
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# █
```

Figure 2.173 Result Configuration Rule ID 28587

Based on Figure 2.173, it is the result of the configuration that has been carried out on iptables.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28587	Ensure iptables loopback traffic is configured.	Command: iptables -L INPUT -v -n	● Passed

Figure 2.174 Status Rule ID 28587

Based on Figure 2.174, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28587 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28588

Title	Ensure iptables default deny firewall policy.
Description	Firewall policy with default "deny" ensures all unspecified network usage is blocked. Using a "deny all" policy is safer than "accept all" because it is easier to explicitly allow desired traffic rather than block unwanted traffic. With this policy, only explicitly permitted traffic is accepted.
Prerequisite	1. Ensure iptables is installed on the system. 2. Ubuntu 22.04 server with root access.
Testing Step	1. Verify iptables installation using <code>dpkg-query -s iptables</code> . 2. Run <code>iptables -L</code> to verify whether the default policies for chains INPUT, FORWARD, and OUTPUT are set to DROP. 3. If not set properly, run: <code>iptables -P INPUT DROP</code> <code>iptables -P OUTPUT DROP</code> <code>iptables -P FORWARD DROP</code>
Test Data	Default policy status on the iptables firewall.
Expectation	The default policies on the INPUT, FORWARD, and OUTPUT chains must be set to "DROP."
Actual Result	The default iptables policies on INPUT, FORWARD, and OUTPUT chains have been set to "DROP."
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.58 Rule ID 28588

Based on Table 2.58, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28588.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# iptables -P INPUT DROP
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# iptables -P OUTPUT DROP
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# iptables -P FORWARD DROP
```

Figure 2.175 Configuration Rule ID 28588

Based on Figure 2.175, the configuration for input, output and forward on iptables has been done with the default action “DROP”.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# ip6tables -L
Chain INPUT (policy DROP)
target    prot opt source                destination

Chain FORWARD (policy DROP)
target    prot opt source                destination

Chain OUTPUT (policy DROP)
target    prot opt source                destination
  
```

Figure 2.176 Result Configuration Rule ID 28588

Based on Figure 2.176, the default status in Iptables has become “DROP”.

ID	Title	Target	Result
28588	Ensure ip6tables default deny firewall policy.	Command: ip6tables -L	Passed

Figure 2.177 Status Rule ID 28588

Based on Figure 2.177, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28588 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28589

Title	Ensure ip6tables loopback traffic is configured.
Description	Loopback traffic is used for communication between processes on the same machine. The loopback interface should only accept traffic from the loopback network (:::1), while other interfaces must reject traffic from this address to prevent spoofing. ip6tables must be configured to accept traffic from the loopback interface and deny traffic from the loopback address on other interfaces.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure iptables is installed on the system. 2. Ubuntu 22.04 server with root access.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verify that iptables is installed by running <code>dpkg-query -s iptables</code>. 2. Run <code>ip6tables -L</code> to verify if the default policies for INPUT, FORWARD, and OUTPUT chains are set to DROP. 3. If not properly configured, apply:

	ip6tables -P INPUT DROP ip6tables -P OUTPUT DROP ip6tables -P FORWARD DROP
Test Data	ip6tables policy status for the loopback interface.
Expectation	ip6tables should allow all traffic on the loopback (lo) interface and deny traffic from the loopback address (::1) on other interfaces.
Actual Result	The ip6tables policy for loopback interface has been correctly configured. The loopback interface accepts all traffic while traffic from ::1 is rejected on all other interfaces.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.59 Rule ID 28589

Based on Table 2.59, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28589.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# ip6tables -A INPUT -i lo -j ACCEPT
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# ip6tables -A OUTPUT -o lo -j ACCEPT
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# ip6tables -A INPUT -s ::1 -j DROP
```

Figure 2.178 Configuration Rule ID 28589

Based on Figure 2.178, a configuration has been performed to perform a DROP originating from the loopback interface to another interface and receive all traffic originating from or going to the loopback interface.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# ip6tables -L -v -n
Chain INPUT (policy DROP 0 packets, 0 bytes)
 pkts bytes target    prot opt in     out     source     destination
    0    0 ACCEPT  all  lo    *      ::/0       ::/0
    0    0 DROP    all  *    *      ::1        ::/0

Chain FORWARD (policy DROP 0 packets, 0 bytes)
 pkts bytes target    prot opt in     out     source     destination

Chain OUTPUT (policy DROP 1 packets, 56 bytes)
 pkts bytes target    prot opt in     out     source     destination
    0    0 ACCEPT  all  *    lo    ::/0       ::/0
```

Figure 2.179 Result Configuration Rule ID 28589

Based on Figure 2.179, the iptables configuration for the loopback interface has been successfully performed.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28589	Ensure iptables loopback traffic is configured.	Command: iptables -L INPUT -v -n	Passed

Figure 2.180 Status Rule ID 28589

Based on Figure 2.180, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28589 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28590

Title	Ensure auditd is installed.
Description	Auditd is a component of the Linux Auditing System. It is responsible for writing audit records to disk, helping system administrators monitor and detect unauthorized access to the system.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu 22.04 server with root access. 2. Internet connection to install necessary packages.
Testing Step	1. Run <code>dpkg-query -s auditd</code> and <code>dpkg-query -s audispd-plugins</code> to ensure the packages are correctly installed. 2. If the packages are not installed, run <code>apt-get install auditd audispd-plugins</code> .
Test Data	Installation status of auditd and audispd-plugins packages.
Expectation	The auditd and audispd-plugins packages should be installed.
Actual Result	The auditd and audispd-plugins packages are already installed on the system.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.60 Rule ID 28590

Based on Table 2.60, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28590.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# apt install auditd audispd-plugins -y
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
The following additional packages will be installed:
  libauparse0
The following NEW packages will be installed:
  audispd-plugins auditd libauparse0
0 upgraded, 3 newly installed, 0 to remove and 40 not upgraded.
Need to get 309 kB of archives.
After this operation, 1,013 kB of additional disk space will be used.
Get:1 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy/main amd64 libauparse0 amd64 1:3.0.7-1build1 [58.0 kB]
Get:2 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy/main amd64 auditd amd64 1:3.0.7-1build1 [212 kB]
Get:3 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy/universe amd64 audispd-plugins amd64 1:3.0.7-1build1 [39.1 kB]

```

Figure 2.181 Install Auditd

Based on Figure 2.181, a command is executed to install the auditd package with the command "apt install auditd audispd-plugins -y".

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# dpkg-query -s auditd
Package: auditd
Status: install ok installed
Priority: optional
Section: admin
Installed-Size: 690
Maintainer: Ubuntu Developers <ubuntu-devel-discuss@lists.ubuntu.com>
Architecture: amd64
Source: audit
Version: 1:3.0.7-1build1
```

Figure 2.182 Result Install

Based on Figure 2.182, auditd was successfully installed, as evidenced by “Status: install ok installed”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28590	Ensure auditd is installed.	Command: dpkg-query -s auditd	Passed

Figure 2.183 Status Rule ID 28590

Based on Figure 2.183, after auditd was successfully installed, the status of Rule ID 28590 has become “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28591

Title	Ensure auditd service is enabled and active.
Description	Auditd must be running and enabled at boot to ensure that the system logs security-relevant events. This is essential for monitoring system activity and detecting unauthorized access.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu 22.04 server with root access. 2. The auditd package must be installed on the system.
Testing Step	1. Run <code>systemctl is-active auditd</code> — the result should be "active". 2. Run <code>systemctl is-enabled auditd</code> — the result should be "enabled". 3. If not active and enabled, run <code>systemctl --now enable auditd</code> .

Test Data	No specific test data required.
Expectation	The auditd service should be active and enabled to start automatically at system boot.
Actual Result	The auditd service is active and enabled.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.61 Rule ID 28591

Based on Table 2.61, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28591.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl enable --now auditd
systemctl status auditd
Synchronizing state of auditd.service with SysV service script with /lib/systemd/systemd-sysv-install.
Executing: /lib/systemd/systemd-sysv-install enable auditd
● auditd.service - Security Auditing Service
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/auditd.service; enabled; vendor preset: enabled)
   Active: active (running) since Tue 2025-03-11 06:30:05 WIB; 2min 7s ago
     Docs: man:auditd(8)
           https://github.com/linux-audit/audit-documentation
   Main PID: 4690 (auditd)
     Tasks: 2 (limit: 4562)
    Memory: 484.0K
       CPU: 258ms
   CGroup: /system.slice/auditd.service
           └─4690 /sbin/auditd

```

Figure 2.184 Enable auditd

Based on Figure 2.184, after the auditd installation is complete, the next step is to activate the auditd package, by running the command “systemctl enable –now auditd”.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl is-active auditd
active
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl is-enabled auditd
enabled
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# █

```

Figure 2.185 Status Auditd

Based on Figure 2.185, the status on auditd is “active” and “enable”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28591	Ensure auditd service is enabled and active.	Command: systemctl is-enabled auditd	● Passed

Figure 2. 186 Status Rule ID 28591

Based on Figure 2.186, after the auditd Service status becomes “active” and “enable”, the status on Rule ID 28591 changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28592

Title	Ensure auditing for processes that start prior to auditd is enabled.
Description	Audit must be enabled from the beginning of the boot process to ensure that system activities, including those that occur before auditd starts, are logged. This helps prevent suspicious activities from going undetected.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu 22.04 server with root access. 2. The system must use GRUB as its bootloader.
Testing Step	1. Open the file /etc/default/grub and ensure that the line GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX contains audit=1. 2. If missing, edit /etc/default/grub and add audit=1 to the GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX variable. 3. Save the changes by running update-grub.
Test Data	Value of the audit=1 parameter in the GRUB configuration.
Expectation	The line GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX in /etc/default/grub should contain audit=1.
Actual Result	The file /etc/default/grub already contains audit=1 in the GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX variable.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.62 Rule ID 28592

Based on Table 2.62, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28592.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/default/grub
# If you change this file, run 'update-grub' afterwards to update
# /boot/grub/grub.cfg.
# For full documentation of the options in this file, see:
info -f grub -n 'Simple configuration'

GRUB_DEFAULT=0
GRUB_TIMEOUT_STYLE=hidden
GRUB_TIMEOUT=0
GRUB_DISTRIBUTOR=`lsb_release -i -s 2> /dev/null || echo Debian`
GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX_DEFAULT="quiet splash noprompt noshell automatic-ubiquity debian-installer/l
GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX="apparmor=1 security=apparmor audit=1"

```

Figure 2.187 Configuration Rule ID 28592

Based on Figure 2.187, Configuration has been added to the “/etc/default/grub” file in the “GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX” line with the “audit=1” parameter.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28592	Ensure auditing for processes that start prior to auditd is enabled.	Directory: /boot	● Passed

Figure 2.188 Status Rule ID 28592

Based on Figure 2.188, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28592 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28593

Title	Ensure audit_backlog_limit is sufficient.
Description	The audit_backlog_limit parameter defines the maximum number of audit events that can be queued in the kernel before being passed to auditd. This value should be sufficiently high to prevent the loss of audit events during system activity spikes.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ubuntu 22.04 server with root access. 2. The system must use GRUB as its bootloader.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the file /etc/default/grub and ensure that the GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX line contains audit_backlog_limit=8192. 2. If it's missing, edit the /etc/default/grub file and add audit_backlog_limit=8192 or higher to the GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX variable. 3. Save the changes by running update-grub.
Test Data	The /etc/default/grub file contains the parameter audit_backlog_limit=8192 or higher.
Expectation	The GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX line in the /etc/default/grub file should contain audit_backlog_limit=8192.
Actual Result	The /etc/default/grub file already includes audit_backlog_limit=8192 in the GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX variable.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.63 Rule ID 28593

Based on Table 2.63, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28593.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/default/grub
# If you change this file, run 'update-grub' afterwards to update
# /boot/grub/grub.cfg.
# For full documentation of the options in this file, see:
# info -f grub -n 'Simple configuration'

GRUB_DEFAULT=0
GRUB_TIMEOUT_STYLE=hidden
GRUB_TIMEOUT=0
GRUB_DISTRIBUTOR=`lsb_release -i -s 2> /dev/null || echo Debian`
GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX_DEFAULT="quiet splash noprompt noshell automatic-ubiquity debian-installer/locale=en_US
GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX="audit=1 apparmor=1 audit_backlog_limit=8192 security=apparmor"

```

Figure 2.189 Configuration Rule ID 28593

Based on Figure 2.189, Configuration has been added to the /etc/default/grub file, in the line “GRUB_CMDLINE_LINUX” with the addition of the parameter “audit_backlog_limit=8192”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28593	Ensure audit_backlog_limit is sufficient.	Directory: /boot	Passed

Figure 2.190 Status Rule ID 28593

Based on Figure 2.190, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28593 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28594

Title	Ensure audit log storage size is configured
Description	Configuring the maximum audit log file size helps prevent excessive disk space usage and avoids the loss of audit data due to uncontrolled log growth.
Prerequisite	1. Ubuntu 22.04 server with root access. 2. auditd package must already be installed on the system.
Testing Step	1. Open the file /etc/audit/auditd.conf and check whether the max_log_file parameter exists. 2. If not, add the max_log_file parameter with a value that aligns with your log retention policy. 3. Save the changes and restart the auditd service using the command <code>systemctl restart auditd</code> .

Test Data	The /etc/audit/auditd.conf file contains the max_log_file parameter.
Expectation	The /etc/audit/auditd.conf file should contain max_log_file = <value>, where <value> is a numeric value defined by the organization's storage policy.
Actual Result	The /etc/audit/auditd.conf file already contains the max_log_file parameter with a specified numeric value.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.64 Rule ID 28594

Based on Table 2.64, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28594.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/audit/auditd.conf
###
# This file controls the configuration of the audit daemon
#

local_events = yes
write_logs = yes
log_file = /var/log/audit/audit.log
log_group = adm
log_format = ENRICHED
flush = INCREMENTAL_ASYNC
freq = 50
max_log_file = 80
num_logs = 5
priority_boost = 4
name_format = NONE
##name = mydomain
max_log_file_action = keep_logs
space_left = 75
space_left_action = email
verify_email = yes
action_mail_acct = root

```

Figure 2.191 Configuration Rule ID 28594

Based on Figure 2.191, the Configuration is added to the /etc/audit/auditd.conf file with the parameter “max_log_file = 80”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28594	Ensure audit log storage size is configured.	Directory: /etc/audit	● Passed

Figure 2.192 Status Rule ID 28594

Based on Figure 2.192, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28594 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28595

Title	Ensure audit logs are not automatically deleted.
-------	--

Description	Configure the system to not automatically delete audit logs, as they are required for historical auditing purposes.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ubuntu 22.04 server with root access. 2. The auditd package must already be installed on the system.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the file /etc/audit/auditd.conf and verify whether the max_log_file_action parameter exists. 2. If not present, add the line max_log_file_action = keep_logs. 3. Save the file and restart the auditd service with systemctl restart auditd.
Test Data	The /etc/audit/auditd.conf file contains the max_log_file_action parameter.
Expectation	The /etc/audit/auditd.conf file must contain the parameter max_log_file_action = keep_logs to ensure old logs are preserved after log rotation.
Actual Result	The /etc/audit/auditd.conf file already contains the max_log_file_action parameter set to keep_logs.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.65 Rule ID 28595

Based on Table 2.65, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28595.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/audit/auditd.conf
###
# This file controls the configuration of the audit daemon
#

local_events = yes
write_logs = yes
log_file = /var/log/audit/audit.log
log_group = adm
log_format = ENRICHED
flush = INCREMENTAL_ASYNC
freq = 50
max_log_file = 80
num_logs = 5
priority_boost = 4
name_format = NONE
##name = mydomain
max_log_file_action = keep_logs
space_left = 75
space_left_action = email

```

Figure 2.193 Configuration Rule ID 28595

Based on Figure 2.193, Configuration has been added to the “/etc/audit/auditd.conf” file with the parameter “max_log_file_action = keep_logs”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28595	Ensure audit logs are not automatically deleted.	Directory: /etc/audit	● Passed

Figure 2.194 Status Rule ID 28595

Based on Figure 2.194, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28595 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28596

Title	Ensure system is disabled when audit logs are full.
Description	Configure auditd so that the system sends an email alert and either halts or enters single-user mode when audit logs are full.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ubuntu 22.04 server with root access. 2. The auditd package must already be installed on the system.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the /etc/audit/auditd.conf file and verify the existence of the parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - space_left_action - action_mail_acct - admin_space_left_action 2. If not present, add the following lines: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - space_left_action = email - action_mail_acct = root - admin_space_left_action = halt (or single) 3. Save the file and restart auditd with systemctl restart auditd.
Test Data	/etc/audit/auditd.conf file contains the parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - space_left_action = email - action_mail_acct = root - admin_space_left_action = halt or single
Expectation	The file /etc/audit/auditd.conf must contain the configured parameters for log space management and alerts.

Actual Result	The /etc/audit/auditd.conf file already contains the parameters space_left_action, action_mail_acct, and admin_space_left_action as configured.
Test Status	Passed

Table 2.66 Rule ID 28596

Based on Table 2.66, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28596.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/audit/auditd.conf
##
# This file controls the configuration of the audit daemon
#
local_events = yes
write_logs = yes
log_file = /var/log/audit/audit.log
log_group = adm
log_format = ENRICHED
flush = INCREMENTAL_ASYNC
freq = 50
max_log_file = 80
num_logs = 5
priority_boost = 4
name_format = NONE
##name = mydomain
max_log_file_action = keep_logs
space_left = 75
space_left_action = email
verry_email = yes
action_mail_acct = root
admin_space_left = 50
admin_space_left_action = halt
disk_full_action = SUSPEND
disk_error_action = SUSPEND

```

Figure 2.195 Configuration Rule ID 28596

Based on Figure 2.195, the parameters “space_left_action”, “action_mail_acct”, “admin_space_left_action” have been added to the “/etc/audit/auditd.conf” file.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28596	Ensure system is disabled when audit logs are full.	Directory: /etc/audit	Passed

Figure 2.196 Status Rule ID 28596

Based on Figure 2.196, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28596 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28597

Title	Ensure changes to system administration scope (sudoers) is collected.
-------	---

Description	Configure the audit system to monitor and log any changes made to the /etc/sudoers file and the /etc/sudoers.d directory. These files define administrative privileges through the sudo mechanism. Logging changes helps administrators detect unauthorized attempts to alter user privilege scopes.
Prerequisite	1. auditd package must be installed and running. 2. Root access is required to add audit rules.
Testing Step	1. Create a new audit rule file using the command: nano /etc/audit/rules.d/50-scope.rules 2. Add the following lines: -w /etc/sudoers -p wa -k scope -w /etc/sudoers.d -p wa -k scope 3. Load the audit rules using: augenrules --load
Test Data	Content of /etc/audit/rules.d/50-scope.rules file containing audit rules for /etc/sudoers and /etc/sudoers.d.
Expectation	Audit rules for /etc/sudoers and /etc/sudoers.d with permissions wa and key scope should be configured.
Actual Result	Audit rules for /etc/sudoers and /etc/sudoers.d have been successfully added in the 50-scope.rules file with write (w) and attribute (a) monitoring.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.67 Rule ID 28597

Based on Table 2.67, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28597.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# cat /etc/audit/rules.d/50-scope.rules
-w /etc/sudoers -p wa -k scope
-w /etc/sudoers.d -p wa -k scope
```

Figure 2.197 Configuration Rule ID 28597

Based on Figure 2.197, the parameters “-w /etc/sudoers -p wa -k scope” and “-w /etc/sudoers.d -p wa -k scope” have been added to the file “/etc/audit/rules.d/50-scope.rules”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28597	Ensure changes to system administration scope (sudoers) is collected.	Directory: /etc/audit/rules.d	● Passed

Figure 2.198 Status Rule ID 28597

Based on Figure 2.198, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28597 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28598

Title	Ensure changes to system administration scope (sudoers) is collected.
Description	Ensure all actions performed using temporary elevated privileges (e.g., via sudo) are recorded in the audit logs. This is essential to identify actions taken by users who temporarily gain privileges of another user (e.g., root).
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. auditd package must be installed and running. 2. Root access is required to add audit rules
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the command <code>auditctl -l</code> to list current audit rules. 2. Verify if a rule exists with the key <code>user_emulation</code>. 3. If not present, create the file <code>/etc/audit/rules.d/50-user_emulation.rules</code>. 4. Add the following rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -a always,exit -F arch=b64 -C euid!=uid -F auid!=unset -S execve -k user_emulation -a always,exit -F arch=b32 -C euid!=uid -F auid!=unset -S execve -k user_emulation 5. Reload the audit rules using <code>augenrules --load</code>.
Test Data	The file <code>/etc/audit/rules.d/50-user_emulation.rules</code> contains the appropriate rules for both b32 and b64 architectures with the key <code>user_emulation</code> .
Expectation	Audit rules to monitor command executions where the euid differs from uid (indicating privilege escalation) must be present for both b32 and b64 architectures, using the key <code>user_emulation</code> .

Actual Result	The audit rules with key user_emulation have been successfully configured in the /etc/audit/rules.d/50-user_emulation.rules file.
Test Status	Passed

Table 2.68 Rule ID 28598

Based on Table 68, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28598.

```

GNU nano 6.2 50-user_emulation.rules
#System 64 Bit
-a always,exit -F arch=b64 -C euid!=uid -F auid!=1 -S execve -k user_emulation
-a always,exit -F arch=b32 -C euid!=uid -F auid!=1 -S execve -k user_emulation

```

Figure 2.199 Rule ID 28598

Based on Figure 2.199, Configuration has been carried out in the file "/etc/audit/rules.d/50-user_emulation.rules" by adding the parameters "-a always,exit -F arch=b64 -C euid!=uid -F auid!=1 -s execve -k user_emulation" and "-a always,exit -F arch=b32 -C euid!=uid -F auid!=1 -s execve -k user_emulation".

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# auditctl -l | grep user_emulation
-a always,exit -F arch=b64 -S execve -C uid!=euid -F auid!=1 -F key=user_emulation
-a always,exit -F arch=b32 -S execve -C uid!=euid -F auid!=1 -F key=user_emulation

```

Figure 2.200 Result Configuration Rule ID 28598

Berdasarkan Figure 2.200, Result Configuration telah berResult diterapkan pada Service audit.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28598	Ensure actions as another user are always logged.	Directory: /etc/audit/rules.d	Passed

Figure 2.201 Status Rule ID 28598

Based on Figure 2.201, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28598 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28599

Title	Ensure events that modify date and time information are collected
Description	Ensure that all events that change system date and time information are recorded in the audit logs. This is critical to

	detect suspicious activities involving system time manipulation.
Prerequisite	1. auditd package must be installed and running. 2. Root access is required to add audit rules.
Testing Step	1. Run auditctl -l to list current audit rules. 2. Check whether rules with key time-change exist. 3. If not present, create the file /etc/audit/rules.d/50-time-change.rules. 4. Add the following rules: <pre>-a always,exit -F arch=b64 -S adjtimex,setttimeofday,clock_settime -k time-change</pre> <pre>-a always,exit -F arch=b32 -S adjtimex,setttimeofday,clock_settime -k time-change</pre> <pre>-w /etc/localtime -p wa -k time-change</pre> 5. Reload audit rules with augenrules --load.
Test Data	Configuration present in the file /etc/audit/rules.d/50-time-change.rules.
Expectation	Audit rules must exist to monitor system time/date changes through syscalls and file changes, using the key time-change.
Actual Result	Audit rules for monitoring time/date changes have been successfully configured in 50-time-change.rules and are active.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.69 Rule ID 28599

Based on Table 2.69, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28599.

```
GNU nano 6.2 /etc/audit/rules.d/50-time-change.rules
-a always,exit -F arch=b64 -S adjtimex,setttimeofday,clock_settime -k time-change
-a always,exit -F arch=b32 -S adjtimex,setttimeofday,clock_settime -k time-change
-w /etc/localtime -p wa -k time-change
```

Figure 2.202 Configuration Rule ID 28599

Based on Figure 2.202, Configuration is added to the file "/etc/audit/rules.d/50-time-change.rules", with the parameters "-a always,exit -F arch=b64 -S

adjtimex,setttimeofday,clock_settime -k time-change", "-a always,exit -F arch=b32 -S adjtimex,setttimeofday,clock_settime -k time-change" and "-w /etc/localtime -p wa -k time-change".

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# auditctl -l | grep time-change
-a always,exit -F arch=b64 -S adjtimex,setttimeofday,clock_settime -F key=time-change
-a always,exit -F arch=b32 -S stime,setttimeofday,adjtimex,clock_settime -F key=time-change
-w /etc/localtime -p wa -k time-change
```

Figure 2.203 Result Configuration Rule ID 28599

Based on Figure 2.203, after reloading the audit rules with the command “augenrules –load”, verify with the command “auditctl -l”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28599	Ensure events that modify date and time information are collected.	Directory: /etc/audit/rules.d	Passed

Figure 2.204 Status Rule ID 28599

Based on Figure 2.204, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28599 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28600

Title	Ensure events that modify the system's network environment are collected
Description	Ensure that all changes to system network environment settings—such as hostname, domain name, and related configuration files—are logged in the audit logs. This is essential for detecting unauthorized actions that could compromise or disrupt the system's network configuration.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. auditd package must be installed and running. 2. Root access is required to add audit rules.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run auditctl -l to view current audit rules. 2. Verify whether rules with the key system-locale are already present. 3. If not present, create a new rule file /etc/audit/rules.d/50-system_local.rules. 4. Add the following audit rules:

	<pre> -a always,exit -F arch=b64 -S sethostname,setdomainname -k system-locale -a always,exit -F arch=b32 -S sethostname,setdomainname -k system-locale -w /etc/issue -p wa -k system-locale -w /etc/issue.net -p wa -k system-locale -w /etc/hosts -p wa -k system-locale -w /etc/networks -p wa -k system-locale -w /etc/network/ -p wa -k system-locale 5. Reload audit rules using augenrules --load. </pre>
Test Data	Audit rule configuration exists in /etc/audit/rules.d/50-system_local.rules.
Expectation	The audit system is configured to monitor and log changes to hostname, domain name, and network configuration files using the key system-locale.
Actual Result	Audit rules to monitor changes to hostname, domain name, and network configurations have been successfully configured in 50-system_local.rules and are active.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.70 Rule ID 28600

Based on Table 2.70, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28600.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/audit/rules.d/50-system_local.rules
# Memantau perubahan hostname dan domain name
-a always,exit -F arch=b64 -S sethostname,setdomainname -k system-locale
-a always,exit -F arch=b32 -S sethostname,setdomainname -k system-locale

# Memantau perubahan pada file konfigurasi jaringan
-w /etc/issue -p wa -k system-locale
-w /etc/issue.net -p wa -k system-locale
-w /etc/hosts -p wa -k system-locale
-w /etc/networks -p wa -k system-locale
-w /etc/network/ -p wa -k system-locale

```

Figure 2.205 Configuration Rule ID 28600

Based on Figure 2.205, a Configuration has been added to monitor changes in system information such as hostname, domain name and network Configuration in the file “/etc/audit/rules.d/50-system_local.rules”.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# auditctl -l | grep system-locale
-a always,exit -F arch=b64 -S sethostname,setdomainname -F key=system-locale
-a always,exit -F arch=b32 -S sethostname,setdomainname -F key=system-locale
-w /etc/issue -p wa -k system-locale
-w /etc/issue.net -p wa -k system-locale
-w /etc/hosts -p wa -k system-locale
-w /etc/networks -p wa -k system-locale
-w /etc/network -p wa -k system-locale

```

Figure 2.206 Result Configuration Rule ID 28600

Based on Figure 2.206, it is the result of the configuration that has been carried out on the file “/etc/audit/rules.d/50-system_local.rules”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28600	Ensure events that modify the system's network environment are collected.	Directory: /etc/audit/rules.d	Passed

Figure 2.207 Status Rule ID 28600

Based on Figure 2.207, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28600 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28601

Title	Ensure events that modify user/group information are collected
Description	Ensure that all changes to user and group account information—including passwords and historical passwords—are logged in the audit logs. This helps in identifying potential security incidents related to system accounts.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. auditd package must be installed and running. 2. Root access is required to add audit rules.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run auditctl -l to check the currently loaded audit rules. 2. Verify if audit rules with the key identity already exist. 3. If not found, create a rule file at /etc/audit/rules.d/50-identity.rules. 4. Add the following audit rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -w /etc/group -p wa -k identity -w /etc/passwd -p wa -k identity -w /etc/gshadow -p wa -k identity -w /etc/shadow -p wa -k identity

	-w /etc/security/opasswd -p wa -k identity 5. Reload audit rules with augenrules --load.
Test Data	Audit rule configuration exists in /etc/audit/rules.d/50-identity.rules.
Expectation	The audit system is configured to log any changes to user and group account data, including password modifications, using the key identity.
Actual Result	Audit rules for monitoring changes to user and group account information, including password-related files, have been successfully configured in 50-identity.rules and are active.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.71 Rule ID 28601

Based on Table 2.71, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28601.

```
GNU nano 6.2 /etc/audit/rules.d/50-identity.rules
-w /etc/group -p wa -k identity
-w /etc/passwd -p wa -k identity
-w /etc/gshadow -p wa -k identity
-w /etc/shadow -p wa -k identity
-w /etc/security/opasswd -p wa -k identity
```

Figure 2.208 Configuration Rule ID 28601

Based on Figure 2.208, Configuration audit has been performed on the file “etc/audit/rules.d/50-identity.rules” to monitor changes in password information for accounts on the system.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# auditctl -l | grep identity
-w /etc/group -p wa -k identity
-w /etc/passwd -p wa -k identity
-w /etc/gshadow -p wa -k identity
-w /etc/shadow -p wa -k identity
-w /etc/security/opasswd -p wa -k identity
```

Figure 2.209 Result Configuration Rule ID 28601

Based on Figure 2.209, the configuration that has been done in the file “/etc/audit/rules.d/50-identity.rules” is running normally.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28601	Ensure events that modify user/group information are collected.	Directory: /etc/audit/rules.d	● Passed

Figure 2.210 Status Rule ID 28601

Based on Figure 2.210, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28601 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28602

Title	Ensure session initiation information is collected
Description	Ensure that all session initiation events (such as logins, logouts, reboots, shutdowns, and failed login attempts) are logged in the audit log. This is critical for detecting unusual activity such as access during non-working hours, which could indicate a potential intrusion.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. auditd package must be installed and running. 2. Root access is required to add audit rules.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run <code>auditctl -l</code> to view the currently loaded audit rules. 2. Verify whether rules with the key session already exist. 3. If not, create a rule file at <code>/etc/audit/rules.d/50-session.rules</code>. 4. Add the following audit rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -w /var/run/utmp -p wa -k session -w /var/log/wtmp -p wa -k session -w /var/log/btmp -p wa -k session 5. Reload the audit rules using the command <code>augenrules --load</code>.
Test Data	Audit rule configuration exists in <code>/etc/audit/rules.d/50-session.rules</code> .
Expectation	The audit system is configured to monitor and log session-related events, including login, logout, reboot, shutdown, and failed login attempts, using the key session.
Actual Result	Audit rules for monitoring session initiation and termination events have been successfully configured in <code>50-session.rules</code> and are currently active.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.72 Rule ID 28602

Based on Table 2.72, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28602.

```
GNU nano 6.2 /etc/audit/rules.d/50-session.rules
-w /var/run/utmp -p wa -k session
-w /var/log/wtmp -p wa -k session
-w /var/log/btmp -p wa -k session
```

Figure 2.211 Configuration Rule ID 28602

Based on Figure 2.211, Configuration has been done on the file “/etc/audit/rules.d/50-session.rules” to monitor the initiation.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# auditctl -l | grep session
-w /var/run/utmp -p wa -k session
-w /var/log/wtmp -p wa -k session
-w /var/log/btmp -p wa -k session
```

Figure 2.212 Result Configuration

Based on Figure 2.212, the configuration that has been done in the file “/etc/audit/rules.d/50-session.rules” runs normally.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28602	Ensure session initiation information is collected.	Directory: /etc/audit/rules.d	Passed

Figure 2.213 Status Rule ID 28602

Based on Figure 2.213, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28602 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28603

Title	Ensure session initiation information is collected
Description	Ensure that login and logout events are recorded in the audit log to help detect potential brute-force attacks on the system. This data monitors both successful and failed login attempts.
Prerequisite	1. The auditd package is installed and running. 2. Root access is required to configure audit rules.
Testing Step	1. Run the command auditctl -l to check the current audit rules. 2. Verify whether any rules include the logins key.

	<p>3. If no such rules are found, create a new file /etc/audit/rules.d/50-login.rules.</p> <p>4. Add the following lines:</p> <pre>-w /var/log/lastlog -p wa -k logins</pre> <pre>-w /var/run/faillock -p wa -k logins</pre> <p>5. Reload the audit rules using augenrules --load.</p>
Test Data	Audit rule configuration file: /etc/audit/rules.d/50-login.rules
Expectation	The audit system includes rules to monitor successful and failed login attempts using the key logins.
Actual Result	Audit rules for monitoring login success and failure have been successfully configured in 50-login.rules and are currently active.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.73 Rule ID 28603

Based on Table 4.73, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28603.

```
GNU nano 6.2 /etc/audit/rules.d/50-login.rules
-w /var/log/lastlog -p wa -k logins
-w /var/run/faillock -p wa -k logins
```

Figure 2.214 Configuration Rule ID 28603

Based on Figure 2.214, Configuration has been done on the file “/etc/audit/rules.d/50-login.rules”, with the command “-w /var/log/lastlog -p wa -k logins” and “-w /var/run/faillock -p wa -k logins”.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# auditctl -l | grep login
-w /var/log/lastlog -p wa -k logins
-w /var/run/faillock -p wa -k logins
```

Figure 2.215 Result Configuration Rule ID 28603

Based on Figure 2.215, the configuration that has been done in the file “/etc/audit/rules.d/50-login.rules” is running normally.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28603	Ensure login and logout events are collected.	Directory: /etc/audit/rules.d	● Passed

Figure 2.216 Status Rule ID 28603

Based on Figure 2.216, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28603 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28611

Title	Ensure audit tools are owned by root.
Description	Ensure that all audit tools such as auditctl, aureport, ausearch, autrace, auditd, and augenrules are owned by the root user. This is to prevent unauthorized modification or usage of audit log management tools.
Prerequisite	Root access is required to verify and change file ownership.
Testing Step	<p>1. Run the following command to check ownership of audit tools:</p> <pre>stat -c "%n %U" /sbin/auditctl /sbin/aureport /sbin/ausearch /sbin/autrace /sbin/auditd /sbin/augenrules</pre> <p>2. Ensure that each file is owned by the user root.</p> <p>3. If any file is not owned by root, run the following command to correct it:</p> <pre>chown root /sbin/auditctl /sbin/aureport /sbin/ausearch /sbin/autrace /sbin/auditd /sbin/augenrules</pre>
Test Data	Output of stat command showing file ownership in /sbin/
Expectation	All specified audit tool files are owned by the root user.
Actual Result	All audit tool files are confirmed to be owned by the root user.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.74 Rule ID 28611

Based on Table 2.74, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28611.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# chown root /sbin/auditctl /sbin/aureport /sbin/ausearch /sbin/autrace /sbin/auditd /sbin/augenrules
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# █
```

Figure 2.217 Configuration Rule ID 28611

Based on Figure 2.217, Configuration has been done to change the owner of the auditctl, aureport, ausearch, auditd and augenrules files, with the command "chown root /sbin/auditctl /sbin/aureport /sbin/ausearch /sbin/autrace /sbin/auditd /sbin/augenrules".

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Illam-WazuhAgent# stat -c "%n %U" /sbin/auditctl /sbin/aureport /sbin/ausearch /sbin/autrace /sbin/auditd /sbin/augenrules
/sbin/auditctl root
/sbin/aureport root
/sbin/ausearch root
/sbin/autrace root
/sbin/auditd root
/sbin/augenrules root
```

Figure 2.218 Result Configuration Rule ID 28611

Based on Figure 2.218, the owner of these files has changed to root.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28611	Ensure audit tools are owned by root.	Command: stat -c "%n %U" /sbin/auditctl /sbin/aureport /sbin/ausearch /sbin/autrace /sbin/auditd /sbin/augenrules	Passed

Figure 2.219 Status Rule ID 28611

Based on Figure 2.219, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28611 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28613

Title	Ensure cryptographic mechanisms are used to protect the integrity of audit tools
Description	Ensure that audit tools (auditctl, auditd, ausearch, aureport, autrace, augenrules) are protected using cryptographic mechanisms (e.g., SHA-512 hash) to prevent undetected modifications, tampering, or replacement of these tools.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AIDE (Advanced Intrusion Detection Environment) package is installed 2. Root access to edit the AIDE configuration file
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the AIDE configuration file using the command: cat /etc/aide/aide.conf 2. Search for entries referring to audit tools under /sbin/ 3. If not found, add the following lines: /sbin/auditctl p+i+n+u+g+s+b+acl+xattrs+sha512 /sbin/auditd p+i+n+u+g+s+b+acl+xattrs+sha512 /sbin/ausearch p+i+n+u+g+s+b+acl+xattrs+sha512

	<pre> /sbin/aureport p+i+n+u+g+s+b+acl+xattrs+sha512 /sbin/autrace p+i+n+u+g+s+b+acl+xattrs+sha512 /sbin/augenrules p+i+n+u+g+s+b+acl+xattrs+sha512 4. Save the changes to the configuration file </pre>
Test Data	Content of /etc/aide/aide.conf showing audit tool entries with SHA-512 hash protection
Expectation	All audit tools in /sbin/ are listed in aide.conf and configured with SHA-512 hashing for integrity checking
Actual Result	All audit tools in /sbin/ have been added to aide.conf and are protected with SHA-512 cryptographic hash as specified
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2. 75 Rule ID 28613

Based on Table 75, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28613.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/aide/aide.conf *
# the next rotation (being compressed)
LowDELog = SerMemberLog+ANF+ARF

# Compressed log created by logrotate's dateext option: These files appear
# once and are not touched any more.
SerMemberDELog = Full+ANF

# For daemons that log to a variable file name and have the live log
# hardlinked to a static file name
LinkedLog = Log-n

@@x_include_setenv PATH /bin:/usr/bin
@@x_include /etc/aide/aide.conf.d ^[a-zA-Z0-9_-]+$

#Audit Tools
/sbin/auditctl p+i+n+u+g+s+b+acl+xattrs+sha512
/sbin/auditd p+i+n+u+g+s+b+acl+xattrs+sha512
/sbin/ausearch p+i+n+u+g+s+b+acl+xattrs+sha512
/sbin/aureport p+i+n+u+g+s+b+acl+xattrs+sha512
/sbin/autrace p+i+n+u+g+s+b+acl+xattrs+sha512
/sbin/augenrules p+i+n+u+g+s+b+acl+xattrs+sha512

```

Figure 2. 220 Configuration Rule ID 28613

Based on Figure 220, additional configuration has been added to protect files using a cryptographic mechanism.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28613	Ensure cryptographic mechanisms are used to protect the integrity of audit tools.	File: /etc/aide/aide.conf	Passed

Figure 2. 221 Status Rule ID 28613

Based on Figure 221, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28613 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28614

Title	Ensure systemd-journal-remote is installed.
Description	Ensure that the systemd-journal-remote package is installed. This package enables the system to send or receive logs from remote hosts, supporting centralized log management and protecting log integrity from local attacks.
Prerequisite	1. Root access on Ubuntu Server 22.04 2. Server is connected to the internet
Testing Step	1. Run the command: dpkg-query -s systemd-journal-remote 2. Verify whether the package is installed 3. If not installed, run: apt-get install systemd-journal-remote
Test Data	No specific test data required
Expectation	The systemd-journal-remote package is listed with status: install ok installed.
Actual Result	The systemd-journal-remote package has been successfully installed with status: install ok installed.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.76 Rule ID 28614

Based on Table 76, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28614.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# apt install systemd-journal-remote
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
The following additional packages will be installed:
  libmicrohttpd12
The following NEW packages will be installed:
  libmicrohttpd12 systemd-journal-remote
0 upgraded, 2 newly installed, 0 to remove and 40 not upgraded.
Need to get 146 kB of archives.
After this operation, 600 kB of additional disk space will be used.
Do you want to continue? [Y/n] y
Get:1 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy/universe amd64 libmicrohttpd12 amd64 0.9.75-3ubuntu1 [77.6 kB]
Get:2 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy-updates/universe amd64 systemd-journal-remote amd64 249.11-0ubuntu3.12 [68.3 kB]
Fetched 146 kB in 2s (71.4 kB/s)
Selecting previously unselected package libmicrohttpd12:amd64.

```

Figure 2.222 Install Systemd Journal Remote

Based on Figure 2.222, the systemd-journal-remote package is installed with the command “apt-get install systemd-journal-remote”.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Illam-WazuhAgent# dpkg-query -s systemd-journal-remote
Package: systemd-journal-remote
Status: install ok installed
Priority: optional
Section: admin
Installed-Size: 401
Maintainer: Ubuntu Developers <ubuntu-devel-discuss@lists.ubuntu.com>
Architecture: amd64
Multi-Arch: foreign

```

Figure 2.223 Status Install Systemd Journal Remote

Based on Figure 2.223, Systemd Journal Remote has successfully installed, as evidenced by “Status: install ok installed”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28614	Ensure systemd-journal-remote is installed.	Command: dpkg-query -s systemd-journal-remote	Passed

Figure 2.224 Status Rule ID 28614

Based on Figure 2.224, Systemd-journal-remote has been installed, so the final status on Rule ID 28614 is “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28617

Title	Ensure journald is configured to compress large log files.
Description	Ensure that journald is configured to compress large log files by enabling the Compress=yes option. This helps prevent the filesystem from filling up due to accumulation of uncompressed log files.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses systemd-journald 2. Root access to edit configuration files and restart services
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. View the journald configuration file using: <code>cat /etc/systemd/journald.conf</code> 2. Check if the line Compress=yes is present 3. If not present or commented out, add or modify the line: <code>Compress=yes</code> 4. Reload the journald service: <code>systemctl restart systemd-journald</code>
Test Data	Output of /etc/systemd/journald.conf
Expectation	The file /etc/systemd/journald.conf contains the line Compress=yes.

Actual Result	The journald.conf file contains the line Compress=yes, and the service has been reloaded and is running normally.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.77 Rule ID 28617

Based on Table 2.77, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28617.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/systemd/journald.conf *
# This file is part of systemd.
#
# systemd is free software; you can redistribute it and/or modify it under the
# terms of the GNU Lesser General Public License as published by the Free
# Software Foundation; either version 2.1 of the License, or (at your option)
# any later version.
#
# Entries in this file show the compile time defaults. Local configuration
# should be created by either modifying this file, or by creating "drop-ins" in
# the journald.conf.d/ subdirectory. The latter is generally recommended.
# Defaults can be restored by simply deleting this file and all drop-ins.
#
# Use 'systemd-analyze cat-config systemd/journald.conf' to display the full config.
#
# See journald.conf(5) for details.
[Journal]
#Storage=auto
Compress=yes

```

Figure 2.225 Configuration Rule ID 28617

Based on Figure 2.225, Configuration has been added to the journald.conf file with the parameter “Compress=yes”.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl restart systemd-journald
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# systemctl status systemd-journald
● systemd-journald.service - Journal Service
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/systemd-journald.service; static)
   Active: active (running) since Wed 2025-03-12 06:04:18 WIB; 3s ago
 TriggeredBy: ● systemd-journald.socket
               ● systemd-journald-audit.socket
               ● systemd-journald-dev-log.socket
   Docs: man:systemd-journald.service(8)
         man:journald.conf(5)
 Main PID: 2637 (systemd-journal)
  Status: "Processing requests..."
   Tasks: 1 (limit: 4562)
  Memory: 1.1M
     CPU: 67ms
   CGroup: /system.slice/systemd-journald.service
           └─2637 /lib/systemd/systemd-journald

```

Figure 2.226 Restart Systemd-Journald

Based on Figure 2.226, the systemd-journald service is reloaded so that the configuration changes work.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28617	Ensure journald is configured to compress large log files.	File: /etc/systemd/journald.conf	● Passed

Figure 2.227 Status Rule ID 28617

Based on Figure 227, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28617 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28618

Title	Ensure journald is configured to write logfiles to persistent disk.
Description	Ensure journald is configured to store logs persistently on disk by enabling the option Storage=persistent. This allows logs to remain available for forensic analysis even after system reboot.
Prerequisite	1. The system uses systemd-journald 2. Root access to edit configuration files and restart services
Testing Step	1. View the journald configuration file using: cat /etc/systemd/journald.conf 2. Check if the line Storage=persistent is present 3. If not present or commented out, add or modify the line: Storage=persistent 4. Reload the journald service: systemctl restart systemd-journald
Test Data	Output of /etc/systemd/journald.conf
Expectation	The file /etc/systemd/journald.conf contains the line Storage=persistent.
Actual Result	The journald.conf file contains the line Storage=persistent, and the service has been reloaded and is running normally.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.78 Rule ID 28618

Based on Table 2.78, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28618.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/systemd/journald.conf *
#
# systemd is free software; you can redistribute it and/or modify it under the
# terms of the GNU Lesser General Public License as published by the Free
# Software Foundation; either version 2.1 of the License, or (at your option)
# any later version.
#
# Entries in this file show the compile time defaults. Local configuration
# should be created by either modifying this file, or by creating "drop-ins" in
# the journald.conf.d/ subdirectory. The latter is generally recommended.
# Defaults can be restored by simply deleting this file and all drop-ins.
#
# Use 'systemd-analyze cat-config systemd/journald.conf' to display the full config.
# See journald.conf(5) for details.

[Journal]
Storage=Persistent
Compress=yes
#Seal=yes

```

Figure 2.228 Configuration Rule ID 28618

Based on Figure 2.228, add the Configuration to the “journald.conf” file with the “Storage=Persistent” parameter and reload the Journald Service so that the Configuration changes work.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28618	Ensure journald is configured to write logfiles to persistent disk.	File: /etc/systemd/journald.conf	Passed

Figure 2.229 Status Rule ID 28618

Based on Figure 2.229, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28618 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28623

Title	Ensure rsyslog default file permissions are configured
Description	Ensure rsyslog is configured to set the default file permission for newly created log files to mode 0640 or more restrictive, in order to protect sensitive log data from unauthorized access.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. System uses rsyslog 2. Root access to edit configuration files and restart services
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. View the rsyslog configuration file: <code>cat /etc/rsyslog.conf</code> 2. Verify the presence of the line: <code>\$FileCreateMode 0640</code> 3. If missing or incorrect, add or modify the line to: <code>\$FileCreateMode 0640</code>

	4. Reload the rsyslog service: systemctl restart rsyslog
Test Data	Output of /etc/rsyslog.conf file
Expectation	The file /etc/rsyslog.conf contains the line \$FileCreateMode 0640.
Actual Result	The configuration file /etc/rsyslog.conf contains \$FileCreateMode 0640 and the rsyslog service has been reloaded and is running normally.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.79 Rule ID 28623

Based on Table 2.79, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28623.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/rsyslog.conf
#module(load="imjournal")
#*. * @127.0.0.1:514

# Add module Journald
#module(load="imjournal" PersistStateInterval="100" StateFile="imjournal.state")

# Add Port Syslog
#module(load="imudp")
#input(type="imudp" port="514")

#module(load="imtcp")
#input(type="imtcp" port="514")

#####
### GLOBAL DIRECTIVES ###
#####

#
# Use traditional timestamp format.
# To enable high precision timestamps, comment out the following line.
#
$ActionFileDefaultTemplate RSYSLOG_TraditionalFileFormat

# Filter duplicated messages
$RepeatedMsgReduction on

#
# Set the default permissions for all log files.
#
$FileOwner syslog
$FileGroup adm
$FileCreateMode 0640
$DirCreateMode 0755
$Umask 0022
$PrivDropToUser syslog
$PrivDropToGroup syslog

```

Figure 2.230 Configuration Rule ID 28623

Based on Figure 2.230, Configuration has been added to the /etc/rsyslog.conf file with the parameter “\$FileCreateMode 0640”, then the Configuration is saved and the rsyslog Service is reloaded.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28623	Ensure rsyslog default file permissions are configured.	File: /etc/rsyslog.conf	● Passed

Figure 2. 231. Status Rule ID 28623

Based on Figure 2.231, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28623 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28624

Title	Ensure rsyslog is not configured to receive logs from a remote client
Description	Ensure rsyslog is not configured to receive logs from remote clients. If enabled, the system acts as a log server, violating its role as a client.
Prerequisite	1. System uses rsyslog 2. Root access to edit configuration files and restart services
Testing Step	1. Open the rsyslog configuration file: <code>cat /etc/rsyslog.conf</code> 2. Verify that the following lines are not present: - <code>\$ModLoad imtcp</code> - <code>\$InputTCPServerRun</code> - <code>module(load="imtcp")</code> - <code>input(type="imtcp" port="514")</code> 3. If any of these lines exist, comment them out by adding # at the beginning or remove them. 4. Reload rsyslog service: <code>systemctl restart rsyslog</code>
Test Data	Output of /etc/rsyslog.conf file
Expectation	The file /etc/rsyslog.conf does not contain any active lines enabling TCP input modules or TCP server functionality such as <code>\$ModLoad imtcp</code> , <code>\$InputTCPServerRun</code> , or equivalent directives.
Actual Result	The configuration in /etc/rsyslog.conf has these lines commented out with # and the rsyslog service has been reloaded and is running normally.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.80 Rule ID 28624

Based on Table 2.80, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28624.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/rsyslog.conf
# /etc/rsyslog.conf configuration file for rsyslog
#
# For more information install rsyslog-doc and see
# /usr/share/doc/rsyslog-doc/html/configuration/index.html
#
# Default logging rules can be found in /etc/rsyslog.d/50-default.conf

#####
###  MODULES  ###
#####

module(load="imuxsock") # provides support for local system logging
#module(load="immark") # provides --MARK-- message capability

# provides UDP syslog reception
#module(load="imudp")
#input(type="imudp" port="514")

# provides TCP syslog reception
#module(load="imtcp")
#input(type="imtcp" port="514")

```

Figure 2.232 Configuration Rule ID 28624

Based on Figure 2.232, changes have been made to the Rsyslog.conf Configuration, disabling the “Provides UDP syslog reception” and “Provides TCP syslog reception” sections.

ID ^	Title	Target	Result
28624	Ensure rsyslog is not configured to receive logs from a remote client.	File: /etc/rsyslog.conf	Passed

Figure 2.233 Status Rule ID 28624

Based on Figure 2.233, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28624 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28626

Title	Ensure permissions on /etc/crontab are configured.
Description	Ensure the file /etc/crontab is accessible only by the root user, both in ownership and permission. This prevents unauthorized privilege escalation and protects system schedule confidentiality.
Prerequisite	1. The system uses the crontab service 2. Root access to modify file ownership and permissions
Testing Step	1. Run the command:

	<pre>stat /etc/crontab</pre> <p>Verify that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access permissions are 0600 (-rw-----) - Owner (Uid) is 0/root - Group (Gid) is 0/root <p>2. If the permissions or ownership do not match, run:</p> <pre>chown root:root /etc/crontab</pre> <pre>chmod 600 /etc/crontab</pre> <p>3. Re-verify with:</p> <pre>stat /etc/crontab</pre>
Test Data	Output of the command <code>stat /etc/crontab</code> showing permission and ownership status
Expectation	Ownership of <code>/etc/crontab</code> is <code>root:root</code> and the file permissions are set to <code>0600</code> (read/write only for root)
Actual Result	Ownership and permissions of <code>/etc/crontab</code> have been successfully set to <code>root:root</code> and <code>0600</code> respectively
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2. 81. Rule ID 28626

Based on Table 81, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28626.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# chown root:root /etc/crontab
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# chmod og-rwx /etc/crontab
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# stat /etc/crontab
  File: /etc/crontab
  Size: 1136          Blocks: 8           IO Block: 4096   regular file
Device: 802h/2050d  Inode: 393893      Links: 1
Access: (0600/-rw-----)  Uid: (  0/   root)  Gid: (  0/   root)
Access: 2025-03-13 21:41:31.268000000 +0700
Modify: 2022-03-23 20:49:13.000000000 +0700
Change: 2025-03-13 23:48:39.827980000 +0700
 Birth: 2025-03-10 22:20:08.191853083 +0700
```

Figure 2.234 Configuration Rule ID 28626

Based on Figure 2.234, Configuration has been carried out to change the owner and permissions on the `/etc/crontab` file with the commands “`chown root:root`” and “`chmod og-rwx`”..

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28626	Ensure permissions on /etc/crontab are configured.	Command: stat /etc/crontab	Passed

Figure 2.235 Status Rule ID 28626

Based on Figure 2.235, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28626 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28627

Title	Ensure permissions on /etc/cron.hourly are configured.
Description	Ensure the directory /etc/cron.hourly is owned by root and accessible only by root. This is important to prevent regular users from adding, reading, or modifying scripts executed automatically every hour.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the crontab service 2. Root access to modify ownership and permissions
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the command: <code>stat /etc/cron.hourly</code> Verify that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access permissions are 0700 (drwx-----) - Owner (Uid) is 0/root - Group (Gid) is 0/root 2. If the ownership or permissions are incorrect, run: <code>chown root:root /etc/cron.hourly</code> <code>chmod 700 /etc/cron.hourly</code> 3. Re-verify with: <code>stat /etc/cron.hourly</code>
Test Data	Output of <code>stat /etc/cron.hourly</code> showing permission and ownership
Expectation	Ownership of /etc/cron.hourly is root:root and permissions are set to 0700 (full access only for root)
Actual Result	Ownership and permissions of /etc/cron.hourly have been correctly set to root:root and 0700 respectively
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.82 Rule ID 28627

Based on Table 2.82, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28627.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# chown root:root /etc/cron.hourly/
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# chmod og-rwx /etc/cron.hourly/
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# stat /etc/cron.hourly/
  File: /etc/cron.hourly/
  Size: 4096          Blocks: 8           IO Block: 4096   directory
Device: 802h/2050d  Inode: 393241      Links: 2
Access: (0700/drwx-----)  Uid: (  0/   root)  Gid: (  0/   root)
Access: 2025-03-13 21:42:09.952000000 +0700
Modify: 2024-09-11 21:24:07.000000000 +0700
Change: 2025-03-13 23:55:30.591980000 +0700
 Birth: 2025-03-10 22:20:08.123839214 +0700
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# █

```

Figure 2.236 Configuration Rule ID 28627

Based on Figure 2.236, Configuration has been carried out to change the owner and permissions on the /etc/cron.hourly file with the commands “chown root:root” and “chmod og-rwx”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28627	Ensure permissions on /etc/cron.hourly are configured.	Command: stat /etc/cron.hourly/	Passed

Figure 2.237 Status Rule ID 28627

Based on Figure 2.237, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28627 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28628

Title	Ensure permissions on /etc/cron.daily are configured
Description	Ensure the /etc/cron.daily directory is owned by root and only accessible by root. This is to prevent regular users from viewing or modifying scripts that are executed automatically every day.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the crontab service 2. Root access to modify ownership and permissions
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the command: stat /etc/cron.daily Verify that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Permissions are 0700 (drwx-----) - Owner (Uid) is 0/root - Group (Gid) is 0/root 2. If not compliant, run the following commands to correct: chown root:root /etc/cron.daily

	<pre>chmod 700 /etc/cron.daily</pre> <p>3. Re-verify by running:</p> <pre>stat /etc/cron.daily</pre>
Test Data	Output from <code>stat /etc/cron.daily</code> showing ownership and permission status
Expectation	The <code>/etc/cron.daily</code> directory is owned by <code>root:root</code> and permissions are set to <code>0700</code> so that only root can access it
Actual Result	The ownership and permissions of <code>/etc/cron.daily</code> are correctly set to <code>root:root</code> and <code>0700</code>
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.83 Rule ID 28628

Based on Table 2.83, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28628.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# chown root:root /etc/cron.daily/
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# chmod og-rwx /etc/cron.daily/
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# stat /etc/cron.daily/
  File: /etc/cron.daily/
  Size: 4096          Blocks: 8           IO Block: 4096   directory
Device: 802h/2050d  Inode: 393240      Links: 2
Access: (0700/drwx-----)  Uid: (  0/   root)   Gid: (  0/   root)
Access: 2025-04-25 19:38:08.540000000 +0700
Modify: 2025-04-12 00:07:02.260378008 +0700
Change: 2025-04-27 00:04:41.008599866 +0700
 Birth: 2025-03-10 22:20:08.123839214 +0700
```

Figure 2.238 Configuration Rule ID 28628

Based on Figure 2.238, Configuration has been done to change the owner and permissions on the `/etc/cron.daily` file with the commands “`chown root:root`” and “`chmod og-rwx`”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28628	Ensure permissions on /etc/cron.daily are configured.	Command: stat /etc/cron.daily/	● Passed

Figure 2.239. Status Rule ID 28628

Based on Figure 2.239, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28628 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28629

Title	Ensure permissions on <code>/etc/cron.weekly</code> are configured
-------	--

Description	Ensure the /etc/cron.weekly directory is owned by root and accessible only by root. This is to prevent regular users from accessing or modifying the weekly cron scripts which could compromise the system.
Prerequisite	1. The system uses the crontab service 2. Root access to edit configuration files
Testing Step	1. Run the command: <code>stat /etc/cron.weekly</code> Verify that: - Permissions are 0700 (drwx-----) - Owner (Uid) is 0/root - Group (Gid) is 0/root 2. If not compliant, run the following commands to correct: <code>chown root:root /etc/cron.weekly</code> <code>chmod 700 /etc/cron.weekly</code> 3. Re-verify after changes by running: <code>stat /etc/cron.weekly</code>
Test Data	Output of the ownership and permission status of /etc/cron.weekly
Expectation	The /etc/cron.weekly directory is owned by root and permissions are set to 0700 to restrict access to root only
Actual Result	Ownership and permissions of /etc/cron.weekly have been set correctly to root and 0700
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.84 Rule ID 28629

Based on Table 2.84, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28629.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# chown root:root /etc/cron.weekly/
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# chmod og-rwx /etc/cron.weekly/
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# stat /etc/cron.weekly/
  File: /etc/cron.weekly/
  Size: 4096          Blocks: 8           IO Block: 4096   directory
Device: 802h/2050d  Inode: 393243      Links: 2
Access: (0700/drwx-----)  Uid: (  0/   root)  Gid: (  0/   root)
Access: 2025-03-13 21:42:12.048000000 +0700
Modify: 2024-09-11 21:24:08.000000000 +0700
Change: 2025-03-14 00:39:18.927980000 +0700
 Birth: 2025-03-10 22:20:08.123839214 +0700

```

Figure 2.240 Configuration Rule ID 28629

Based on Figure 2.240, Configuration has been done to change the owner and permissions on the /etc/cron.weekly file with the commands “chown root:root” and “chmod og-rwx”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28629	Ensure permissions on /etc/cron.weekly are configured.	Command: stat /etc/cron.weekly/	● Passed

Figure 2.241 Status Rule ID 28629

Based on Figure 2.241, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28629 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28630

Title	Ensure permissions on /etc/cron.monthly are configured.
Description	Ensure the /etc/cron.monthly directory is owned by root and accessible only by root. This is to prevent regular users from accessing or modifying the monthly cron scripts which could threaten system security or operation.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the crontab service 2. Root access to edit configuration files
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the command: stat /etc/cron.monthly Verify that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Permissions are 0700 (drwx-----) - Owner (Uid) is 0/root - Group (Gid) is 0/root 2. If not compliant, run the following commands: chown root:root /etc/cron.monthly chmod 700 /etc/cron.monthly 3. Re-verify by running: stat /etc/cron.monthly
Test Data	Output showing ownership and permission status of /etc/cron.monthly

Expectation	The /etc/cron.monthly directory is owned by root and has permission 0700 restricting access to root only
Actual Result	Ownership and permissions of /etc/cron.monthly have been correctly set to root and 0700
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.85 Rule ID 28630

Based on Table 2.85, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28630.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# chown root:root /etc/cron.monthly/
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# chmod og-rwx /etc/cron.monthly/
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# stat /etc/cron.monthly/
  File: /etc/cron.monthly/
  Size: 4096          Blocks: 8          IO Block: 4096   directory
Device: 802h/2050d  Inode: 393242     Links: 2
Access: (0700/drwx-----) Uid: (    0/   root) Gid: (    0/   root)
Access: 2025-03-13 21:42:09.732000000 +0700
Modify: 2024-09-11 21:24:07.000000000 +0700
Change: 2025-03-14 00:53:34.047980000 +0700
 Birth: 2025-03-10 22:20:08.123839214 +0700

```

Figure 2.242 Configuration Rule ID 28630

Based on Figure 2.242, Configuration has been carried out to change the owner and permissions on the /etc/cron.monthly file with the commands “chown root:root” and “chmod og-rwx”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28630	Ensure permissions on /etc/cron.monthly are configured.	Command: stat /etc/cron.monthly/	Passed

Figure 2.243 Status Rule ID 28630

Based on Figure 2.243, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28630 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28631

Title	Ensure permissions on /etc/cron.d are configured.
Description	Ensure the /etc/cron.d directory is owned by root and accessible only by root. This directory contains system cron scripts that need to run under more granular control. Maintaining strict access permissions on this directory is crucial to prevent unauthorized access.
Prerequisite	1. The system uses the crontab service

	2. Root access to edit configuration files
Testing Step	<p>1. Run the command: stat /etc/cron.d/</p> <p>Verify that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Permissions are 0700 (drwx-----) - Owner (Uid) is 0/root - Group (Gid) is 0/root <p>2. If not compliant, run: chown root:root /etc/cron.d/ chmod 700 /etc/cron.d/</p> <p>3. Re-verify by running: stat /etc/cron.d/</p>
Test Data	Output showing ownership and permission status of /etc/cron.d/
Expectation	The /etc/cron.d/ directory is owned by root and has permission 0700 restricting access to root only
Actual Result	Ownership and permissions of /etc/cron.d/ have been correctly set to root and 0700
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.86 Rule ID 28631

Based on Table 2.86, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28631.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# chown root:root /etc/cron.d/
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# chmod og-rwx /etc/cron.d/
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/audit/rules.d# stat /etc/cron.d/
  File: /etc/cron.d/
  Size: 4096          Blocks: 8          IO Block: 4096   directory
Device: 802h/2050d  Inode: 393239     Links: 2
Access: (0700/drwx-----)  Uid: (  0/   root)   Gid: (  0/   root)
Access: 2025-03-13 21:41:31.272000000 +0700
Modify: 2024-09-11 21:24:07.000000000 +0700
Change: 2025-03-14 01:01:45.795980000 +0700
 Birth: 2025-03-10 22:20:08.123839214 +0700

```

Figure 2.244 Configuration Rule ID 28631

Based on Figure 244, Configuration has been carried out to change the owner and permissions on the /etc/cron.d file with the commands “chown root:root” and “chmod og-rwx”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28631	Ensure permissions on /etc/cron.d are configured.	Command: stat /etc/cron.d/	● Passed

Figure 2.245 Status Rule ID 28631

Based on Figure 245, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28631 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28632

Title	Ensure cron is restricted to authorized users.
Description	Configure cron.allow to restrict cron usage access only to authorized users. This makes it easier to manage the list of users allowed to use cron compared to using a deny list (cron.deny).
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the crontab service. 2. Root access to edit configuration files
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check the permission status and ownership of /etc/cron.allow using the command "stat /etc/cron.allow". 2. If the ownership and permissions are not Root and -rw-r-----, 3. Run the commands "chown root:root /etc/cron.allow" and "chmod 0640 /etc/cron.allow". 4. Ensure the /etc/cron.deny file does not exist.
Test Data	/etc/cron.allow file must exist. /etc/cron.deny file must not exist.
Expectation	Ownership of the /etc/cron.allow file is Root, the permission set on /etc/cron.allow is 0640, and ensure the cron.deny file does not exist.
Actual Result	The permission and ownership of /etc/cron.allow have been set to root and 0640. The cron.deny file does not exist.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.87 Rule ID 28632

Based on Table 2.87, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28632.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc# touch /etc/cron.allow
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc# chmod g-wx,o-rwx /etc/cron.allow
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc# chown root:root /etc/cron.allow
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc# stat /etc/cron.allow
  File: /etc/cron.allow
  Size: 0          Blocks: 0          IO Block: 4096   regular empty file
Device: 802h/2050d Inode: 432874     Links: 1
Access: (0640/-rw-r-----)  Uid: (  0/   root)   Gid: (  0/   root)
Access: 2025-03-14 01:06:57.371980000 +0700
Modify: 2025-03-14 01:06:57.371980000 +0700
Change: 2025-03-14 01:07:06.351980000 +0700
 Birth: 2025-03-14 01:06:05.391980000 +0700
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc#

```

Figure 2.246 Configuration Rule ID 28632

Based on Figure 2.246, Configuration has been carried out to change the owner and permissions on the /etc/cron.allow file with the commands “chown root:root” and “chmod g-wx,o-rwx”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28632	Ensure cron is restricted to authorized users.	File: /etc/cron.deny	Passed

Figure 2.247 Configuration Rule ID 28632

Based on Figure 2.247, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28632 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28633

Title	Ensure at is restricted to authorized users.
Description	Configure the system so that only authorized users can use the at command to schedule specific tasks by using the /etc/at.allow file.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the at service 2. Root access to edit configuration files
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check the ownership and permission status of /etc/at.allow by running: stat /etc/at.allow 2.If the ownership is not root and permissions are not -rw-r----- (0640), run the following commands: chown root:root /etc/at.allow chmod 0640 /etc/at.allow 3. Ensure that the file /etc/at.deny does not exist.

Test Data	File /etc/at.allow must exist File /etc/at.deny must not exist
Expectation	Ownership of /etc/at.allow is set to root, permissions are 0640, and the file /etc/at.deny is absent.
Actual Result	Ownership and permissions of /etc/at.allow are correctly set to root and 0640. The file /etc/at.deny does not exist.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.88 Rule ID 28633

Based on Table 2.88, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28633.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc# touch /etc/at.allow
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc# chmod g-wx,o-rwx /etc/at.allow
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc# chown root:root /etc/at.allow
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc# stat /etc/at.allow
  File: /etc/at.allow
  Size: 0          Blocks: 0          IO Block: 4096   regular empty file
Device: 802h/2050d Inode: 432894     Links: 1
Access: (0640/-rw-r-----)  Uid: (  0/   root)   Gid: (  0/   root)
Access: 2025-03-14 01:10:49.547980000 +0700
Modify: 2025-03-14 01:10:49.547980000 +0700
Change: 2025-03-14 01:10:59.935980000 +0700
Birth:  2025-03-14 01:10:36.455980000 +0700

```

Figure 2.248 Configuration Rule ID 28633

Based on Figure 2.248, Configuration has been carried out to create a folder in “/etc/at.allow” and change the owner and permissions on the /etc/at.allow file with the commands “chown root:root” and “chmod g-wx,o-rwx”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28633	Ensure at is restricted to authorized users.	File: /etc/at.deny	Passed

Figure 2.249 Status Rule ID 28633

Based on Figure 2.249, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28633 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28634

Title	Ensure at is restricted to authorized users.
Description	The /etc/ssh/sshd_config file contains configuration settings for the SSH daemon (sshd). To protect it from unauthorized

	changes by non-privileged users, it must be configured so that only the root user can access and modify it. The file must be owned by root and should be readable and writable only by root.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the SSH (Secure Shell) service. 2. Root access is required to modify the configuration file.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check the ownership and permissions of the sshd_config file using the command: <code>stat /etc/ssh/sshd_config</code> 2. Verify that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Permissions are 0600 (-rw-----) - Owner (UID) is root - Group (GID) is root 3. If not compliant, run the following commands: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <code>chown root:root /etc/ssh/sshd_config</code> - <code>chmod 0600 /etc/ssh/sshd_config</code>
Test Data	File /etc/ssh/sshd_config
Expectation	The /etc/ssh/sshd_config file is owned by root and has permissions set to 0600, allowing only root to read and write the file.
Actual Result	The ownership and permissions of /etc/ssh/sshd_config have been correctly set to root and 0600.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.89 Rule ID 28634

Based on Table 2.89, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28634.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# chown root:root /etc/ssh/sshd_config
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# chmod og-rwx /etc/ssh/sshd_config
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# stat /etc/ssh/sshd_config
  File: /etc/ssh/sshd_config
  Size: 3263          Blocks: 8          IO Block: 4096   regular file
Device: 802h/2050d  Inode: 432152     Links: 1
Access: (0600/-rw-----)  Uid: (  0/   root)  Gid: (  0/   root)
Access: 2025-03-14 21:43:20.052044414 +0700
Modify: 2025-03-11 02:22:40.804985214 +0700
Change: 2025-03-14 23:53:31.424000000 +0700
 Birth: 2025-03-10 22:33:04.892301408 +0700

```

Figure 2.250 Configuration Rule ID 28634

Based on Figure 2.250, Configuration has been carried out to change the owner and permissions on the `/etc/ssh/sshd_config` file with the commands “`chown root:root`” and “`chmod og-rwx`”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28634	Ensure permissions on <code>/etc/ssh/sshd_config</code> are configured.	Command: <code>stat /etc/ssh/sshd_config</code>	● Passed

Figure 2.251 Status Rule ID 28634

Based on Figure 2.251, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28634 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28635

Title	Ensure SSH access is limited.
Description	To ensure that only authorized users can access the system via SSH, it is necessary to restrict users and groups allowed to connect using SSH. This can be achieved by configuring the <code>/etc/ssh/sshd_config</code> file with parameters such as <code>AllowUsers</code> , <code>AllowGroups</code> , <code>DenyUsers</code> , or <code>DenyGroups</code> .
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the SSH (Secure Shell) service 2. Root access to edit configuration files
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run Command <code>"sshd -T grep -E 'allowusers denyusers allowgroups denygroups'"</code>. 2. If it doesn't exist, create a new file to give certain users permission to SSH, with the command <code>"touch listuser.conf"</code> 3. Edit the <code>listuser.conf</code> file and add the line <code>"Allowusers <user>"</code> 4. Restart Service SSHD
Test Data	File <code>/etc/ssh/sshd_config</code>
Expectation	The <code>/etc/ssh/sshd_config</code> file (directly or via included files) contains one or more of the following parameters: <code>AllowUsers</code> , <code>AllowGroups</code> , <code>DenyUsers</code> , or <code>DenyGroups</code> .
Actual Result	The <code>/etc/ssh/sshd_config</code> file contains one or more of the expected parameters, and the SSHD service is running normally.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.90 Rule ID 28635

Based on Table 2.90, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28635.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/ssh/sshd_config.d# touch listuser.conf
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/ssh/sshd_config.d# nano listuser.conf
```

Figure 2.252 Create File List User

Based on Figure 2.252, a command is run to create a new file named “listuser.conf” which will be used to create the “AllowUsers”, “AllowGroups” or “DenyUsers” parameters.

```
GNU nano 6.2 listuser.conf
Allowusers Ilham-WazuhAgent
```

Figure 2.253 Allow Users

Based on Figure 2.253, adding the “Allowusers Ilham-WazuhAgent” parameter to the listuser.conf file, the purpose is to list users who are only allowed to perform SSH, namely Ilham-WazuhAgent.

```
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/ssh/sshd_config.d# sshd -T | grep -E "allowusers|denyusers|allowgroups|denygroups"
allowusers Ilham-WazuhAgent
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/ssh/sshd_config.d# systemctl restart sshd
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/ssh/sshd_config.d# systemctl status sshd
● ssh.service - OpenBSD Secure Shell server
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/ssh.service; enabled; vendor preset: enabled)
   Active: active (running) since Sat 2025-03-15 00:35:24 WIB; 10s ago
     Docs: man:sshd(8)
           man:sshd_config(5)
   Process: 9454 ExecStartPre=/usr/sbin/sshd -t (code=exited, status=0/SUCCESS)
  Main PID: 9456 (sshd)
    Tasks: 1 (limit: 4562)
   Memory: 1.7M
      CPU: 70ms
   CGroup: /system.slice/ssh.service
           └─9456 "sshd: /usr/sbin/sshd -D [listener] 0 of 10-100 startups"
```

Figure 2.254 Restart Service SSH

Based on Figure 2.254, so that the Configuration changes that have been made can be applied, a reload is carried out on the sshd Service.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28635	Ensure SSH access is limited.	File: /etc/ssh/sshd_config	Passed

Figure 2.255 Status Rule ID 28535

Based on Figure 2.255, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28635 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28538

Title	Ensure SSH root login is disabled
Description	The PermitRootLogin parameter specifies whether the root user is allowed to log in via SSH. The default value is prohibit-password, meaning root login is permitted using methods other than password (e.g., SSH keys). To enhance security, it is recommended to disable root login over SSH by setting this parameter to no, requiring system administrators to log in with their own accounts and escalate privileges when needed.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the SSH (Secure Shell) service. 2. Root access to modify configuration files.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the SSH configuration file: nano /etc/ssh/sshd_config 2. Search for the PermitRootLogin directive. 3. If it is not set to no, change or add the line: PermitRootLogin no 4. Save and close the file. 5. Restart the SSHD service: systemctl restart sshd
Test Data	File /etc/ssh/sshd_config
Expectation	The PermitRootLogin directive is set to no in the SSH configuration to prevent direct root login.
Actual Result	The SSH configuration has PermitRootLogin no set, and the SSHD service is running properly.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.91 Rule ID 28538

Based on Table 2.91, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28638.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/ssh/sshd_config
# This is the sshd server system-wide configuration file. See
# sshd_config(5) for more information.
# This sshd was compiled with PATH=/usr/local/sbin:/usr/local/bin:/usr/sbin:/usr/bin:/sbin:/bin:/usr/games
# The strategy used for options in the default sshd_config shipped with
# OpenSSH is to specify options with their default value where
# possible, but leave them commented. Uncommented options override the
# default value.
Include /etc/ssh/sshd_config.d/*.conf
#Port 22
#AddressFamily any
#ListenAddress 0.0.0.0
#ListenAddress ::
#HostKey /etc/ssh/ssh_host_rsa_key
#HostKey /etc/ssh/ssh_host_ecdsa_key
#HostKey /etc/ssh/ssh_host_ed25519_key
# Ciphers and keying
#RekeyLimit default none
# Logging
#SyslogFacility AUTH
#LogLevel INFO
# Authentication:
#LoginGraceTime 2m
PermitRootLogin no
#StrictModes yes
#MaxAuthTries 6
#MaxSessions 10

```

Figure 2.256 Configuration Rule ID 28538

Based on Figure 2.256, the parameter “PermitRootLogin no” was added to the /etc/ssh/sshd_config file.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28638	Ensure SSH root login is disabled.	Command: sshd -T	Passed

Figure 2.257 Status Rule ID 28638

Based on Figure 2.257, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28638 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28645

Title	Ensure only strong MAC algorithms are used.
Description	The use of weak MAC (Message Authentication Code) algorithms, such as hmac-md5 and hmac-md5-96, increases the risk of exploitation through SSH downgrade attacks. These weak algorithms are vulnerable as computing power improves, making them easier to break. An attacker could potentially launch a Man-in-the-Middle (MiTM) attack, decrypt the SSH channel, and capture credentials or sensitive information.
Prerequisite	1. The system uses the SSH (Secure Shell) service.

	2. Root access to modify configuration files.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check the SSH configuration to verify the use of the MAC algorithm used, by running the following command "sshd -T grep MACs". 2. Make sure the output does not contain the use of the "hmac-md5" and "hmac-md5-96" algorithms. 3. If there are such algorithms, then update the configuration file in /etc/ssh/sshd_config by adding or modifying strong MACs parameters. 4. Restart the SSHD service
Test Data	/etc/ssh/sshd_config file
Expectation	Only strong and approved MAC algorithms are used in the SSH configuration. Weak algorithms such as hmac-md5 and hmac-md5-96 must not be present.
Actual Result	The SSH configuration no longer uses weak MAC algorithms such as hmac-md5 and hmac-md5-96.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.92 Rule ID 28645

Based on Table 2.92, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28645.

```

GNU nano 6.2 sshd_config
#AuthorizedPrincipalsFile none
#AuthorizedKeysCommand none
#AuthorizedKeysCommandUser nobody
# Configuration Strong MACs
MACs hmac-sha2-512-etm@openssh.com,hmac-sha2-256-etm@openssh.com,hmac-sha2-512,hmac-sha2-256
# For this to work you will also need host keys in /etc/ssh/ssh_known_hosts
#HostbasedAuthentication no
# Change to yes if you don't trust ~/.ssh/known_hosts for

```

Figure 2.258 Configuration Rule ID 28645

Based on Figure 2.258, changes were made to the Configuration in the sshd_config file, to ensure that there was no use of MAC “hmac-md5” and “hmac-md5-96”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28645	Ensure only strong MAC algorithms are used.	Command: sshd -T	● Passed

Figure 2.259 Status Rule ID 28645

Based on Figure 2.259, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28645 policy, namely there is no use of MAC “hmac-md5” and “hmac-md5-96”, so the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28647

Title	Ensure SSH AllowTcpForwarding is disabled.
Description	SSH port forwarding allows port redirection between client and server. If this feature is left enabled, it can pose security risks because communications conducted through SSH cannot be monitored by network monitoring systems. This can be exploited by malicious parties, such as cybercriminals or malware, to hide unauthorized communications or to exfiltrate stolen data from the network.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the SSH (Secure Shell) service 2. Root access to edit the configuration file
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check the SSH configuration to verify the TCP forwarding setting on SSH by using the command <code>sshd -T grep allowtcpforwarding</code>. 2. If the AllowTcpForwarding parameter is set to "yes" or is missing, add or modify the line to read AllowTcpForwarding no. 3. Reload the SSHD service.
Test Data	File /etc/ssh/sshd_config
Expectation	SSH port forwarding (AllowTcpForwarding) must be properly disabled, indicated by the AllowTcpForwarding parameter set to "no".
Actual Result	SSH Port Forwarding has been set to "No" and the SSH service is running normally.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.93 Rule ID 28647

Based on Table 2.93, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28647

```

GNU nano 6.2 sshd_config *
# Set this to 'yes' to enable PAM authentication, account processing,
# and session processing. If this is enabled, PAM authentication will
# be allowed through the KbdInteractiveAuthentication and
# PasswordAuthentication. Depending on your PAM configuration,
# PAM authentication via KbdInteractiveAuthentication may bypass
# the setting of "PermitRootLogin without-password".
# If you just want the PAM account and session checks to run without
# PAM authentication, then enable this but set PasswordAuthentication
# and KbdInteractiveAuthentication to 'no'.
UsePAM yes

#AllowAgentForwarding yes
AllowTcpForwarding no
#GatewayPorts no
X11Forwarding no

```

Figure 2.260 Configuration Rule ID 28647

Based on Figure 2.260, Configuration has been done on the sshd_config file for the “AllowTcpForwarding no” parameter.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/ssh# systemctl restart sshd
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/ssh# sshd -T | grep -i "allowtcp"
allowtcpforwarding no
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/ssh# systemctl status sshd
● ssh.service - OpenBSD Secure Shell server
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/ssh.service; enabled; vendor preset: enabled)
   Active: active (running) since Sat 2025-03-15 01:42:37 WIB; 20s ago
     Docs: man:sshd(8)
           man:sshd_config(5)
   Process: 16217 ExecStartPre=/usr/sbin/sshd -t (code=exited, status=0/SUCCESS)
   Main PID: 16219 (sshd)
     Tasks: 1 (limit: 4562)
    Memory: 1.7M
       CPU: 71ms
   CGroup: /system.slice/ssh.service
           └─16219 "sshd: /usr/sbin/sshd -D [listener] 0 of 10-100 startups"

Mar 15 01:42:37 WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer systemd[1]: Starting OpenBSD Secure Shell server...
Mar 15 01:42:37 WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer sshd[16219]: Server listening on 0.0.0.0 port 22.
Mar 15 01:42:37 WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer sshd[16219]: Server listening on :: port 22.
Mar 15 01:42:37 WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer systemd[1]: Started OpenBSD Secure Shell server.
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/etc/ssh#

```

Figure 2.261 Restart SSHD

Based on Figure 2.261, after making changes to the Configuration on sshd_config, restart the sshd Service so that the Configuration changes made can be applied.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28647	Ensure SSH AllowTcpForwarding is disabled.	Command: sshd -T	Passed

Figure 2.262 Status Rule ID 28647

Based on Figure 2.262, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28647 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28649

Title	Ensure SSH MaxAuthTries is set to 4 or less
-------	---

Description	The MaxAuthTries parameter specifies the maximum number of authentication attempts allowed per SSH connection. Setting a low number of authentication attempts helps minimize the risk of brute-force attacks on the SSH server. The recommended value is 4, but it can be adjusted according to site-specific security policies.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the SSH (Secure Shell) service 2. Root access is available to edit the configuration file
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the SSH configuration file using the command: nano /etc/ssh/sshd_config. 2. Locate or add the line MaxAuthTries 3, then save the changes and exit the editor. 3. Reload the SSH service to apply the changes using the command: systemctl restart sshd. 4. Verify the changes with the command: sshd -T grep maxauthtries. 5. Ensure the output shows that the MaxAuthTries value is 4 or fewer.
Test Data	File /etc/ssh/sshd_config
Expectation	The system should allow a maximum of 4 authentication attempts or fewer. If it allows more than that, it does not comply with the policy.
Actual Result	The MaxAuthTries parameter has been configured to allow a maximum of 3 attempts. The SSHD service has been reloaded and is running normally.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.94 Rule ID 28649

Based on Table 2.94, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28649.

```

GNU nano 6.2 sshd_config *
#LogLevel INFO

# Authentication:

#LoginGraceTime 2m
PermitRootLogin no
#StrictModes yes
MaxAuthTries 3
#MaxSessions 10

```

Figure 2.263. Configuration Rule ID 28649

Based on Figure 2.263, Configuration changes have been made to the “sshd_config” file with the “MaxAuthTries 3” parameter and the sshd Service has been reloaded so that the changes can be applied.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28649	Ensure SSH MaxAuthTries is set to 4 or less.	Command: sshd -T	Passed

Figure 2.264 Status Rule ID 28649

Based on Figure 2.264, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28649 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28650

Title	Ensure SSH MaxStartups is configured.
Description	The MaxStartups parameter defines the maximum number of unauthenticated connections allowed by the SSH daemon. Setting a limit on authentication attempts helps reduce the risk of denial-of-service attacks. The recommended value is 10:30:60, but it can be adjusted according to the site’s security policy.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the SSH (Secure Shell) service 2. Root access to edit the configuration file
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the SSH configuration file using the command: nano /etc/ssh/sshd_config. 2. Locate or add the line MaxStartups 10:30:60, then save the changes and exit the editor. 3. Restart the SSH service to apply the changes using the command: systemctl restart sshd.

	<p>4. Verify the changes with the command: <code>sshd -T grep maxstartups</code>.</p> <p>5. Ensure the output shows the MaxStartups value set to the desired setting, for example, MaxStartups 10:30:60.</p>
Test Data	File /etc/ssh/sshd_config
Expectation	The system limits the number of unauthenticated connections accepted by the SSH daemon according to the configured parameter such as MaxStartups 10:30:60.
Actual Result	The MaxStartups parameter has been configured with the value 10:30:60, and the SSHD service has been reloaded and is running normally.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.95 Rule ID 28650

Based on Table 2.95, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28650.

```

GNU nano 6.2 sshd_config *
# PasswordAuthentication. Depending on your PAM configuration,
# PAM authentication via KbdInteractiveAuthentication may bypass
# the setting of "PermitRootLogin without-password".
# If you just want the PAM account and session checks to run without
# PAM authentication, then enable this but set PasswordAuthentication
# and KbdInteractiveAuthentication to 'no'.
UsePAM yes

#AllowAgentForwarding yes
AllowTcpForwarding no
#GatewayPorts no
X11Forwarding no
#X11DisplayOffset 10
#X11UseLocalhost yes
#PermitTTY yes
PrintMotd no
#PrintLastLog yes
#TCPKeepAlive yes
#PermitUserEnvironment no
#Compression delayed
#ClientAliveInterval 0
#ClientAliveCountMax 3
#UseDNS no
#PidFile /run/sshd.pid
MaxStartups 10:30:60
#PermitTunnel no
#ChrootDirectory none
#VersionAddendum none

```

Figure 2.265 Configuration Rule ID 28650

Based on Figure 2.265, Configuration has been done on the “sshd_config” file by adding or editing the “MaxStartups 10:30:60” parameter.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28650	Ensure SSH MaxStartups is configured.	Command: sshd -T	Passed

Figure 2.266 Status Rule ID 28650

Based on Figure 2.266, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28650 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28652

Title	Ensure SSH LoginGraceTime is set to one minute or less.
Description	The LoginGraceTime parameter defines the amount of time allowed for successful authentication to the SSH server. The longer the time allowed, the longer unauthenticated connections can remain active. To minimize the risk of brute-force attacks and limit the number of unauthenticated connections, the LoginGraceTime should be set to a low value. The recommended setting is 60 seconds (1 minute), but this value can be adjusted according to site policy.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the SSH (Secure Shell) service 2. Root access to edit the configuration file
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the SSH configuration file with the command: nano /etc/ssh/sshd_config. 2. Locate or add the line LoginGraceTime 60, then save the changes and exit the editor. 3. Restart the SSH service to apply the changes using: systemctl restart sshd. 4. Verify the changes with the command: sshd -T grep logingracetime. 5. Ensure the output shows the LoginGraceTime value as recommended, i.e., LoginGraceTime 60.
Test Data	File /etc/ssh/sshd_config
Expectation	The allowed authentication time for SSH does not exceed 60 seconds, in accordance with the applicable policy.

Actual Result	The LoginGraceTime parameter has been configured with the value 60, so the allowed authentication time for SSH will not exceed 60 seconds.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.96 Rule ID 28652

Based on Table 2.96, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28652.

```

GNU nano 6.2 sshd_config *
#ListenAddress ::

#HostKey /etc/ssh/ssh_host_rsa_key
#HostKey /etc/ssh/ssh_host_ecdsa_key
#HostKey /etc/ssh/ssh_host_ed25519_key

# Ciphers and keying
#RekeyLimit default none

# Logging
#SyslogFacility AUTH
#LogLevel INFO

# Authentication:
LoginGraceTime 1m
PermitRootLogin no
#StrictModes yes
MaxAuthTries 3
#MaxSessions 10

```

Figure 2.267 Configuration Rule ID 28652

Based on Figure 2.267, Configuration has been done on the “sshd_config” file by adding the “LoginGraceTime 1m” parameter.

ID ^	Title	Target	Result
28652	Ensure SSH LoginGraceTime is set to one minute or less.	Command: sshd -T	Passed

Figure 2.268 Status Rule ID 28652

Based on Figure 2.268, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28652 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28653

Title	Ensure SSH Idle Timeout Interval is configured.
Description	The parameters ClientAliveInterval and ClientAliveCountMax are used to configure the timeout period for inactive SSH connections. If connections remain

	<p>open indefinitely, this can lead to resource exhaustion or can be exploited for DDoS attacks. The ClientAliveCountMax value must be greater than zero for SSH to close inactive connections after the specified number of "client alive" messages. The recommended settings are ClientAliveInterval of 15 seconds and ClientAliveCountMax of 3 to terminate the connection after 45 seconds of no response. Be sure to check site policies for timeout settings and apply them accordingly.</p>
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system uses the SSH (Secure Shell) service 2. Root access to edit the configuration file
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the SSH configuration file using the command: nano /etc/ssh/sshd_config. 2. Locate or add the lines ClientAliveInterval 15 and ClientAliveCountMax 3, then save the changes and exit the editor. 3. Restart the SSH service to apply changes with: systemctl restart sshd. 4. Verify the changes using the command: sshd -T grep clientalive. 5. Ensure the output shows the values ClientAliveInterval 15 and ClientAliveCountMax 3.
Test Data	File /etc/ssh/sshd_config
Expectation	The timeout period for inactive connections does not exceed 45 seconds, in accordance with the applied policy.
Actual Result	The parameters ClientAliveInterval and ClientAliveCountMax have been configured in the sshd_config file to enforce a 45-second timeout. Therefore, the connection timeout will not exceed the applied limit.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.97. Rule ID 28653

Based on Table 2.97, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28653.

```

GNU nano 6.2 sshd_config *
# Set this to 'yes' to enable PAM authentication, account processing,
# and session processing. If this is enabled, PAM authentication will
# be allowed through the KbdInteractiveAuthentication and
# PasswordAuthentication. Depending on your PAM configuration,
# PAM authentication via KbdInteractiveAuthentication may bypass
# the setting of "PermitRootLogin without-password".
# If you just want the PAM account and session checks to run without
# PAM authentication, then enable this but set PasswordAuthentication
# and KbdInteractiveAuthentication to 'no'.
UsePAM yes

#AllowAgentForwarding yes
AllowTcpForwarding no
#GatewayPorts no
X11Forwarding no
#X11DisplayOffset 10
#X11UseLocalhost yes
#PermitTTY yes
PrintMotd no
#PrintLastLog yes
#TCPKeepAlive yes
#PermitUserEnvironment no
#Compression delayed
ClientAliveInterval 15
ClientAliveCountMax 3
#UseDNS no
#PidFile /run/sshd.pid

```

Figure 2.269 Configuration Rule ID 28653

Based on Figure 2.269, Configuration has been done on the “sshd_config” file by adding the parameters “ClientAliveInterval 15” & “ClientAliveCountMax 3”.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28653	Ensure SSH Idle Timeout Interval is configured.	Command: sshd -T	Passed

Figure 2.270 Status Rule ID 28653

Based on Figure 2.270, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28653 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28656

Title	Ensure sudo log file exists.
Description	Logging sudo commands is crucial for audit and security purposes. By enabling a log file for sudo, all commands executed with sudo privileges will be recorded in a specific log file, facilitating monitoring and tracing in case of security incidents. Adding the logfile setting in the sudo configuration file ensures that all sudo commands are properly logged.

Prerequisite	Root access to edit the configuration file
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the sudo configuration file using the command: <code>nano /etc/sudoers</code>. Locate the line: <code>Defaults logfile="/var/log/sudo.log"</code>. 2. If the line is not found, add <code>Defaults logfile="/var/log/sudo.log"</code> to the sudoers file. 3. Save the changes and exit the editor. 4. Verify the existence of the sudo.log file with the command: <code>ls -l /var/log/sudo.log</code>.
Test Data	File <code>/var/log/sudo.log</code>
Expectation	The log file specified in the sudoers configuration must exist and be accessible, and every command executed using sudo must be recorded in the specified log file.
Actual Result	The sudoers configuration has been applied, verification shows that the sudo.log file exists and is accessible, and every sudo command is recorded in the specified log file.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.98 Rule ID 28656

Based on Table 2.98, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28656.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/sudoers
# This file MUST be edited with the 'visudo' command as root.
#
# Please consider adding local content in /etc/sudoers.d/ instead of
# directly modifying this file.
#
# See the man page for details on how to write a sudoers file.
#
Defaults    env_reset
Defaults    mail_badpass
Defaults    secure_path="/usr/local/sbin:/usr/local/bin:/usr/sbin:/usr/bin:/sbin:/bin:/snap/bin"
Defaults    use_pty
Defaults    logfile="/var/log/sudo.log"

```

Figure 2.271 Configuration Rule ID 28656

Based on Figure 2.271, the Configuration parameter is added, namely “`logfile="/var/log/sudo.log"`” in the “`/etc/sudoers`” file.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28656	Ensure sudo log file exists.	File: <code>/etc/sudoers</code>	● Passed

Figure 2.272 Status Rule ID 28656

Based on Figure 2.272, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28656 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28660

Title	Ensure access to the su command is restricted.
Description	The su command allows users to execute commands or open a shell as another user. However, using sudo provides more granular access control over privileged actions. sudo also offers better logging and auditing capabilities than su, which only logs that a user invoked the su command. By restricting access to the su command and directing privilege escalation through sudo, system administration can better control user privilege escalation. This restriction can be implemented by using a specific group that is permitted to run the su command.
Prerequisite	Root access to edit the su configuration file
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Create an empty group for specific users allowed to use su with the command: <code>groupadd sugroup</code>. 2. Edit the configuration file <code>/etc/pam.d/su</code> using: <code>nano /etc/pam.d/su</code>. 3. Add the line: <code>auth required pam_wheel.so use_uid group=sugroup</code>. 4. Save the changes and exit the text editor.
Test Data	File <code>/etc/pam.d/su</code>
Expectation	Users not listed in the group sugroup are not allowed to use the su command.
Actual Result	The configuration in <code>/etc/pam.d/su</code> has been updated; only users in the sugroup group can execute the su command.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.99. Rule ID 28660

Based on Table 99, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28660.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/pam.d/su *
#
# The PAM configuration file for the Shadow `su' service
#
# This allows root to su without passwords (normal operation)
auth sufficient pam_rootok.so
# Uncomment this to force users to be a member of group wheel
# before they can use `su'. You can also add "group=foo"
# to the end of this line if you want to use a group other
# than the default "wheel" (but this may have side effect of
# denying "root" user, unless she's a member of "foo" or explicitly
# permitted earlier by e.g. "sufficient pam_rootok.so").
# (Replaces the `SU WHEEL ONLY' option from login.defs)
auth required pam_wheel.so use_uid group=sugroup

```

Figure 2.273 Configuration Rule ID 28660

Based on Figure 2.273, Configuration is added to the /etc/pam.d/su file with the parameter “auth required pam_wheel.so use_uid group=sugroup”. The purpose of adding the Configuration is so that only users in the “sugroup” group can execute the su command.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28660	Ensure access to the su command is restricted.	File: /etc/pam.d/su	Passed

Figure 2.274 Status Rule ID 28660

Based on Figure 2.274, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28660 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28661

Title	Ensure password creation requirements are configured.
Description	Strong passwords protect the system from brute force attacks. Proper password policy settings, such as minimum length and character complexity, improve system security by ensuring passwords are harder to guess or crack. To enforce an appropriate password policy, you can configure the pam_pwquality module, which checks password strength based on criteria like minimum length and character variety (uppercase letters, lowercase letters, numbers, special symbols).
Prerequisite	1. Root access to install the pam_pwquality service and edit the pwquality configuration file.

	2. Internet access to download the package.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the command <code>apt list --installed libpam-pwquality</code> to verify whether the package is installed. 2. If not installed, run <code>apt install libpam-pwquality</code>. 3. After installation, adjust the configuration in <code>/etc/security/pwquality.conf</code> by setting the parameters: <code>minlen = 14</code> <code>dcredit = -1</code> <code>ucredit = -1</code> <code>ocredit = -1</code> <code>minclass = 4</code> 4. Save the changes and exit the text editor.
Test Data	File <code>/etc/security/pwquality.conf</code>
Expectation	Passwords created must meet the length and complexity requirements according to the defined policy. The system should enforce the password length and complexity policy.
Actual Result	The pwquality package was successfully installed, and configuration adjustments in <code>pwquality.conf</code> have been made, such as <code>minlen = 14</code> (passwords must be at least 14 characters long) and <code>minclass = 4</code> (passwords must contain all four character classes: uppercase letters, lowercase letters, numbers, and symbols).
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.100 Rule ID 28661

Based on Table 2.100, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28661.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# apt install libpam-pwquality
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
The following additional packages will be installed:
 cracklib-runtime libcrack2 libpwquality-common libpwquality1 wamerican
The following NEW packages will be installed:
 cracklib-runtime libcrack2 libpam-pwquality libpwquality-common libpwquality1 wamerican
0 upgraded, 6 newly installed, 0 to remove and 41 not upgraded.
Need to get 448 kB of archives.
After this operation, 1,956 kB of additional disk space will be used.
Do you want to continue? [Y/n] y
Get:1 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy/main amd64 libcrack2 amd64 2.9.6-3.4build4 [29.6 kB]
Get:2 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy/main amd64 cracklib-runtime amd64 2.9.6-3.4build4 [149 kB]
Get:3 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy/main amd64 libpwquality-common all 1.4.4-1build2 [7,642 B]
Get:4 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy/main amd64 libpwquality1 amd64 1.4.4-1build2 [13.4 kB]
Get:5 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy/main amd64 libpam-pwquality amd64 1.4.4-1build2 [11.8 kB]
Get:6 http://id.archive.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy/main amd64 wamerican all 2020.12.07-2 [236 kB]
Fetched 448 kB in 3s (168 kB/s)

```

Figure 2.275 Install Libpam

Based on Figure 2.275, install the libpam-pwquality package with the command “apt install libpam-pwquality”

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/security/pwquality.conf *
# Configuration for systemwide password quality limits
# Defaults:
#
# Number of characters in the new password that must not be present in the
# old password.
# difok = 1
#
# Minimum acceptable size for the new password (plus one if
# credits are not disabled which is the default). (See pam_cracklib manual.)
# Cannot be set to lower value than 6.
minlen = 14
#
# The maximum credit for having digits in the new password. If less than 0
# it is the minimum number of digits in the new password.
dcredit = -1
#
# The maximum credit for having uppercase characters in the new password.
# If less than 0 it is the minimum number of uppercase characters in the new
# password.
uccredit = -1
#
# The maximum credit for having lowercase characters in the new password.
# If less than 0 it is the minimum number of lowercase characters in the new
# password.
lccredit = -1
#
# The maximum credit for having other characters in the new password.
# If less than 0 it is the minimum number of other characters in the new
# password.
occredit = -1
#
# The minimum number of required classes of characters for the new
# password (digits, uppercase, lowercase, others).
minclass = 4
#

```

Figure 2.276 Configuration Rule ID 28661

Based on Figure 2.276, Configuration adjustments have been made to pwquality.conf, such as minlen = 14, which means the password must have a minimum character length of 14, minclass = 4, the password must contain all four character classes such as uppercase letters, lowercase letters, numbers and symbols.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28661	Ensure password creation requirements are configured.	Command: apt list --installed libpam-pwquality	Passed

Figure 2.277 Status Rule ID 28661

Based on Figure 2.277, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28661 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28662

Title	Ensure lockout for failed password attempts is configured.
Description	Implementing account lockout after a number of consecutive failed login attempts to prevent brute force attacks. By configuring lockout, the system can protect accounts from unauthorized login attempts by limiting the number of failed login attempts within a certain time period.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. System uses PAM (Pluggable Authentication Modules) 2. Root access to configure PAM
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In the configuration file <code>/etc/pam.d/common-auth</code>, add the following parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <code>auth required pam_faillock.so preauth</code> - <code>auth [success=1 default=ignore] pam_unix.so nullok</code> - <code>auth [default=die] pam_faillock.so authfail</code> - <code>auth sufficient pam_faillock.so authsucc</code> 2. In the file <code>/etc/pam.d/common-account</code>, add the parameter: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <code>account required pam_faillock.so</code> 3. Configure the file <code>/etc/security/faillock.conf</code> with the parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <code>deny = 4</code> - <code>fail_interval = 900</code> - <code>unlock_time = 600</code>
Test Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - File <code>/etc/pam.d/common-auth</code> - File <code>/etc/pam.d/common-account</code> - File <code>/etc/security/faillock.conf</code>

Expectation	After this configuration, if an account fails to log in 4 times within 900 seconds (15 minutes), the account will be locked and can be unlocked after 600 seconds (10 minutes).
Actual Result	Configuration has been applied to the files common-auth, common-account, and faillock.conf. The system will lock any user account that fails to log in 4 times within 900 seconds, and the account will be automatically unlocked after 600 seconds (10 minutes).
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.101 Rule ID 28662

Based on Table 2.101, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28662.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/security/faillock.conf *
# Don't log informative messages via syslog.
# Enabled if option is present.
# no_log_info
#
# Only track failed user authentications attempts for local users
# in /etc/passwd and ignore centralized (AD, IdM, LDAP, etc.) users.
# The `faillock` command will also no longer track user failed
# authentication attempts. Enabling this option will prevent a
# double-lockout scenario where a user is locked out locally and
# in the centralized mechanism.
# Enabled if option is present.
# local_users_only
#
# Deny access if the number of consecutive authentication failures
# for this user during the recent interval exceeds n tries.
# The default is 3.
deny = 4
#
# The length of the interval during which the consecutive
# authentication failures must happen for the user account
# lock out is <replaceable>n</replaceable> seconds.
# The default is 900 (15 minutes).
fail_interval = 900
#
# The access will be re-enabled after n seconds after the lock out.
# The value 0 has the same meaning as value `never` - the access
# will not be re-enabled without resetting the faillock
# entries by the `faillock` command.
# The default is 600 (10 minutes).
unlock_time = 600
#
# Root account can become locked as well as regular accounts.
# Enabled if option is present.
# even_deny_root

```

Figure 2.278 Configuration Rule ID 28662

Based on Figure 2.278, Configuration is done on the file “/etc/security/faillock.conf” with the parameters “deny = 4”, “fail_interval = 900”, and “unlock_time = 600”, with the explanation that the maximum failed attempt is 4 times within a time span of 15 minutes and the account will be locked within 10 minutes if the login fails 4 times within 15 minutes..

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28662	Ensure lockout for failed password attempts is configured.	File: /etc/pam.d/common-auth	Passed

Figure 2.279 Status Rule ID 28662

Based on Figure 2.279, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28662 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

- Rule ID 28663

Title	Ensure password reuse is limited.
Description	Restricting reuse of old passwords aims to enhance account security by forcing users to create new passwords different from their previous ones. This policy makes accounts more resilient against compromise attempts through guessing or theft of old passwords.
Prerequisite	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. System uses PAM (Pluggable Authentication Modules) 2. Root access to configure PAM
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In the configuration file <code>/etc/pam.d/common-password</code>, ensure the following configuration is present: <pre>password [success=1 default=ignore] pam_unix.so obscure use_authtok try_first_pass yescrypt remember=5</pre> 2. If the configuration is missing, add it to <code>common-password</code>. 3. Save the changes and exit the text editor.
Test Data	File <code>/etc/pam.d/common-password</code>
Expectation	Users should not be able to set a new password identical to any of their last 5 used passwords.
Actual Result	Configuration has been applied in the <code>common-password</code> file, and users cannot create a new password that matches any of their last 5 previously used passwords.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.102 Rule ID 28663

Based on Table 2.102, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28663.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/pam.d/common-password *
#
# /etc/pam.d/common-password - password-related modules common to all services
#
# This file is included from other service-specific PAM config files,
# and should contain a list of modules that define the services to be
# used to change user passwords. The default is pam_unix.

# Explanation of pam_unix options:
# The "yescrypt" option enables
#hashed passwords using the yescrypt algorithm, introduced in Debian
#11. Without this option, the default is Unix crypt. Prior releases
#used the option "sha512"; if a shadow password hash will be shared
#between Debian 11 and older releases replace "yescrypt" with "sha512"
#for compatibility. The "obscure" option replaces the old
# 'OBSCURE_CHECKS_ENAB' option in login.defs. See the pam_unix manpage
#for other options.

# As of pam 1.0.1-6, this file is managed by pam-auth-update by default.
# To take advantage of this, it is recommended that you configure any
# local modules either before or after the default block, and use
# pam-auth-update to manage selection of other modules. See
# pam-auth-update(8) for details.

# here are the per-package modules (the "Primary" block)
password requisite pam_pwquality.so retry=3
password [success=1 default=ignore] pam_unix.so obscure use_authtok try_first_pass yescrypt remember=5
# here's the fallback if no module succeeds
password requisite pam_deny.so
# prime the stack with a positive return value if there isn't one already;
# this avoids us returning an error just because nothing sets a success code
# since the modules above will each just jump around
password required pam_permit.so
# and here are more per-package modules (the "Additional" block)
# end of pam-auth-update config

```

Figure 2.280 Configuration Rule ID 28663

Based on Figure 2.280, Configuration has been done on the file “/etc/pam.d/common-password” with the parameter “remember=5”, so that users cannot create a new password that is the same as one of the 5 most recently used passwords.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28663	Ensure password reuse is limited.	File: /etc/pam.d/common-password	Passed

Figure 2.281 Status Rule ID 28663

Based on Figure 2.281, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28663 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28664

Title	Ensure password hashing algorithm is up to date with the latest standards.
Description	Using the latest hashing algorithms such as yescrypt enhances password storage security. This algorithm is stronger compared to older ones like SHA-512 or MD5, making password cracking attempts significantly more difficult.
Prerequisite	1. System uses PAM (Pluggable Authentication Modules) 2. Root access to configure PAM

Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the configuration file <code>/etc/login.defs</code> and locate the line <code>ENCRYPT_METHOD</code>. Ensure it is set to <code>yescrypt</code>. 2. If the value is different, edit the file <code>/etc/login.defs</code> and change the line to: <code>ENCRYPT_METHOD yescrypt</code> 3. Save the changes and exit the text editor. 4. Verify that <code>/etc/pam.d/common-password</code> does not use outdated hashing algorithms such as <code>md5</code>, <code>sha256</code>, <code>sha512</code>, <code>blowfish</code>, etc
Test Data	File <code>/etc/login.defs</code>
Expectation	The encryption method in <code>/etc/login.defs</code> should be set to <code>ENCRYPT_METHOD yescrypt</code> .
Actual Result	The encryption method used in <code>/etc/login.defs</code> is set to <code>yescrypt</code> , and no outdated hashing algorithms (<code>md5</code> , <code>sha256</code> , <code>sha512</code> , <code>blowfish</code> , etc.) are used in <code>/etc/pam.d/common-password</code> .
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.103 Rule ID 28664

Based on Table 2.103, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28664.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/login.defs *
# If set to "yes", new passwords will be encrypted using the MD5-based
# algorithm compatible with the one used by recent releases of FreeBSD.
# It supports passwords of unlimited length and longer salt strings.
# Set to "no" if you need to copy encrypted passwords to other systems
# which don't understand the new algorithm. Default is "no".
#
# This variable is deprecated. You should use ENCRYPT_METHOD.
#
#MD5_CRYPT_ENAB no
#
# If set to MD5 , MD5-based algorithm will be used for encrypting password
# If set to SHA256, SHA256-based algorithm will be used for encrypting password
# If set to SHA512, SHA512-based algorithm will be used for encrypting password
# If set to DES, DES-based algorithm will be used for encrypting password (default)
# Overrides the MD5_CRYPT_ENAB option
#
# Note: It is recommended to use a value consistent with
# the PAM modules configuration.
#
ENCRYPT_METHOD yescrypt
#

```

Figure 2.282 Configuration Rule ID 28664

Based on Figure 2.282, changes were made to the Configuration in the “/etc/login.defs” file with the “ENCRYPT_METHOD yescrypt” parameter.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28664	Ensure password hashing algorithm is up to date with the latest standards.	File: /etc/pam.d/common-password	● Passed

Figure 2.283 Status Rule ID 28664

Based on Figure 2.283, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28664 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”..

- Rule ID 28665

Title	Ensure minimum days between password changes is configured.
Description	Setting the minimum number of days between password changes aims to prevent users from repeatedly changing their passwords in a short period to bypass password reuse restrictions. It is recommended to set a minimum of 1 day between password changes.
Prerequisite	Root access to edit the login configuration file.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the configuration file /etc/login.defs and look for the parameter PASS_MIN_DAYS. 2. If it is not found, add or edit the parameter to: PASS_MIN_DAYS 1 3. Save the changes and exit the text editor.
Test Data	File /etc/login.defs
Expectation	The PASS_MIN_DAYS parameter in /etc/login.defs is set to 1 day.
Actual Result	Users can only change their password once per day. This is confirmed by the configuration of PASS_MIN_DAYS 1 in /etc/login.defs, and can be verified by checking the fifth field in the /etc/shadow file, which reflects the value 1.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.104 Rule ID 28665

Based on Table 2.104, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28665.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/login.defs *
# HOME_MODE is used by useradd(8) and newusers(8) to set the mode for new
# home directories.
# If HOME_MODE is not set, the value of UMASK is used to create the mode.
HOME_MODE    0750

#
# Password aging controls:
#
#     PASS_MAX_DAYS   Maximum number of days a password may be used.
#     PASS_MIN_DAYS   Minimum number of days allowed between password changes.
#     PASS_WARN_AGE   Number of days warning given before a password expires.
#
PASS_MAX_DAYS 99999
PASS_MIN_DAYS 1
PASS_WARN_AGE 7

```

Figure 2.284 Configuration Rule ID 28665

Based on Figure 2.284, a change was made to the parameter for “PASS_MIN_DAYS 1” in the /etc/login.defs file, to limit the minimum days for changing the password.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28665	Ensure minimum days between password changes is configured.	File: /etc/login.defs	Passed

Figure 2.285 Status Rule ID 28665

Based on Figure 2.285, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28665 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28666

Title	Ensure password expiration is 365 days or less.
Description	Limiting the maximum age of a password to 365 days or less aims to reduce the window of opportunity for attackers to exploit compromised credentials or perform brute force attacks. This setting ensures users change their passwords regularly to enhance system security.
Prerequisite	Root access to edit the login configuration file.
Testing Step	1. Open the configuration file /etc/login.defs and look for the parameter PASS_MAX_DAYS. 2. If it is not found, add or edit the parameter to: PASS_MAX_DAYS 365

	3. Save the changes and exit the text editor
Test Data	File /etc/login.defs
Expectation	The maximum password age for a user is configured in /etc/login.defs to a maximum of 365 days. If a password exceeds 365 days, it will expire, and the user will be prompted to create a new password.
Actual Result	The maximum password age for a user has been configured in the file /etc/login.defs with the parameter PASS_MAX_DAYS 365 and can be verified in the sixth field of the /etc/shadow file, which reflects the value 365.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.105 Rule ID 28666

Based on Table 2.105, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28666.

```

GNU nano 6.2 /etc/login.defs *
# UMASK is the default umask value for pam_umask and is used by
# useradd and newusers to set the mode of the new home directories.
# 022 is the "historical" value in Debian for UMASK
# 027, or even 077, could be considered better for privacy
# There is no One True Answer here : each sysadmin must make up his/her
# mind.
#
# If USERGROUPS_ENAB is set to "yes", that will modify this UMASK default value
# for private user groups, i. e. the uid is the same as gid, and username is
# the same as the primary group name: for these, the user permissions will be
# used as group permissions, e. g. 022 will become 002.
#
# Prefix these values with "0" to get octal, "0x" to get hexadecimal.
#
ERASECHAR      0177
KILLCHAR       025
UMASK          022

# HOME_MODE is used by useradd(8) and newusers(8) to set the mode for new
# home directories.
# If HOME_MODE is not set, the value of UMASK is used to create the mode.
HOME_MODE      0750

#
# Password aging controls:
#
#     PASS_MAX_DAYS   Maximum number of days a password may be used.
#     PASS_MIN_DAYS   Minimum number of days allowed between password changes.
#     PASS_WARN_AGE   Number of days warning given before a password expires.
#
PASS_MAX_DAYS  365
PASS_MIN_DAYS   1
PASS_WARN_AGE   7

```

Figure 2 286 Configuration Rule ID 28666

Based on Figure 2.286, changes were made to the Configuration parameter “PASS_MAX_DAYS 365” in the “/etc/login.defs” file, so that a user’s password expiration will be applied within 365 days.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# chage -l Ilham-WazuhAgent
Last password change           : Mar 10, 2025
Password expires               : Mar 10, 2026
Password inactive              : Mar 10, 2027
Account expires                : never
Minimum number of days between password change : 1
Maximum number of days between password change : 365
Number of days of warning before password expires : 7

```

Figure 2.287 Password Expired

Based on Figure 2.287, it can be seen that “Password expires” is 365 days from the time the password was last changed, namely March 10, 2026.

ID ↑	Title	Target	Result
28666	Ensure password expiration is 365 days or less.	File: /etc/login.defs	Passed

Figure 2.288 Status Rule ID 28666

Based on Figure 2.288, the Configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28666 policy, so that the final status changes to “Passed”.

- Rule ID 28668

Title	Ensure inactive password lock is 30 days or less.
Description	User accounts that remain inactive after password expiration can become security risks because users may not notice failed login attempts or suspicious activities. Therefore, it is recommended to automatically lock accounts that have been inactive for more than 30 days after password expiration.
Prerequisite	Root access to edit the login configuration file.
Testing Step	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run the command <code>useradd -D</code> and verify that the INACTIVE value is 30 or less. 2. Check the <code>/etc/shadow</code> file, focusing on the 7th field (inactive). Ensure the value is 30 days or less. 3. If any user has an INACTIVE value greater than 30 days, reset it to 30 using the command: <code>chage --inactive 30 <user></code>
Test Data	INACTIVE value from <code>useradd -D</code> output
Expectation	Every user in <code>/etc/shadow</code> has an inactive period of a maximum of 30 days or less after the password expiration.

Actual Result	Configuration has been applied such that when a user's password expires, the inactive period is set to a maximum of 30 days after the password expiration begins.
Test Status	<i>Passed</i>

Table 2.106 Rule ID 28668

Based on Table 2.106, this is an explanation of further information related to Rule ID 28668.

```

root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# chage --inactive 30 Ilham-WazuhAgent
root@WazuhAgent-UbuntuServer:/home/Ilham-WazuhAgent# chage -l Ilham-WazuhAgent
Last password change           : Mar 10, 2025
Password expires               : Mar 10, 2026
Password inactive              : Apr 09, 2026
Account expires                : never
Minimum number of days between password change : 1
Maximum number of days between password change : 365
Number of days of warning before password expires : 7

```

Figure 2.289 Configuration Rule ID 28668

Based on Figure 2.289, the command “—inactive -D <user>” is used to set the Password inactive time, if the user experiences a password expiration, then there will be an inactive period, if the inactive period has passed, then the password will be locked.

ID	Title	Target	Result
28668	Ensure inactive password lock is 30 days or less.	Command: useradd -D	Passed

Figure 2.290 Status Rule ID 28668

Based on Figure 2.290, the configuration that has been carried out is in accordance with the Rule ID 28668 policy, so that the final status changes to "Passed".

2.3 Analysis and Evaluation

After the remediation process was carried out for all rules identified in the initial scan results, the next step was to analyze and evaluate the level of compliance based on the CIS Benchmark for Ubuntu Server 22.04. At this stage, it was found that not all rules could be implemented simultaneously due to overlapping functionalities between rules, differences in recommended tools, and configuration dependency conflicts. For example, Table 4.35 contains a rule that configures time synchronization services using *chrony*, while the rule in Table 4.36 uses *systemd-timesyncd*. Applying both simultaneously on a single system results in configuration conflicts and potential

duplication of functionality. Therefore, further analysis and evaluation of these rules were necessary.

Based on the analysis, simplification and selection of rules were performed according to the system context, functional requirements, and technical compatibility. Subsequently, an evaluation was conducted, resulting in nine system configuration cases that represent combinations of tools and firewalls which can operate without conflict, namely:

- Case 1, Iptables and Timesyncd
- Case 2, Nftables and Timesyncd
- Case 3, UFW and Timesyncd
- Case 4, Iptables and Chrony
- Case 5, Nftables and Chrony
- Case 6, UFW and Chrony
- Case 7, Iptables and NTP
- Case 8, Nftables and NTP
- Case 9, UFW and NTP

The following presents the results of rule simplification and selection based on the nine configuration cases that have been defined

ID	Title	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7	Case 8	Case 9
28545	Ensure chrony is running as user chrony.	Failed	Failed	Failed	OK	OK	OK	Failed	Failed	Failed
28546	Ensure chrony is enabled and running.	Failed	Failed	Failed	OK	OK	OK	Failed	Failed	Failed
28547	Ensure systemd-timesyncd is enabled and running.	OK	OK	OK	Failed	Failed	Failed	Failed	Failed	Failed
28548	Ensure ntp access control is configured.	Failed	Failed	Failed	Failed	Failed	Failed	OK	OK	OK
28549	Ensure ntp is running as user ntp.	Failed	Failed	Failed	Failed	Failed	Failed	OK	OK	OK

28550	Ensure ntp is enabled and running.	Failed	Failed	Failed	Failed	Failed	Failed	OK	OK	OK
28573	Ensure ufw is installed.	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK
28574	Ensure iptables-persistent is not installed with ufw.	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK
28575	Ensure ufw service is enabled.	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK
28576	Ensure ufw loopback traffic is configured.	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK
28577	Ensure ufw default deny firewall policy.	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK
28578	Ensure nftables is installed.	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed
28579	Ensure a nftables table exists.	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed
28580	Ensure nftables base chains exist.	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed
28581	Ensure nftables default deny firewall policy.	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed
28582	Ensure nftables service is enabled.	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed
28583	Ensure iptables packages are installed.	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed
28584	Ensure nftables is not installed with iptables.	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed
28585	Ensure ufw is uninstalled or disabled with iptables.	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed
28586	Ensure iptables default deny firewall policy.	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed
28587	Ensure iptables loopback traffic is configured.	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed
28588	Ensure ip6tables default deny firewall policy.	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed
28589	Ensure ip6tables loopback traffic is configured.	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed	OK	Failed	Failed

Table 2.107 Result Scenario

Table 2.107 presents the results of tool combinations that can be executed without conflict. For entries marked as “Failed,” the corresponding Rule ID cannot be applied in that specific case due to inherent conflicts and can therefore be categorized as “Not Applicable.” In contrast, entries marked as “OK” indicate that the Rule ID is applicable and can be implemented in the respective case.

Based on these nine cases, independent configurations were applied and subsequently re-scanned using the Wazuh Security Configuration Assessment (SCA) module, with the results as follows:

- Case 1, Iptables and Timesyncd

Figure 2.291 Iptables and Timesyncd

Based on Figure 2.291, it can be observed that the Iptables and Timesyncd configuration with a total of 167 Rule Passed including 8 optional rules used and 15 optional rules not used are categorized as Failed.

- Case 2, Nftables and Timesyncd

Figure 2.292 Nftables and Timesyncd

Based on Figure 2.292, it can be observed that the Nftables and Timesyncd configuration with a total of 165 Rule Passed including 6 optional rules used and 17 optional rules not used are categorized as Failed.

- Case 3, UFW and Timesyncd

Figure 2.293 UFW and Timesyncd

Based on Figure 2.293, it can be observed that the UFW and Timesyncd configuration with a total of 165 Rule Passed including 6 optional rules used and 17 optional rules not used are categorized as Failed.

- Case 4, Iptables and Chrony

Figure 2.294 Iptables and Chrony

Based on Figure 2.294, it can be observed that the Iptables and Chrony configuration with a total of 168 Rule Passed including 9 optional rules used and 14 optional rules not used are categorized as Failed.

- Case 5, Nftables and Chrony

Figure 2.295 Nftables and Chrony

Based on Figure 2.295, it can be observed that the Nftables and Chrony configuration with a total of 166 Rule Passed including 7 optional rules used and 16 optional rules not used are categorized as Failed.

- Case 6, UFW and Chrony

Figure 2.296 UFW and Chrony

Based on Figure 2.4.296, it can be observed that the Nftables and Timesyncd configuration with a total of 166 Rule Passed including 7 optional rules used and 16 optional rules not used are categorized as Failed.

- Case 7, Iptables and NTP

Figure 2.297 Iptables and NTP

Based on Figure 2.297, it can be observed that the Iptables and NTP configuration with a total of 169 Rule Passed including 10 optional rules used and 13 optional rules not used are categorized as Failed.

- Case 8, Nftables and NTP

Figure 2.298 Nftables and NTP

Based on Figure 2.298, it can be observed that the Nftables and NTP configuration with a total of 167 Rule Passed including 8 optional rules used and 15 optional rules not used are categorized as Failed.

- Case 9, UFW and NTP

Figure 2.299 UFW and NTP

Based on Figure 2.299, it can be observed that the UFW and NTP configuration with a total of 167 Rule Passed including 8 optional rules used and 15 optional rules not used are categorized as Failed.

2.4 Result Analysis and Evaluation

From the results of testing the nine cases, it can be seen in Table 2.107 that 23 rules were identified as potentially causing configuration conflicts or having duplicated functionalities. Therefore, the following presents the conclusions derived from the evaluation of these nine scenarios:

No.	Test Case	Rule ID Opsional yang digunakan	Rule ID Opsional yang tidak digunakan
1	Iptables dan Timesyncd	8	15
2	Nftables dan Timesyncd	6	17
3	UFW dan Timesyncd	6	17
4	Iptables dan Chrony	9	14
5	Nftables dan Chrony	7	16

6	UFW dan Chrony	7	16
7	Iptables dan NTP	10	13
8	Nftables dan NTP	8	15
9	UFW dan NTP	8	15
Total Opsional rule ID		23	
Total Independen rule ID		159	
Total Rule ID		182	

Table 2.108 Summary Scenario

Based on Table 2.108, it can be concluded that out of a total of 182 Rule IDs, 159 are categorized as independent rules, while 23 are categorized as optional rules. Independent rules refer to configurations that can be implemented without relying on other configurations or causing system conflicts. Optional rules, on the other hand, are those that have the potential to overlap with other rules, either in terms of functionality or system configuration.

2.5 Conclusion

Based on the results of the installation, remediation, analysis, and evaluation processes, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The simulation of Security Configuration Assessment (SCA) on Ubuntu Server 22.04 was conducted through several stages, including the preparation of hardware and software, system installation, and configuration of the Wazuh Security Configuration Assessment (SCA) module. After completing the installation and configuration, an initial scan was performed on the system in its default, unhardened state. The initial scan results indicated a compliance level of only 41% with the CIS Benchmark for Ubuntu Server 22.04, as shown in Figure 2.15, with 76 rules marked as passed and 106 as failed. This result demonstrates that the default configuration of Ubuntu Server 22.04 contains numerous security gaps that do not meet the recommended standards of the CIS Benchmark.
2. In implementing all CIS Benchmark rules for Ubuntu Server 22.04, it was found that not all rules could be applied simultaneously. Several challenges were encountered, including overlapping functionalities between rules, the use of different tools for the same purpose, and dependency conflicts between configurations. For example, Table 2.35 includes a rule that configures time synchronization services using *chrony*, while Table 2.36 uses *systemd-timesyncd*, which also manages time synchronization. Due to such challenges, an evaluation was conducted to simplify and select rules relevant to the system context, functionality, and compatibility. Based on Table 2.107, nine system configuration cases were created, each representing a combination of tools that can operate without causing conflicts or functional duplication.
3. Based on the testing results of the nine scenarios in Table 2.108, the evaluation shows that out of 182 CIS Benchmark rules, 23 are categorized as optional and

159 as independent. From the nine configuration scenarios, the compliance level can be considered as having reached 100% with the applicable CIS Benchmark. This is because the rules marked as “Failed” in the test results were optional rules that were not applied in the respective scenarios. Remediating these unused optional rules simultaneously may lead to potential conflicts or overlaps with other Rule IDs.